

Internet of Things Architecture

IoT-A

Project Deliverable *D1.1* - SOTA report on existing integration frameworks/architectures for WSN, RFID and other emerging IoT related Technologies

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Executive Summary

The focus of Deliverable D1.1 is the collection of the state of the art on a broad set of technologies that belong to the Internet of Things area. The report includes contributions by all the technical work packages of the IoT-A project, in order to take into account all the research fields that have an impact on the architecture definition. Even though the concept of Internet of Things is well established, there still remains some grey zones in the definition of which technology are included and which have to be taken out from the framework in order not to pose a too strict limit to the system.

The document structure follows the activity organization of the project itself: each of the technical work packages provided a section of this report, namely WP1 addressed the existing architecture and framework solutions in Section 1, WP2 addressed the latest modelling techniques for IoT in Section 2, WP3 provided a survey on the communication protocols in Section 3, WP4 tackled the identification and resolution framework in Section 4, and WP5 contributed with an overview of the available IoT object platforms. Finally a security and privacy section is provided at the end of the document.

All sections except the fifth one are further split in three main subsections devoted to public projects, commercial products and standardization activities, respectively. Since section 5 has to describe hardware related topics, it is organized in four parts: a hardware survey, lower layers protocols that are tightly coupled with the hardware, operating systems and security.

Besides a thorough list of IoT available technologies, this report provides the reader with a first evaluation of what is today and what can be tomorrow the IoT universe: without claiming of being exhaustive, this document highlights which solution will be central in the definition of the IoT architecture and which, instead, will be marginal if not a burden for the system.

In order to maintain the size of this report acceptable, it has been decided to include here only the main parts of the entire state of the art collected by the different WPs.

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1. Architecture Frameworks and Solutions

The aim of this section is to provide a comprehensive overview on the different approaches for defining an architecture for the Internet of Things (IoT). In particular, three main categories have been investigated: 1) solutions provided by public projects such as those of the FP7 of the European Commission, 2) solutions derived from existing commercial products, and 3) standardization attempts from different standardization bodies.

In order to provide coherent description of heterogeneous topics, the section is organized in tables addressing a set of features, which are deemed relevant for the definition of a unified reference architecture for the IoT. These features are:

- Architecture description: addressing how the architecture view is provided in the related project/product/standard
- Architecture style: addressing the main style governing the structure of the architecture
- Information model and distribution: addressing how the information is treated by the project/product/standard and how it is distributed in the system and how it is made accessible
- Horizontality: refers to the capability of the system of re-using the same building blocks for providing many different upper layer functionalities. For instance, horizontality applies to a framework providing virtual services for building applications
- Context awareness and semantic capabilities: refers to the possibility of enhancing the information exchanged through the system with descriptors, which enable data to be categorized and complex queries to be answered
- Technological specificity and interoperability: addresses how much the project/product/standard is dependent on a particular technology and how it focus on interoperability
- Adaptation and self-*: addresses the capabilities offered by the project/product/standard in terms of reactivity to environmental changes

Finally, for each of the feature a relevance score is expressed. Scores can be one of the following: "--" stands for "the solution must be avoided in IoT systems", "-" stands for "the solution is not encouraged for IoT systems", "0" stands for "a system using this solution can be part of the IoT universe, but it is not advisable as a general guideline", "+" stands for "the solution offers a good contribution to the IoT universe" and "++" stands for "the solution is a must have for IoT systems and will be proposed as a guideline for the reference architecture". These relevance scores are provided by the editor of the specific sections and are meant to drive the discussion about which of the existing solutions have to become part of the IoT-A reference architecture.

1.1 Public project solutions

1.1.1 SENSEI

In order to realise the vision of Ambient Intelligence in a future network and service environment, heterogeneous wireless sensor and actuator networks (WS&AN) have to be integrated into a common framework of global scale and made available to services and applications via universal service interfaces. SENSEI creates an open, business driven architecture that fundamentally addresses the scalability problems for a large number of globally distributed WS&AN devices. It provides necessary network and information management services to enable reliable and accurate context information retrieval and interaction with the physical environment. By adding mechanisms for accounting, security, privacy and trust it enables an open and secure market space for context-awareness and real world interaction.

Tangible results of the SENSEI project are: 1) A highly scalable architectural framework with corresponding protocol solutions that enable easy plug and play integration of a large number of globally distributed WS&AN into a global system – providing support for network and information management, security, privacy and trust and accounting. 2) An open service interface and corresponding semantic specification to unify the access to context information and actuation services offered by the system for services and applications. 3) Efficient WS&AN island solutions consisting of a set of cross-optimised and energy aware protocol stacks including an ultra low power multi-mode transceiver targeting 5nJ/bit. 4) Pan European test platform, enabling large-scale experimental evaluation of the SENSEI results and execution of field trials - providing a tool for long term evaluation of WS&AN integration into the Future Internet.

1.1.1.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	The SENSEI architecture has been defined in two steps: firstly, it has been provided a reference architecture [5] analysing goals, principles, requirements and designing a functional decomposition and proposing a first realization. Subsequently, the architecture has been refined to its final aspect in [7]: the document specifies a component Architecture, the SENSEI Resource concept, SENSEI Support Services, System interactions, SENSEI Resource and information modelling.	Score: + SENSEI methodology cannot be used directly, but should be integrated with more general considerations, since the IoT-A scope is broader. However, the decisions adopted in SENSEI are still useful for IoT-A and must kept into account.
Architecture style	SENSEI architecture had to take into consideration the many different souls of the project, which asked for a combination of the main solutions. For instance the SENSEI architecture can be defined RESTful [5] in the WS&AN islands part of the system, while in the service/application the system become more service oriented [7]	Relevance score: + IoT-A should rely on the feedback from the SENSEI project partners when evaluating its architecture.
Information model and distribution	Information provided by resources in the SENSEI framework ranges from the raw data obtained from sensor nodes, the observation and measurement containing not only a value but also associated meta information about the data which is required by simple applications, to the high-level context required by more sophisticated applications and services. The Information Model addresses the coherent modelling of information on these three different abstraction levels and follows a layered approach: on top of the raw data an observation and measurement can be built and this can be used in the upper layer as part of the context information [4]. Information is provided by resources directly and can be cached across the network to lower the communication burden on the constrained devices and to fasten the gathering operations [7]. Information is accessible by looking up into resource directories which are accessible either directly for a particular element or semantically [5]	Relevance score: ++ Quite aligned with standardization activities and offers straightforward means for scalability support and semantic search.
Horizontality	Horizontality is supported by SENSEI with many solutions: at the lowest layer SENSEI decouples physical devices from software processes that are used to communicate with and control them. This allows to re-use the same software to control many physical devices and adds a sort of virtualization layer on top of the hardware [7]. Also, at the service level, SENSEI provides both means to semantically analyze queries and to dynamically compose services from single simpler routines. In such a way SENSEI can provide almost any needed application which is designable using the devices connected to the network [5]. Finally, SENSEI provides in-sensor routines	Relevance score: + Not every solution from SENSEI can be used in IoT-A as is, but they can be used as a starting point for discussion.

	for re-schedule the services running on sensor nodes and to reprogram a whole sensor island [8].	
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	<p>The higher level of the SENSEI Information Model deals with the modelling of Context Information about real world entities, like people, places or things. These real world entities are modelled through the concept of an Entity of Interest (Eoi). The model captures context redundancy and adds quality information about the context to allow methods to resolve context conflicts [4].</p> <p>The Semantic Query Resolver allows finding Resources stored in the Resource Directory without knowing their Identifiers based on semantic concepts. Resources are related to semantically annotated Entities of Interest and stored in the Entity Directory. Upon query by the Resource User the query will be analysed and the semantic concepts will be recognised. Then the Resource Directory and (if necessary) the Entity Directory will be searched for Resources matching the analysed semantic concepts. Furthermore it should be possible for the Resource User to query a particular Resource, too. The semantic concepts are taken from SENSEI's information model [4].</p>	Relevance score: + Very powerful and flexible, this model is only useable on the double resource/entity directories architecture.
Technological specificity and interoperability	<p>The SENSEI project aimed at, among its objectives, the interoperability of wireless smart objects. The main objects considered for the SENSEI network are described in [9] and several virtualization solutions have been chosen, such as the resource/process decoupling [7] and the dynamic services deploying [5].</p> <p>Also, the legacy technology interoperability has been analysed and dealt with in [6] developing plug and play services wrapping legacy interfaces in SENSEI-like APIs.</p>	Relevance score: + Good starting point, IoT-A needs to further broaden the scope of intelligent objects to be integrated.
Adaptation and self-*	<p>Adaptation and self-* properties of the SENSEI system are implemented at different levels of the system. The SENSEI native island provides functionalities to reprogram itself, update its functions and to reschedule its activities [8]. Services can be dynamically built on top on information sources and processing and actuating components [5]. The federated directory structure as well as the caching capabilities of the system provide solution for data persistency and robustness.</p>	Relevance score: 0 The particular in-island solutions must be used with care within IoT-A, since their integration needs a thorough analysis.

1.1.2 CASAGRAS

CASAGRAS (Coordination and Support Action (CSA) for Global RFID-related Activities and Standardisation) was a FP7 project that ended 30th June 2009 after 18 months. Its goal was to "...provide a framework of foundation studies to assist the European Commission and the global community in defining and accommodating international issues and developments concerning radio frequency identification (RFID) with particular reference to the emerging 'Internet of Things'."

CASAGRAS2 started in June 2010 and will end June 2012. The consortium consists of partners from Europe, the USA, China, Japan, Brazil and Korea. The stated goal is "To address the key international issues that are important in providing the foundations and co-operation necessary for realising the Internet of Things as a global initiative."

As a CSA, the project did not provide available technological output. Instead CASAGRAS project aim to collect, review and analyse current and emerging proposals and solutions in the IoT domain. Note that in this chapter, as CASAGRAS project is finished and CASAGRAS2 started only recently, we will refer to both, for they are both relevant albeit in different contexts.

1.1.2.1 Architecture relevance

CASAGRAS is mostly relevant because it is (probably) the first view on relevant topics of the IoT – such as architecture, features, and governance – that was born from an international analysis and discussion.

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	In the CASAGRAS inclusive model , three layers are identified beneath the Internet communication zone. 1. Physical Layer – where physical objects are identified and sensor data is delivered. According to the specific AIDC technology, objects could be organized in networks. In order to provide interoperability, an universal data capture appliance protocol (UDCAP) is envisioned. Each AIDC technology will use its own implementation of UDCAP 2. Interrogator-Gateway Layer – used to connect object-devices with information management systems 3. Information Management Systems – this layer provides the functional platform for supporting application and services	Relevance score: + First and organic commitment for defining an architecture model; it is though very different from IoT-A in that any interaction must pass through Information Management System which means that the “narrow waist” is at the service or application layer.
Architecture style	This reference architecture provides the basis for implementing distributed architectures. The logic though is not at the periphery of the network, which is only relegated to data acquisition tasks, but at its centre or at the Information Management System Layer	Relevance score: - The approach is different from the IoT-A one.
Information model and distribution	An Information Management System (IMS) component is present for all the AIDC technology implementation. The component manages access to information coming from the Interrogator-Gateway Layer (and thus from the Physical layer). The functionalities of this architectural component are only described, no implementation was/will be carried out in the frame of CASAGRAS or CASAGRAS2.	Relevance score: - The IMS is the narrow-waist of this architecture, which means it is at service/application layer, which, in turn, is a very different approach from the IOTA one.
Horizontality	n/a	Relevance score: 0
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	n/a	Relevance score: 0
Technological specificity and interoperability	CASAGRAS → RFID CASAGRAS2 → The project just started and it is difficult to assess specificity by now. It is though likely that there will be less specificity and more interoperability than in the previous project	Relevance score: 0 The focus is too much on RFID only
Adaptation and self-*	n/a	Relevance score: 0

SmartSantander proposes a unique in the world city-scale experimental research facility supporting typical applications and services for a smart city. The facility will be open to FIRE community and will provide an infrastructure for IoT experimentation at different levels (communication protocols, IoT architectures, services to end-users, etc.).

SmartSantander will provide access to around 20.000 IoT devices deployed mainly in the city of Santander but also in other places worldwide (Guilford, Belgrade, Australia, Lübeck, Aarhus, etc.). The project belongs to objective 1.6 of the FP7 started in September 2010 and will last for 3 years.

The project will provide the experimentation infrastructure and it will be based on the integration of three components: The SENSEI project, the WISEBED and a Platform provided by Telefonica called USN

1.1.3.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	Unknown	Score: -- It is still in the process
Architecture style	It provides solutions at different levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The support for controlling the IoT devices will be provided through a set of low-level APIS. • The support for running experiments will be provided through a portal. • The support for the application support will be provided through Web Services. 	Score: 0 Too early too judge.
Information model and distribution	The information model is still being defined, but it will be based on the SENSEI information model (see 1.1.1), the WISEBED information model (both capable of describing the IoT resources) and the OGC SensorML and O&M standards (see 1.3.4)	Score: 0 Same as SENSEI
Horizontality	Both SENSEI and USN have been designed to provide horizontal services.	Score: + Same as SENSEI
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	This is not the main focus of the project; even some of the SENSEI components provide support for Context-awareness.	Score: -- Not focusing on this
Technological specificity and interoperability	It is intended to provide experimentation support to verticality (technology specific) and to horizontality (technology independent).	Score:0 Nothing is currently defined.
Adaptation and self-*	Nothing currently defined	Score: -- Nothing is currently defined.

1.1.4 BRIDGE

The EPC Information Services are a role defined in EPCglobal Network Architecture Framework, which provide for storage and retrieval of filtered and processed information about different events within the supply-chain. The EPCIS offers two interfaces: one for query request and the other one for capture operations. The query interface allows trading partners to query information about any event data stored in the EPCIS-repository together with business context. However for such a decentralized architecture, since the complete information about an individual object may be fragmented across multiple organizations, there is a need for **secure** lookup services for locating all the providers of the fragments of information that constitute the complete supply-chain or lifecycle history for an object [18].

To enable RFID and EPCglobal standard solutions in practice, technical, social and educational constraints - particularly in the area of security must be overcome. BRIDGE (Building Radio frequency IDentification solutions for the Global Environment) addresses these problems by extending the EPC network architecture. This is done by researching, developing and implementing tools which will enable the deployment of EPCglobal applications in Europe. The "enablement" is mostly in the development of security apparatus, both in hardware, software and business practises. These aspects

are highlighted below - but note that the business aspects and the hardware aspects are outside the scope of this SOTA and are not discussed further in the document:

Network

- Serial-level lookup service to enable unique item level product information storage and retrieval
- Identification and authentication of tags and readers
- Data management of extremely large amounts of real-time data

Application Software

- Serial-level inventory management
- Management of large networks of EPC readers
- Models to exploit environmental data (temperature, humidity, etc)

Security

- Security for privacy and to prevent illicit use of EPC
- Prevention of cloning & emulation of tags in EPC
- Secure transmission of data between readers and tags

1.1.4.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	<p>One of the core aspects of BRIDGE related to IOT-A lies in the Discovery Service which manages the exchange of RFID and aggregated information between nodes [18]. The core of BRIDGE is communication centric is it addresses the problem of handling queries between distributed entities.</p> <p>The project partners of BRIDGE explicitly emphasize confidentiality over integrity and availability of data [20]. This is because the authors have identified confidentiality to be the prime barrier in getting acceptance of the EPCglobal standard for RFIDs.</p> <p>Security is achieved by: (1) Access Control and (2) Secure communication between entities by means of authentication, confidentiality and integrity (ACI) techniques.</p> <p>In BRIDGE, two architectures of the Discovery Service for lookup and resourcing were prototyped and tested. Their topologies and objectives are shown as follows [18][p. 87-94]. The BRIDGE authors note that the effort was concentrated on the synchronous "resources of information" approach. [19][p. 12]</p> <p>"Synchronous Resources of Information Model" - information is provided by resources of information.</p> <p>"Query Relay Model" - the DS is limited to a filter of queries that are answered by end resources</p>	<p>Relevance score: +</p> <p>This project describes potential candidate in look-up methods for allowing client entities in IOT-A to choose how much information to disclose [WP4]</p>
Architecture style	<p>BRIDGE describes itself as being "distributed" with the following characteristics: modular, flexible, remoteness, concurrency, lack of global state, heterogeneous, autonomous, and mobile</p> <p>RFID network components are replicated and distributed over different locations to protect against DoS attacks. [20][p. 62]</p>	<p>Relevance score: +</p> <p>A distributed approach would probably serve IOT-A 's security interests since the large and expandable scale makes it unrealistic to have everything centralized (for memory, performance, etc.)</p>
Information model and distribution	<p>Common frameworks: The BRIDGE discovery service IS the common framework for managing information.</p> <p>Flexibility: Its flexibility compared to the vision of IOT-A however is more limited in that it handles information of known</p>	<p>Relevance score: +</p> <p>Relevant to WP4 for the ideas on</p>

	<p>formats belonging to known hardware (RFID tags).</p> <p>Information storage: Information is stored in a distributed fashion between nodes and the Discovery Service in BRIDGE is responsible for gathering this distributed information and sending it to the different nodes. The amount of information stored in the service was minimal. The Discovery Service records would include only pointers to sources of information, enabling whoever uses this service to discover the source, but not releasing information and leaving this decision to the companies which would keep control of the information</p> <p>Information Exchange in this system is handled by the processes described in the "Architecture Description" section.</p> <p>Quality of Information: the authors of BRIDGE make reference to the problem of "broken hyperlinks" in the "search engine of the Internet of Things" (the "Discovery Service" in the case of BRIDGE). To solve this, the Discovery Service was designed to avoid having the "URL" embedded in the records held by the Discovery Service. Instead, the records contain a pointer or immutable cross-reference ID to a "publisher profile record". This is illustrated in [18] [p. 24].</p>	<p>resolution, identification and security.</p>
<p>Horizontality</p>	<p>The infrastructure can be reused within different RFID applications since BRIDGE was designed to be used horizontally in the EPCglobal network for RFID. The messages and the data are built around EPCIS.</p> <p>The interface specifications are open to the public and thus allow other systems (outside of EPCglobal) to connect to BRIDGE as well, but additional work will be needed to make this transfer.</p> <p>Conceptually, the ideas developed for BRIDGE can also be abstracted to other projects (such as the topology of the Discovery Service architecture), but its direct implementation is not horizontal.</p>	<p>Relevance score: - The concept of a Discovery Service is general enough to be horizontal, but the specifics of the implementation in BRIDGE needs adaptive work before it can be used in IOT-A</p>
<p>Context awareness and semantic capabilities</p>	<p>BRIDGE is based on the EPCglobal network concept and thus follows the metadata capture / filtering / aggregation as specified in the corresponding EPCIS and other event standard. The event data allows for extensions with rich meta data.</p>	<p>Relevance score: + The project follows metadata capture.</p>
<p>Technological specificity and interoperability</p>	<p>The technology is bound to certain standards which is the EPCglobal network using EPCIS. BRIDGE is designed to work with just EPCglobal and that is the fullest scope of its interoperability.</p> <p>BRIDGE is not interoperable with other technologies since it deals specifically with RFID readers, tags and their applications using EPCGlobal. However, within EPCglobal BRIDGE enables interoperability between different RFID technologies and applications. Links to enterprise systems are often proprietary operations.</p> <p>Interfaces to other information systems however are clearly defined. The reader is encouraged to read about EPCGlobal in another chapter of the SoTA.</p> <p>The development of security features for BRIDGE was conducted with existing standards and open specifications, meaning that with modification some of the developed work might be reusable for other projects.</p>	<p>Relevance score: 0 BRIDGE is a specific solution to a problem within EPCGlobal and thus is not directly interoperable. Security however was developed with open and existing standards, which are - with work - transferrable.</p>
<p>Adaptation and self-*</p>	<p>Auto-Adapt - The system cannot auto-adapt to the changes in the environment.</p> <p>Self * - BRIDGE does not have "self*" properties other than discovering new objects by itself.</p>	<p>Relevance score: 0 The system does not address the evolution of underlying</p>

	systems.
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1.1.5 SmartProducts

SmartProducts develops the scientific and technological basis for building "smart products" with embedded "proactive knowledge. Proactive knowledge encompasses knowledge about the product itself (features, functions, dependencies, usage, etc.), its environment (physical context, other smart products) and its users (preferences, abilities, intentions, etc.).

Therefore, smart products "talk", "guide", and "assist" designers, workers and consumers dealing with them. Some proactive knowledge will be co-constructed with the product, while other parts are gathered during the product lifecycle using embedded sensing and communication capabilities. The outcome of SmartProducts will impact the manufacturing and consumer domain, primarily targeting consumer goods, automotive and aerospace industries, spanning both product innovation (for consumer goods and automotive) and process innovations (for automotive and aerospace).

1.1.5.1 Architecture relevance

It should be noted that a distinction could be made between the architecture of a single SmartProduct vs. the architecture that links the different SmartProducts together. For the purpose of this SOTA, the focus will be on the architecture that links the different SmartProducts together

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	The architecture linking different SmartProducts together is described by the authors as following a distributed channel-based publish/subscribe system . It is service orientated (ex. focused on communications) since SmartProducts must integrate information from heterogeneous sources to create a "smart" system. Within a SmartProduct, however, each Smart Product follows its own hard-coded architecture - there is no unifying principle. They follow "simple component based architecture" - each SmartProducts is set of OSGI bundles (a Java bundle technology), and the bundles can be described by text that says what classes they provide and what classes they need	Relevance score: + The communication methods of SmartProducts of subscribing to messages might be useful for IOT-A entities needing a simple communication method
Architecture style	The architecture style is described as a distributed channel-based publish/subscribe system for communication between nodes in the architecture. Information is stored in a "distributed" fashion [31][p.19] in that whenever a device cannot store all of the data it needs, it instead offloads it to nearby related SmartProducts devices and if this too is not possible, it offloads it to backend servers.	Relevance score: + The distributed style of communication between nodes in SmartProducts fits with the heterogeneity of IOT-A
Information model and distribution	How Information is Managed: the Information Management Framework Because SmartProducts deals with information exchange between heterogeneous products, the information structure is broken into several levels [27][p.12]. Information is accumulated and stored in different models maintained by the inter-SmartProducts architecture. The granularity of data is highly variable between the models, and some data are derived from other data sets. Higher level modules can be: Meta Model , used to represent information about other bits of proactive knowledge rather than about the entities of the environment; Time Model , using temporal information both as a part of knowledge about the world and as meta-level descriptions. Lower level modules can be: User Model , accumulating user-related information; Context Model , representing information about the state of the environment;	Relevance score: + The semantic models and approach however might be useful to IOT-A. The distributed storage and access concept is relevant to IOT-A's own set of design challenges of objects with low storage capabilities.

	<p>Domain model, which extends generic models with application-specific information relevant for the domains of cars, kitchen appliances, and aircraft manufacturing.</p>	
Horizontality	<p>The designers of the SmartProducts kept scalability in mind - meaning the same architecture applies to different sized computers (gumstix and computers) of different capabilities. For instance, this was done by</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decoupling of physical resources from logical entities: having all of the memory storage related to a SmartProducts to be done "off-board" or distributed between nearby SmartProducts [31][p. 19]; 2. Using a semantic language, independent of operating system or application [29] 	<p>Relevance score: + The SmartProduct techniques for horizontality - such as decoupling physical resources from logical entities - can also help solve certain IOT-A problems.</p>
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	<p>SmartProducts aims to empower objects with context awareness. There is a Context Model module [27][p. 19], described earlier, which provides environmental (location, time, etc.) and use context (plans, intentions, social context). However, the detailed mechanisms and how the SmartProducts context awareness works are not completely publically available.</p> <p>The two components in the SmartProducts architecture which address this are the "Proactive Knowledge Base" module and the latter is handled by the "Reasoner" module [29][p.9]. The reasoning capabilities use "Generic ontological reasoning based on OWL/RDFS semantics" (to characterize a state) and "Task-specific reasoning" to solve problems.</p>	<p>Relevance score: 0 While SmartProducts does factor in context awareness, the public resources available for such information are not complete.</p>
Technological specificity and interoperability	<p>SmartProducts uses the "MundoCore" platform [30] as a communication middleware between devices, which allows for interoperability between devices. This is implemented to be independent from platforms, components and programming languages by avoiding programming abstractions from object-orientated-programming. The serialized forms of requests, replies, and events are explicitly described along with the interfaces. Interoperability is established on the protocol level [30][p.6].</p>	<p>Relevance score: + The MundoCore platform seems to be general enough to allow interoperability between different entities in a SmartProducts network. On the other hand, some work is needed for MundoCore to be adapted or abstracted to an IOT-A usable form.</p>
Adaptation and self-*	<p>In its design, it was envisioned that every SmartProduct should be autonomous & provide functionality on its own, and every node should be able to interact with user, and actively initialize interaction.</p> <p>This is done by the Context Module [27][p. 19] and proactive data delivery [31][p. 36] (dispatching relevant data objects to devices according to specific information about the devices and their environment) - both of which get contextual based state information. The SmartProduct then adapts to the environment via rule-based problem solving</p>	<p>Relevance score: + Having segments of the architecture devoted to processing and forming contextual data would help enable self*- operations.</p>

1.1.6 CUBIQ

The Cross UBIquituous Platform (CUBIQ) [33] project aims to develop a common platform that facilitates the development of context-aware applications. The idea is to provide an integrated platform that offers unified data access, processing and service federation on top of existing, heterogeneous

ubiquitous services. The CUBIQ architecture [34] consists of three layers: (1) a data resource layer, (2) an intra-context processing layer and (3) an inter-context processing layer. The data resource layer provides transparent data access and handles mobility, migration, replication, concurrency, faults and persistency. The intra-context layer provides data processing services. The inter-context processing layer is responsible for service composition. The CUBIQ architecture provides interfaces for each layer.

Technically, CUBIQ uses PIAX [37], an open source agent platform for P2P structured overlay networks and a Universal Service Description Language (USDL) for describing services in CUBIQ [35]. Further CUBIQ provides solutions for real-time stream data processing and complex event processing.

1.1.6.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	The architecture is defined by a high-level vision figure. The actual architecture has been divided in three layers a (1) data resource layer, (2) an intra-context processing layer and (3) an inter-context processing layer. Each layer defines a set of functionalities. The inter-context processing layer and intra-context processing layer is further divided in two sub-layers with their respective functionalities [34].	Relevance score: 0 The architecture identifies useful functional blocks and requirements that are relevant for IoT-A but does not specifically address the requirements of the Internet of Things.
Architecture style	The prevalent architecture style of IoT is (Representational State Transfer) REST and Peer-to-Peer. REST is used in the bottom layer (data resource layer) and the Peer-to-Peer (P2P) agents are deployed at the data sources.	Relevance score: + REST can be considered as potential candidate as it provides a natural abstraction for entities of interest in IoT-A and it is finding increasing adoption. P2P may be relevant in certain parts of the reference architecture or its instances, but is less likely to be the dominant architectural style.
Information model and distribution	In CUBIQ the information model is tightly coupled with the service model used by the service description language USDL [35]. USDL uses an hierarchical object oriented data model in which types describe real-world entities including their properties and operations.	Relevance score: + The basic model is principle suitable for describing entities of interest.
Horizontality	Horizontalisation is achieved by the P2P platform PIAX [37] and unified data models as defined in USDL [35]. Further CUBIQ seeks to provide horizontality by hiding mobility and data replication.	Relevance score: 0 IoT-A should address at least the same level of horizontalisation, but may not fully rely on P2P mechanisms or be able to re-use he CUBIQ data models.
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	Enabling context-awareness is the main purpose of CUBIQ. Semantics is covered in the USDL descriptions, but we are not aware of the use of standard semantic reasoning techniques, e.g. based on OWL.	Relevance score: 0 Only little information about the technical details of the architecture was available at the time of the review.
Technological specificity and interoperability	From its conceptual design CUBIQ is independent of any sensing technologies, data models and service descriptions. However, it seems somewhat specific on the infrastructure part as it uses PIAX [37] as P2P technology.	Relevance score: 0 It is likely that IoT-A will apply similar mechanisms for abstracting from sensor, actuator devices, and networks. But more work needs to be done on network and service level.
Adaptation and self-*	Certain self-* properties are indirectly provided by the P2P infrastructure PIAX [37]. CUBIQ seeks to address mobility,	Relevance score: - No specific information available.

	<p>migration and replication, but at the time of review we had no detailed technical information on how this is achieved or contributes to self-* properties and adaptation.</p>	
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1.2 Commercial products

1.2.1 ZigBee

- Communication protocol up to application layer
- Relies on IEEE 802.15.4-2003 standard for PHY and MAC [40].
- Applications that require a low data rate, long battery life, and secure networking. Examples: wireless light switches with lamps, electrical meters with in-home-displays, etc.
- Alternative to Bluetooth (simpler, better scaling) and IEEE 802.11 (lower energy consumption).
- First specification ratified in 2004. Many updates and extensions since then [39].

1.2.1.1 Architecture integration aspects

Integration aspects	Description	Relevance & requirements
Programmability	APIs for applications (APSDE-SAPs) defined in standard. End-user specific applications enabled. Domain-specific set of stacks provided through profiles (e.g., Home Automation).	Relevance score: + Pro: definition of domain-specific application profiles Con: only accessible on application layer, no influence on communication (ZigBee internal)
Interfacing with the outside world	Products with various interfaces available ¹ .	Relevance score: 0 Interface possible but no mandatory non-ZigBee interfaces for certified ZigBee products
Architectural concepts	Stack architecture: PHY, MAC, Network, Application Support and Application Energy efficiency through sleeping modes. Application-device-type model: application device type – logical device type – 802.15.4 device type [40]. Centralised topology (routing, beacon-enabled TDMA).	Relevance score: - Pro: sleep modes Con: Silo solution (vertical integration from PHY up to application layer).
Adoption	Developed by ZigBee Alliance (consortium of vendors and OEMs) [38]. Various companies sell products. Mandatory certification for new products. Example: battery life of at least tow years for autarkic end devices.	Relevance score: - Silo solution (Intranet of Things) Exception ZigBee Smart Energy V2.0 (see Section 1.2.2 and [41])
Roadmap	Completion of profiles for building automation and retail approaching. Enhancement of Smart Energy (V1.x) under way. PHY/MAC-independent Smart Energy V2 under way (see Section 1.2.2 on ZigBee Smart Energy V2.0).	Relevance score: - Silo solution (Intranet of Things) Exception ZigBee Smart Energy V2.0 (see Section 1.2.2 and [41]).
Can the product interact with other items?	Communication through standardised application interfaces APSDE-SAP. Other products have to “speak” ZigBee. No communication with non-ZigBee entities on lower layers (WirelessHART, ...).	Relevance score: 0 Provides standard interfaces, but ZigBee stack not open (membership required).
Obvious integration aspects	Integration possible via so-called application endpoints (APSDE-SAP).	Relevance score: 0 Integration of ZigBee APSDE-SAP into IoT architecture or agreement with ZigBee alliance on standardised interface.

¹ see, e.g. <http://www.ZigBee4u.com/products/nzc-2400.html>

1.2.1.2 Hardware and software components & details

Component name	Description
ZigBee coordinator (ZC)	Most capable ZigBee device. Forms root of network tree and might bridge to other networks. One ZigBee coordinator in each network. Stores information about network, including acting as trust centre and repository for security keys.
ZigBee Router (ZR)	Runs application function(s). Can act as intermediate router, passing on data from other devices.
ZigBee End Device (ZED)	Contains just enough functionality for talking to parent node (either coordinator or router); it cannot relay data from other devices. This requires the node to be frequently asleep (→ energy conservation). A ZED offers the best performance in terms of energy savings, when compared to other ZigBee devices. Generally, it is less expensive to manufacture than a ZR or ZC.

1.2.2 ZigBee Smart Energy v2.0

- Similar application field as ZigBee Smart Energy V1.x.
- Internet readiness deemed crucial for Smart-Grid application area [45].
- Will meet NIST requirements for future-proof Smart-Grid devices[128].
- Differences to Smart Energy V1.x, or: what will be in it? [41].
- Not longer tied to IEEE 802.15.4 on PHY and MAC.
- If 15.4 is used: 2006 mandatory (with MAC security).[353]
- PLC another envisaged PHY (HomePlug).
- Adoption of ZigBee IP stack: 6lowPAN (IPv6) packet format and fragmentation.[80]
- Routing Protocol over Low power and lossy networks (RPL), being defined by IETF ROLL charter [79]
- Binary http.
- Application layer protocol is being discussed: among the other solutions, it is worth citing here IETF CoAP [81] and SOAP over UDP
- Embedded Service Location Protocol (IETF),
- MAC enhancements (TG IEEE 802.15.4e),
- Meter Access Side Communications standard (TG IEEE 802.15.4g),
- Applications defined in IEC 61968 CIM. Messages in XML.
- Aligning ZigBee certification process to NIST standards for Smart-Grid devices.

1.2.2.1 Architecture integration aspects

Integration aspects	Description	Relevance & requirements
Programmability	APIs for applications (APSDE-SAPs) defined in standard. End-user specific applications enabled. Domain-specific set of stacks provided through profiles (e.g., Home Automation). Standardised message syntax in XML [45].	Relevance score: + Pro: definition of domain-specific application profile Con: only for energy-related applications
Interfacing with the outside world	Interfaces both on the application layer as well toward link-layer and PHY (“PHY agnostic”).	Relevance score: + Standardised interfaces on application layer and below network layer. However: application interfaces geared toward energy-centred applications.
Architectural concepts	Stack architecture: Network, Application Support and Application PHY/MAC agnostic 6lowPAN including ROLL	Relevance score: - Silo solution (vertical integration from PHY up to application layer). +: sleep modes
Adoption	Developed by ZigBee Alliance (consortium of vendors and OEMs) [38]. Mandatory certification for new products. Example: battery life of at least two years for autarkic end devices.	Relevance score: + Many products are already developed using ZigBee profiles
Roadmap	Not available	Relevance score: 0

Can the product interact with other items?	Communication through standardised application interfaces APSDE-SAP. Other products have to “speak” ZigBee. No communication with non-ZigBee entities on lower layers (WirelessHART, ...).	Relevance score: 0 Provides standard interfaces, but ZigBee stack not open (membership required).
Obvious integration aspects	Integration possible via so-called application endpoints (APSDE-SAP).	Relevance score: - Only vertical solutions are envisaged.

1.2.2.2 Hardware and software components & details

Unknown but probably same as for ZigBee V1.x (see Section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

1.2.3 WirelessHART

Features:

- Communication with smart process field devices.
- Extension of popular wired HART communication technology to wireless applications.
- Standard published in 2007
- HART: Highway Addressable Remote Transducer.
- Builds on IEEE 802.15.4-2006 PHY and selected aspects of the MAC (different approach to channel hopping; channel blacklisting).
- Robust real-time communication through central management of TDM slots and routing as well as mesh networking.
- Secure communication through several security mechanisms.
- Due to single-purpose philosophy no interoperability with other communication technologies.

1.2.3.1 Architecture integration aspects

Integration aspects	Description	Relevance & requirements
Programmability	APIs between the OSI layers described in standard (although maybe insufficiently ([50], p. 179).	Relevance score: 0 Only scarce information available.
Interfacing with the outside world	Interfacing via plant-automation network. In other words: currently no planned gateway/interface to other networks.	Relevance score: - No interfacing roadmap.
Architectural concepts	Centralised wireless network. Hierarchical structure (central network manager). Relies on prior network planning. Dedicated sensors and actuators. Builds on OSI layer model. Describes layer 1-4 and 7 (layers 5 and 6 empty). Access to wired networks via dedicated gateway (central) or adapter (field); network managers sets routes and communication schedules. Deterministic communication: Time synchronisation via time slots (super frames); TDMA. Star, cluster and mesh topology (self-organisation and self-healing). Every wireless device is a router.	Relevance score: - Integrated architecture up to the application layer (silo). No device-based interfaces to other communication networks (only via gateways).
Adoption	Standardised by HART Communication Foundation. Units adhering to the WirelessHART standard produced by various companies (ABB, Emerson, ...). Technology is mostly used as a wireless extension of popular HART networks (process automation).	Relevance score: 0 Builds on IEEE 802.15.4-2006 platform Open standard World-wide deployment but: central management might jeopardise scalability
Roadmap	First release in September 2007. Ongoing MAC extension of IEEE 802.15.4 in order to support WirelessHART (harmonisation) → TG IEEE 802.15.4e	Relevance score: - Roadmap embraces continued intranet philosophy.
Can the product interact with other	All WirelessHART products can communicate and cooperate with each other (sameness of OSI 1-7).	Relevance score: - Silo solution. Interfacing

items?	Compulsory compliance tests. Interfaces to networks operating on Fieldbus Foundation (FF) or PROFIBUS Nutzerorganisation (PNO) standards under way [51], [52].	below application has to be achieved via standardisation.
Obvious integration aspects	Difficult due to need of network manager and network usage plan.	Relevance score: - Integration might be elusive. Co-operation with WirelessHART “islands”?

1.2.3.2 Hardware and software components & details

Component name	Description
WirelessHART Field Device (WFD)	Devices that are connected to process or to plant equipment. Routers belong to WFDs but do not interfere with plant processes.
WirelessHART Gateway	Enables communication between host applications and WFDs. Functionally divided into virtual gateway and one-to-many access points. Each access point has unique ID. One gateway per network.
WirelessHART Network Manager	Management, scheduling, and optimisation of WirelessHART network. Provides mechanisms for devices joining and leaving the network. Responsible for managing dedicated and shared resources. Responsible for collecting and maintaining diagnostics and health of network. Reports diagnostics to host application.
WirelessHART Adapter	Integrates HART Field devices into WirelessHART network.
WirelessHART Handheld	Supports direct access to WirelessHART field devices.

1.2.4 Sensinode

Sensinode provides embedded networking software and hardware products based on IP-based 6LoWPAN technology for demanding enterprise applications. NanoStack™ 2.0 is an advanced 6LoWPAN protocol stack software product for 2.4 GHz and Sub-GHz radios. The NanoRouter™ 2.0 platform includes software and hardware solutions for 6LoWPAN-Internet routing infrastructure.

1.2.4.1 Architecture integration aspects

Integration aspects	Description	Relevance & requirements
Programmability	NanoStack™ is a source-code C-based 6LoWPAN protocol stack with development support under Linux and Windows. Socket API, allows the development of 6LoWPAN applications. Reprogrammable using dedicated development board. A Contiki port is available.	Relevance score = + Sensinode hardware and software are easily programmable using internet-like functions (sockets).
Interfacing with the outside world	Sensinode developed a proprietary NanoStack™ which is 6LoWPAN based and offer high compatibility with internet protocols, such as UDP.	Relevance score = + The support for 6LoWPAN and UDP makes them easily interoperable with internet.
Architectural concepts	Sensinode devices are intended for WSN islands and boundary entities (gateways and routers)	Relevance = + Usable for islands of the IoT world
Adoption	Texas Instruments, Radiocrafts, University of Oulu, IPSO	Relevance = 0 Maybe not a major player, but easy to integrate
Roadmap	not available to public. Actually working with TI MSP430, CC2430, CC2431, CC2531	Relevance score = 0
Can the product interact with other items?	Sensinode products should interact with internet items, but the interoperability with other 6LoWPAN network devices has to be tested	Relevance score = 0 Not enough information
Obvious integration aspects	Building sensor island for metering, monitoring and distributed control systems	Relevance = + Adoption of 6LoWPAN

	Building on top of NanoStack
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1.2.4.2 Hardware and software components & details

Component name	Description
NanoSensor	The NanoSensor is a user-programmable sensor node, based on the Sensinode NanoStack TM 2.0 protocol stack. The node provides an easy way to build and test 6LoWPAN networks together with NanoRouterTM 2.0 Products and NodeViewTM 2.0.
NanoRouter	The NanoRouter™ Ethernet 2.0 is a reference access point platform enabling seamless connectivity between 6LoWPAN based enterprise sensor networks and IPv4/IPv6 Ethernet networks. NanoRouter™ 2.0 Ethernet is taking the advance of proven and robust embedded Linux core.
NanoStack 2.0	NanoStack™ 2.0 is the next generation release of Sensinode's field-proven communication stack for IP-based wireless sensor networks. NanoStack™ 2.0 is platform and radio independent. Key features include the industry's best code footprint, as little as 32 k of flash, support for 2.4 GHz (CC2430) and 868/915 MHz (CC1110) Texas Instruments chips.
NodeView	NodeView™ 2.0 is a network analyzer and site survey tool for 6LoWPAN network researchers, designers and integrators. This easy-to-use tool gives a comprehensive graphical analysis of 6LoWPAN networks, including full node statistics, network topologies, routing information and map support. NodeView is compatible with all Sensinode NanoStack, NanoRouter and NanoSensor products.

1.2.5 SunSPOT

Sun SPOTs are a platform from Sun Microsystems for the development of sensor networks and embedded systems. Sun SPOT is an acronym that stands for Sun Small Programmable Object Technology. Unlike other embedded systems the software development is not in C/C++ or specially modified C-variants, but in Java. For this, Sun has developed its own Java Virtual Machine, the Squawk-VM. The use of Squawk-VM abstracts hardware details like access to the wireless communication module and the different sensors; therefore it is quite easy to develop applications for the Sun SPOT in Java. The sensor nodes are able to use multithreading and multiprocessing. The communication model of the Sun SPOTs is based on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard. The IEEE specification describes the structure of MAC and physical layer for low-rate wireless personal area networks (WPANs). The communication model of the Sun SPOTs allows a data transmission up to 250 Kbps.

1.2.5.1 Architecture integration aspects

The Sun SPOTs offer different protocols for wireless communication: the radiostream protocol for stream based communication and the radiogram protocol for datagram-based communication. Based on these protocols different implementations are possible, like webservice interfaces through a modified DPWS-stack [3].

Integration aspects	Description	Relevance & requirements
Programmability	SunSPOT Software Development Kit (Red SDK) based on Java SDK.	Relevance score: 0 Very easy to program because of full java compatibility
Interfacing with the outside world	Wireless interface based on IEEE 802.15.4 standard	Relevance score: + Interesting for testing purpose
Architectural concepts	No specific architecture defined.	N/A
Adoption	Mainly used for education and research projects	Relevance score: -- No market relevance
Roadmap	Detailed roadmap is available under [4]	Relevance score: 0
Can the product interact with other items?	Through standardized interface the connection to nearly any networked object is possible	Relevance score: + Interesting for testing purpose
Obvious integration aspects	Connection is possible through wireless interface (for example through webservice implementation)	none

1.2.5.2 Hardware and software components & details

Component name	Description
Processor board	The processor board consists of a CPU, network interfaces, including antenna, a USB interface and the memory. CPU: 180 Mhz 32-bit ARM920T with 512KB RAM and 4MB flash memory. Network interface: Chipcon CC2420-based wireless platform that meets the 802.15.4 standard.
Sensor board	The sensor board carries an accelerometer, a light and a temperature sensor. In addition, the board has eight LEDs, two buttons, as well as six analog and five digital inputs/outputs. A total of four power outputs and an A/D converter are available. Other components can be connected to the Sun SPOTs via the analog and digital outputs.

1.2.6 QR Code

The Quick Response (QR) code is a 2 Dimension bar code created by Denso-Wave in 1994 and was at first mostly popular in Japan. QR codes were first used by Toyota to track part of vehicles they have become very successful in automatic processing thanks to the possibility they provide to transmit a message that can be recognized by camera equipped devices like smart phone. Since the content of a QR code can be any kind of string, they are commonly used to transmit a URL to a device. Therefore, a Smartphone user can visit the webpage encoded by the QR code instead of typing the URL in its browser. Smartphone applications can directly interprets the content of a QR code and render it over the picture captured by the camera. QR code error correction rate ranges from 7% to 30% depending on the chosen encoding level.

QR code composition: A QR code is composed of three position detection patterns that are placed at corners and used to determine the QR-code position. A timing pattern links the three detection patterns and is used to determine the coordinates inside the code. Format information is placed around the upper-left corner pattern.

QR code main features:

- Large capacity (7,089 numeric characters or 4,296 alphanumeric),
- Small printout size,
- High speed scan.

1.2.6.1 Architecture integration aspects

Integration aspects	Description	Relevance & requirements
Programmability	QR codes are simple to deploy and recognized by many smartphones	Relevance score: 0 QR codes are completely opaque.
Interfacing with the outside world	QR code is an interface	Relevance score: 0
Adoption	Technology is developed by Denso Wave and is used in many Web applications targeting smartphones. This technology is also widely used by URL shortener services	Relevance score: 0
Can the product interact with other items?	QR codes are a communication interface that is already widely used	Relevance score: 0 While popular this interface is non-intuitive as it captures data through a camera.

1.2.6.2 Hardware and software components & details

Component name	Description
Camera	To capture the QR code, user must use a camera and a QR code recognizing software.

1.3 Standardization activities

1.3.1 ETSI TC M2M

The European Telecommunications Standard Institute [60] created in January 2009 a new Technical Committee (TC) focussed on Machine-to-Machine communications. The main responsibilities of the group [60] can be summarized in the following:

- to collect and specify M2M requirements from relevant stakeholders;
- to develop and maintain an end-to-end overall high level architecture for M2M;
- to identify gaps where existing standards do not fulfil the requirements and provide specifications and standards to fill these gaps, where existing standards bodies or groups are unable to do so;
- to provide the ETSI main centre of expertise in the area of M2M;
- to co-ordinate ETSI's M2M activity with that of other standardization groups and fora

1.3.1.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	ETSI generates Technical Reports and Technical Specifications (TS). The Technical Specifications are the real standards. In the group three TS are generated: Service Requirements (Stage 1): Requirements that must be supported by the solution. Functional Architecture (Stage 2): High-level view of the architecture. Protocol definition (Stage 3): Detailed protocol specification.	Relevance score: ++ It is quite common to use the three levels to describe architectures.
Architecture style	It is defined following a centralized RESTful approach, where applications can define resources (memory blocks that are located in the platform components deployed in the devices, gateways or central infrastructures), which can be used to exchange information between applications.	Relevance score: 0 The scope of the M2M is shorter than the scope of IOT-A, since it just provides facilities to exchange information.
Information model and distribution	The M2M architecture is based on the use of resources to exchange information. The structure of the resources is standardized but not the content of the information that is included in the resource. The resources can be located in the central platform, the gateway or the devices and are defined (and accessible) using URLs.	Relevance score: 0 It follows a centralized approach with the use of URLs, which is not really applicable.
Horizontality	The platform is intended to be horizontal to help the development of vertical applications. It provides horizontal facilities that allow the exchange of information between applications (in the server and device side), but the content of the information is not uniform.	Relevance score: + The use of standardized structures without standardizing the content could be interesting for the modelling point of view.
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	None	Relevance score: --
Technological specificity and interoperability	The communication between the network applications and the central server is going to be provided using HTTP REST. The communication between the devices and the central platform mainly using HTTP REST, but not only. The devices are intended to implement the interfaces defined by the ETSI or communicated through interworking Gateways.	Relevance score: - Just the devices that support the interface provided by the ETSI TC M2M are directly supported.
Adaptation and self-*	Nothing currently defined	Relevance score: --

1.3.2 ITU-T USN (Ubiquitous Sensor Networks)

Within ITU-T, USN standardization is being carried out under the auspices of the Next-Generation Network Global Standards Initiative (NGN-GSI).

According to ITU-T, USN is “a conceptual network built over existing physical networks which make use of sensed data and provide knowledge services”. So its main components are the following ones:

- USN Applications and Services platform: technology platform to enable the effective use of a USN in a given application or service.
- USN Middleware: including functionalities for sensor network management and connectivity, event processing, sensor data mining, etc.
- Network infrastructure: mainly based on Next-Generation-Networks (NGNs), USN is not a physical network it is a conceptual network making use of existing networks.
- USN Gateway: A node which interconnects sensor networks with other networks.
- Sensor network: Network of inter-connected sensor nodes ... (IP based nodes possibility of direct connection to NGN; non IP based nodes, often managed via gateway).

ITU-T work has been focused mainly on general functional models and requirements to support of USN application and services in NGN environments. A reference model of USN over NGN has been proposed based on both USN service requirements, and requirements of NGN (enhanced or additional) necessary to support USN applications and services. ITU-T recommendations also include a general functional model and requirements for USN middleware, as well as management and security issues.

1.3.2.1 Architecture relevance

ITU-T USN considers “transport stratum” and “service stratum”. At “transport stratum” various alternatives for networking, middleware and application (IP, non-IP, ZigBee, TinyOS, IETD 6LoWPAN,...) are considered. Focus for middleware and application functions will make “service stratum” issues.

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	USN is based on the architectural style of ITU-T Next-Generation Network (NGN). So they are documented as architectural requirements for USN which are identified based on two main issues (ITU-T Y.2221; Y.USN-reqts, SG13 [66]): Service requirements of USN applications and services, which impact the NGN capabilities. These requirements are used to fetch the required extensions to the set of NGN capabilities. Based on 1) to address NGN capability requirements (extended and/or new capabilities) for support of USN applications and services (from a high level perspective).	Relevance score = - The documentation just refers to requirements.
Architecture style	In the USN service environment where USN middleware works, there are three main elements: USN applications, USN middleware and Sensor Networks. The approach seems to provide a central/model probably with distributed capabilities.	Relevance score = 0 USN architecture style could be relevant if considering possible impact of IoT-A on NGN.
Information model and distribution	Currently ITU-T USN does not have clearly identified information models and specific strategies for the management of information. Information models will probably be based on other SDO initiatives (mainly ISO).	Relevance score = N/A
Horizontality	As USN is based on ITU-T NGN principles, it is based on the decoupling of services (“service stratum”) and transport (“transport stratum”) (see Figure before), which allows them to be offered separately and to evolve independently.	Relevance score = 0 Again the use of horizontal principles of NGN could be relevant if considering possible impact of IoT-A on NGN.
Context awareness and	USN middleware can provide information processing functions such as query processing,	Relevance score = -- These descriptions of USN

semantic capabilities	context-aware processing, event processing, sensor network monitoring and so on.	middleware are too general and still to be developed to have a relevant impact on IoT-A.
Technological specificity and interoperability	At “transport stratum” of ITU-T USN various alternatives for networking, middleware and application (IP, non-IP, ZigBee, TinyOS, IETD 6LoWPAN,...) are considered.	Relevance score = 0 The integration of different networking technologies could be relevant if considering possible impact of IoT-A on NGN.
Adaptation and self-*	No adaptation and self-* procedures have been specifically addressed in ITU-T USN.	Relevance score = N/A

1.3.3 ISO/IEC JTC1 WG7 (Working Group on Sensor Networks)

ISO is the International Organization for Standardization, current JTC (Joint Technical Committee) 1/WG (Work Group) 7 has been preceded by JTC 1 SGSN SC6, the ISO/IEC Study Group on Sensor Networks SGSN that was established in 2007.

A result of JTC 1 SGSN activities was the ISO/IEC 29182 Reference architecture for sensor networks application and services: “This work area can give them an overall architecture consisting of system and network configurations, data processing functionalities, and interface relationships due to heterogeneous application components”. The ISO/IEC 29182 Reference architecture was transferred to JTC 1 WG7 (established in October 2009).

Main Terms of Reference or study items defined under JTC 1 WG7 are: 1) generic solutions for sensor networks, 2) application oriented sensor networks 3) to foster communication and sharing of information between groups.

The recent creation of ISO/IEC JTC1 WG7 (Working Group on Sensor Networks) makes its activities still preliminary and very general. However it is expected a rapid growth both in future activities and relevance in the IoT standardization field in liaison with other important SDOs (as ITU-T USN).

1.3.3.1 Architecture relevance

Most of the objectives of this standardization group can be shared with the objectives of IOT-A: sensor nodes communicating different means (wireless or wired) through different networks (Internet, NGN, ...) to applications that might be located in different parts of the world. From an architecture point of view, this work will be extremely relevant, however the activities just started and we need to monitor their work.

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	The architecture is defined through a set of documents containing: ISO/IEC 29182 Part 1 – General overview and requirements ISO/IEC 29182 Part 2 – Vocabulary/Terminology ISO/IEC 29182 Part 3 – Reference architecture views ISO/IEC 29182 Part 4 – Entity models ISO/IEC 29182 Part 5 – Interface definitions ISO/IEC 29182 Part 6 – Application Profiles ISO/IEC 29182 Part 7 – Interoperability guidelines	Relevance score = ++ As its description is an on-going activity ISO/IEC architecture can provide relevant to insights to IoT-A
Architecture style	ISO/IEC 29182 will identify and define the functional blocks. Right now no more information is provided.	Relevance score = ++ Architecture view of is being defined. Still too early to be taken it into account (but future interest to IoT-A)
Information model and distribution	The architecture design considers Collaborative information processing: so sensor nodes may collaborate to solve complex sensing problems, such as measurement, detection, classification, and tracking in physical world. The data from a sensor may have to be pre-processed and refined at the sensor node or at another sensor node. Depending on applications, intermediary data, such as features or estimated	Relevance score = + The way Collaborative information processing will be defined in ISO/IEC can be a relevant issue to IoT-A

	parameters, may need to be extracted from raw sensor data during the pre-processing. The results from this pre-processing may be shared among the sensor nodes in the sensor network.	
Horizontality	In the horizontal point of view, JTC 1/WG 7 will undertake standardization activities for generic solutions for overall sensor networks applications such as terminology and reference architectures in order to improve the interoperability.	Relevance score = + To follow how ISO/IEC will address horizontality issues for a variety of applications and technologies will be relevant to IoT-A
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	It is envisioned that it will cover both aspects but right now it is unknown.	Relevance score = 0 These basic principles are still to be developed but can have a relevant impact on IoT-A.
Technological specificity and interoperability	ISO/IEC will address how different technologies and the emerging sensor network can connect with existing infrastructures such as database, repository, and other systems through IT backbone and Internet; thus become part of systems of systems (SoS) that provides benefits to home and business.	Relevance score = + This work on progress on the integration of different networking technologies can be relevant to IoT-A
Adaptation and self-*	No adaptation and self-* procedures have been specifically addressed.	Relevance score = N/A

1.3.4 OGC® SWE (Sensor Web Enablement)

Open Geospatial Consortium, OGC®, overall activity is the so-called Geospatial Web: “to publish, discover and use geodata as well as geoprocessing services in an interoperable way”

OGC® Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) mission is the development of standards allowing the integration of sensors and sensor networks into the Geospatial Web (i.e. it is a specialized subtype called the “Sensor Web”).

SWE standardization activity is being pursued through the establishment of several encodings for describing sensors and sensor observations, and through several standard interface definitions for web services.

Main functionalities in OGC® SWE are:

- Quickly discover sensors and sensor data (secure or public) that can meet different needs based on location, observables, quality, ability to task, etc.
- Description of sensors and measurements in a standard machine understandable encoding enabling assessment and processing without a-priori knowledge.
- Readily to access sensor parameter in a common manner, and in a highly configurable way.
- Access to measurement data (real-time data as well as time series) based on standardized data format.
- Tasking of sensors to acquire observations of interest.
- Alerting mechanisms based on sensor measurements and certain alert criteria: subscribe to and receive alerts when a sensor measures a particular phenomenon.

Within the last years, the SWE architecture has been advanced to a solid and mature state. Now, most of the SWE standards have been adopted as official OGC® standards and several practical applications relying on the SWE standards have been built.

1.3.4.1 Architecture relevance

SWE architecture represents a relevant and coherent infrastructure to integrate heterogeneous sensors in a platform independent and uniform way. SWE follows a top down view on sensor networks independent of a particular implementation or hardware platform.

From an application perspective, a set of basic SWE services encapsulates sensor network infrastructures hiding the underlying layers with the network communication details, and heterogeneous sensor hardware and lower-level protocols. At the same time, SWE infrastructure allows sensor network providers to easily share their sensor resources.

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	SWE architecture is described through a set of services, interfaces and data models used to define these services.	Relevance score = ++ SWE represents one of the most evolved Sensor Web

	Standards are made publicly available for: Information models both for describing sensors (SensorML) and sensor data (Observations & Measurements). Web Service interfaces: Sensor Observation Service (SOS), the Sensor Alert Service (SAS), the Sensor Planning Service (SPS) and the Web Notification Service (WNS)	architecture, so it should represent a relevant reference to IoT-A.
Architecture style	SWE is a Net-Centric, SOA-based Architecture. Its distributed style allows independent development of services but at the same time enabling on-the-fly connectivity between resources. SWE can be viewed as a meta-platform that integrates arbitrary sensors and sensor networks; each maintained and operated by individual institutions.	Relevance score = ++ SWE architecture style, based on interoperability at the service layer over the network layer, is applicable to IoT-A.
Information model and distribution	Information can either be stored on the sensor or on the system for later access or directly sent to aggregation systems.	Relevance score = + Moderate relevance for IoT-A sensor data services.
Horizontality	SWE service components provide common services for accessing/tasking sensor resources and accessing the resulting observations and data products. These services present a normalized representation of collected data from sensors, sometimes unprocessed or only minimal processed, sometimes fully processed and ready for analysis and exploitation.	Relevance score = ++ Homogeneous representation of resources in SWE can be relevant to horizontalization and interoperability principles in IoT-A architecture.
	SWE service components expose a standard set of capabilities and a normalized, well-known means for describing the data and representing it for access and sharing across networks.	Relevance score = ++ SWE common services description principles can be useful to seamless integration between IoT services based on dynamic application and service requests in IoT-A.
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	As key to interoperability SWE relies on links to online dictionaries and ontologies for semantics, but these external relation to context entities are not defined by the SWE. Furthermore, the W3C is working on developing ontologies which can be used to annotate the OGC standards.	Relevance score = + Extensions over the use of simple semantic links to ontologies in SWE can be relevant to IoT-A.
Technological specificity and interoperability	SWE is sensor system agnostic. Virtually any sensor, sensor network or processing system can be supported.	Relevance score = + IoT-A will support for heterogeneous sensors and processing elements.
Adaptation and self-*	Although no self-* procedures are defined, SWE allows the integration of individual sensors as much as the integration of complete sensor systems without the need of fundamental changes to the legacy systems. Implement services and processing where it makes sense (e.g. near sensors, closer to user, or in-between). Scalable from single, simple sensor to large sensor collections. SWE traceability includes both observation lineage and quality of measurement support	Relevance score = + Integration, interoperability and scalability of IoT-A could consider SWE solutions for flexible integration of resource, services and scalability

1.3.5 IETF (constrained devices)

The Internet Engineering Task Force, IETF [74], is an international community of network designer, operators, vendors, and researchers concerned with the evolution of the Internet architecture and the

smooth operation of the Internet. For efficient organization, the technical work of IETF is divided into various working groups, which are organized into several research areas such as routing, transport, or security. The mailing list represents one of the most important tools for managing work and the IETF meets three times a year.

The IETF working groups are grouped into areas, and managed by Area Directors (ADs), members of the Internet Engineering Steering Group (IESG). The Internet Architecture Board (IAB), that providing architectural oversight, and IESG are chartered by the Internet Society (ISOC) for these purposes. The mission of the IETF [75] is to make the Internet work better by producing high quality, relevant technical documents that influence the way people design, use, and manage the Internet. In order to realize its mission, IETF follows these basic principles:

- Open process
- Technical competence
- Volunteer Core
- Rough consensus and running code
- Drafts ownership

The basic definition of the IETF standards process is defined in to RFC2026 [76].

1.3.5.1 Architecture relevance

In the following table, the most IoT-A relevant WGs are analyzed. In particular, we addressed 6LoWPAN, ROLL and CoRE charters.

Field	Description	Relevance to IoT-A reference architecture
Architecture description	The architecture of IETF Working Groups is described through a set of RFCs and by several DRAFT which defines how to achieve goals set. Although in the charters analyzed in this section there is no proper architecture definition, some information are available in [86],[87],[88] and [89]: in these documents there are specification of the requirements of the different application scenarios for ROLL; however they are valid for many application for constrained devices.	Relevance score: + The environment analysis performed in the ROLL charter is readily usable in IoT-A for defining requirements.
Architecture style	CORE uses a RESTful architecture, based on the idea that application state and function can be abstracted into addressable resources. ROLL proposes a centralized routing structure, that can dynamically create new central node in order to support multiple routing rules and adaptability.	Relevance score: ++ The RESTful approach looks one of the most promising for implementing Internet procedure on constrained devices.
Information model and distribution	RPL protocol proposes the role of one or more sink nodes that manage and store the information (Centralized model). 6LoWPAN define an adaptation layer for give support of IPv6 packet and mechanisms for header compression required to make IPv6 practical on IEEE 802.15.4 network. CoAP is designed for resource-oriented applications intended to run on constrained IP networks.	Relevance score: 0
Horizontality	RPL is focused on routing issues for Low power and Lossy Networks (LLN), in particular for a subset of application: home and building automation [88], urban WSNs [86] and industry [87]. CoAP is developed to run in special environments that have narrow constraint like energy power, packet loss, limited hardware capability and so on. CoAP must consider the possibility of automatic application to exploit the data from one or several heterogeneous networks.	Relevance score: ++ 6LoWPAN, RPL and CoAP seem the most popular solution for bringing IP networking in constrained environment.

Context awareness and semantic capabilities	Although not directly addressed in none of the considered charters, CoAP allows for an easy design of RESTful semantic applications.	Relevance score: 0 N/A
Technological specificity and interoperability	<p>ROLL Working Group is focused on routing issues for Low power and Lossy networks (LLNs) are made up of many embedded devices with limited power, memory, and processing resources. It focuses only on IPv6 routing architectural framework for different application scenarios and it will take into consideration various aspects including high reliability in the presence of time varying loss characteristics and connectivity while permitting low-power operation with very modest memory and CPU pressure in networks potentially comprising a very large number (several thousands) of nodes.</p> <p>6LoWPAN manage IPv6 packet over IEEE 802.15.4 based networks.</p> <p>CoAP is designed for lossy environments. Moreover, UDP, does not provide any congestion control mechanism.</p>	Relevance score: + The proposed protocols are fitting to many constrained environments, such as IEEE 802.15.4 wireless networks, Power Line Communication and, possibly NFC.
Adaptation and self-*	<p>The routing protocol RPL is able to auto-adapt on changes of the topology through the exchange of special packages (self-managing and self-healing) and it is able to auto-repair if there is a broken link or a shutdown of a node.</p> <p>CoAP allows to transfer compress XML packets, used to describe nodes functionalities, to access information provider and to trigger actuators. Hence, it is a good starting for developing adaptable and composable services.</p>	Relevance score: ++ Given the interest shown by many system integrators and the ZigBee alliance itself, IETF solutions seem a must have for IoT-A.

1.3.6 EPCglobal Network Architecture

In recent years, the Electronic Product Code (EPC) — a worldwide, unambiguous code for the designation of physical goods — has become the subject of enormous interest, not only in research but also in several industries and society in general. The rapid and escalating diffusion of the EPC was particularly driven by the Auto-ID Center, a project to develop RFID standards founded in 1999 at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) with cooperation from numerous industrial sponsors. The Auto-ID Center created the EPC to ensure RFID interoperability in supply-chain-wide applications. An important feature is its capability to serve as a metascheme that integrates with existing numbering schemes, such as the serialized Global Trade Item Number (GTIN) standard used in retail. However, the Center's long-term objective wasn't only standardizing numbering formats but also developing an entire family of open standards, including air interface protocols, software interfaces, and directory services, to bridge the gap between the physical and virtual worlds. In October 2003, the Auto-ID Center was transformed into an international research network known as Auto-ID Labs, which concentrates on technology as well as application-oriented research, and EPCglobal, a nonprofit organization responsible for commercializing, standardizing, and managing EPC standards.

1.3.6.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	<p>The EPC network consists of various elements including EPC tags, readers and a middleware layer that abstracts from EPC reader hardware and manages realtime read events and information. Furthermore, it provides alerts, and manages the basic read information for communication with other information systems.</p> <p>The EPCIS standard enables users to capture, secure and access EPC-related data via a uniform interface. The link between an object's</p>	Relevance score: + It describes a particular architecture regarding RFID scanning process and should be considered as it is a proved concept in the standardisation area.

	EPC number and information that is distributed across the network is established by two additional services, the object name service (ONS) and the EPC discovery service.	
Architecture style	In particular the EPCIS, as a component of the EPCglobal network, has a distributed structure and it is owned and operated by different companies with different business models to be able to read and write data from and to the EPCIS in a standardized method. However, it exists also a REST approach where a new API is designed based on REST fulfilling requirements and complementary to the WS-* interface [98].	Relevance score: + The distributed architecture style is also applicable for IoT-A concerns and makes sense in order to support reliability and scalability
Information model and distribution	Based on XML the Physical Markup Language (PML) is used for data exchange to store PML data on PML servers. This language serves for describing physical objects and to support interoperability where one computer system or organization makes its data readable for another computer system or organization and allow storage of any related information about an item.	Relevance score: 0 A data/information exchange is needed for IoT-A in order to tag certain objects but there exist other approaches which might be more useful
Horizontality	Primarily the following components of the EPCglobal network could be useful for IoT-A : Object Naming Service (ONS) By use of an ID (e.g. EPC code) the ONS returns a network location defining where information about a specific object rests. EPC Discovery Service The Discovery Service acts as a registry for the EPC information system. It collects object-related data and provides access to information of a specific item whenever a trading partner in the supply chain needs track-and-trace information.	Relevance score: + IoT-A must be able to identify the location of Entities of Interest and to provide information about them if needed
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	Above all the prior objective of the EPCglobal network is to identify objects. Therefore only an ID is needed whereas afterwards with the support of databases the ID can be combined to further data to get more information from e.g. a supply chain process.	Relevance score: - The current version of the EPC network does not support any context awareness and semantic capabilities
Technological specificity and interoperability	EPCglobal's objective is to provide a framework especially for RFID concerns. However, the EPCglobal architecture network provides many components which could be useful for other Wireless Sensor Network technologies as well.	Relevance score: 0 Even though EPCglobal is focused on RFID technology and interoperability it could also be interesting for other Wireless Sensor Network technologies
Adaptation and self-*	Adaptation and self-* properties are not directly incorporated but supported i.e. self-replenishment in retail.	Relevance score: -

1.3.7 REST Architecture

REST is a coordinated set of architectural constraints that attempts to minimize latency and network communication, while at the same time maximizing the independence and scalability of component implementations. This is achieved by placing constraints on connector semantics, where other styles have focused on component semantics. REST enables the caching and reuse of interactions, dynamic substitutability of components, and processing of actions by intermediaries, in order to meet the needs of an Internet-scale distributed hypermedia system.

REST elaborates only those portions of the architecture that are considered essential for Internet-scale distributed hypermedia interaction. Areas for improvement of the Web architecture can be seen

where existing protocols fail to express all of the potential semantics for component interaction, and where the details of syntax can be replaced with more efficient forms without changing the architecture capabilities. Likewise, proposed extensions can be compared to REST to see if they fit within the architecture; if not, it is usually more efficient to redirect that functionality to a system running in parallel with a more applicable architectural style.

1.3.7.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	The architecture is described with different models and is designed to be really simple and scalable (see the principle in annex). The REST architecture style is derived from the following base style: replicated repository, cache, client-server, layered system, stateless, virtual machine, code on demand, and uniform interface.	Relevance score: + The architecture is simple and scalable and achieved to federate many different concepts.
Architecture style	The Architecture style is REST (Representational State Transfer)	Relevance score: + REST can be used to 'virtualise' object on the Web (see Web Of Things).
Information model and distribution	In REST, the information is mainly stored in the server. The client should not keep any information other than the one it is currently consuming. One exception is the cookie which stores information on the client side but do not respect REST architecture model.	Relevance score: 0 REST information model may not be suited for IoT-A; information is centralized in servers, end terminal just access it.
Horizontality	The simple semantic of REST and its wide adoption helped it to provide services that have been reused in other domain like SmartPhone Application. Because REST is simple to access and platform providing APIs have been built on top of it.	Relevance score: ++ Many platforms/service (e.g: Facebook, Google) have been designed using the RESTfull architecture style. RESTfull can architecture often exposes WEB APIs that can be used by other services/applications.
Context awareness and semantic capabilities	REST do not provide context awareness. REST basic semantic capabilities are limited with only 4 actions that can be used (GET, PUT, POST, DELETE). In order to provide advanced semantic features, the web uses the Resource Description Framework. Since REST is stateless, there is no context awareness.	Relevance score: + Currently the architecture does not propose semantic based functionalities but the "Semantic Web" will extend the architecture to provide such support.
Technological specificity and interoperability	Interoperability with different technologies is managed through the TCP/IP protocol stack that is widely adopted and can be deployed on top of most technologies.	Relevance score: 0 The interoperability with lower layers is not managed by the architecture itself but mostly by the adopted support (TCP/IP).
Adaptation and self-*	The closest principle to self-* is anarchic scalability that allow the system to be working even when part of the architecture is down. Servers are independent and should be able to work properly even if some of them are disfunctioning. Adaptation is supported through the 'Independent Deployment' principle that states that architectural elements need to be designed with the expectation that later architectural features will be added	Relevance score: + Anarchic scalability and independent deployment are relevant principles but may not fulfil all the IoT-A requirements. Especially, there is no self-healing capability.

1.3.8 Web Service Architecture

The WSA provides a conceptual model and a context for understanding Web services and the relationships between the components of this model. The architecture does not attempt to specify how Web services are implemented, and imposes no restriction on how Web services might be combined. The WSA describes both the minimal characteristics that are common to all Web services, and a number of characteristics that are needed by many, but not all, Web services. The Web services architecture is interoperability architecture: it identifies those global elements of the global Web services network that are required in order to ensure interoperability between Web services.

Web services are most appropriate for applications:

- That must operate over the Internet where reliability and speed cannot be guaranteed;
- Where there is no ability to manage deployment so that all requesters and providers are upgraded at once;
- Where components of the distributed system run on different platforms and vendor products;
- Where an existing application needs to be exposed for use over a network, and can be wrapped as a Web service.

1.3.8.1 Architecture relevance

Field	Description	IoT-A relevance
Architecture description	The architecture is described by several models that are listed below: Message oriented model, Service oriented model, Resource oriented model, Policy Model.	Relevance score: + The architecture is fully described in the last note of the WA working group. However, the architecture description remains high level and does not provide implementation details.
Architecture style	The architecture style is distributed and message oriented: it is described mostly through the interactions that take place between the service requester and the service provider.	Relevance score: - The architecture style of WSA is too broad to be used in IoT-A. Some realisation of this architecture might be more interesting to consider that the global architecture description.
Information model and distribution	The main information that is used in WSA is the service description. There are three leading viewpoints on how a discovery service should be conceived: as a registry, as an index, or as a peer-to-peer system: A registry is an authoritative, centrally controlled store of information. An index is a compilation or guide to information that exists elsewhere. It is not authoritative and does not centrally control the information that it references. With the Peer to Peer view, a requester agent queries its neighbours in search of a suitable Web service. If any one of them matches the request, then it replies. Otherwise each queries its own neighbouring peers and the query propagates through the network until a particular hop count or other termination criterion is reached.	Relevance score: + The basic model is principle suitable for describing entities of interest.
Horizontality	Some element of WSA can be used by other architecture (OWL, Service description,...). The architecture model itself is too broad for it to provide a clear interface.	Relevance score: 0 Some of the component may appear in IoT-A architecture.
Context awareness and	Semantic is addressed through OWL.	Relevance score: 0 Only little information about the

semantic capabilities		technical details of the architecture was available at the time of the review
Technological specificity and interoperability	<p>The WSA should enable the development of interoperable Web services across a wide array of environments. [102]</p> <p>One of the identified requirements of WSA is that WSA does not preclude any programming model.</p> <p>AC023 is comprised of loosely-coupled components and their interrelationships.</p>	Relevance score: 0
Adaptation and self-*	<p>The architecture does not specify how web services are implemented and does not impose restriction on their composition allowing each developer to implement and update services separately.</p>	<p>Relevance score: 0</p> <p>Adaptation is achieved through very high-level abstraction but self-* is not addressed.</p>

2. State of the Art on IoT Modelling Techniques

This chapter discusses the relevant state of the art on IoT process and service modelling as well as the respective orchestration approaches of IoT resources. The content of this chapter bridges the gap between the traditional world of static process and service modelling that has emerged from the domain of high level enterprise systems and the highly dynamic and massively scalable world of resource constrained IoT devices that have traditionally been unable to participate in any kind of enterprise process or service related activities. As these two domains have been hardly related to each other, a considerable amount of information in this chapter addresses the fundamental concepts and principles of process and service modelling, so that reader with an IoT background are facilitated to fully comprehend and evaluate the relevant state of the art at the intersection of IoT and process modelling. The chapter follows the general structure of the deliverable insofar, as the introduction to modelling principles is followed by respective sections on public research projects, commercial products, and standardization activities. Projects and products are discussed to a lesser extent than respective standardization activities, as IoT-A has a real opportunity to influence and provide a real impact on prominent standardization activities both in the process modelling domain, such as BPMN 2.0 that is expected to emerge during the course of the next year, as well as in the service modelling domain with USDL just starting to mature.

2.1 Modelling principles

This section defines the term process and based on that we specifically introduce the term business process. Therefore, we will combine criteria of different definitions at this point to follow a holistic approach during the IoT-A project. Process in computer science means an instance of a computer program that is executed. Depending on the operating system, a process can be divided into a number of threads that run simultaneously. The resources of a process together with the management information define the process context [137].

A Business Process describes a series of ordered activities that are performed stepwise to achieve an operational goal. A business process describes the flow and transformation of material, information, operations and decisions. Business processes and their activities are structured and have a beginning, an end as well as defined in- and outputs. The recipient of the business process is a client for whom the transformation signifies a certain business value [120], [143], [146], [150].

2.1.1 Description and Methodology

The European Association of BPM defines Business Process Management (BPM) as a systematic approach to capture, execute, measure, document, monitor and control automated and non-automated processes to reach a certain goals [110]. One interesting part for IoT-A of the BPM lifecycle is the business process modelling. In operational use [118] distinguish between two modes of modelling a business processes:

Business level: The goal of the business level is the result-oriented and operational representation of the process. Initially, a rough understanding of the process flow is mediated, in which the process is considered in a few steps without using a process modelling language from bird's eye view. This first model is fundamental for the integration of operational details into the process. From the organizational process model a technical model is developed. To develop such a model a specific proceeding is needed, which depends on the used process modelling language.

Technical level: The objective of the technical level is the implementation of the technical described details. To execute a technical process a so-called process engine can be used. Some process modelling languages currently do not support the direct execution of the process model on a process engine. Therefore it is often necessary to refine the technical process model. If no process engine is used, the process logic is transferred and implemented in a certain programming language.

2.1.2 Execution

Process automation does not necessarily mean that the whole process runs automatically. The process engine is the central component for the execution of process the automation and handles the specified technical process model. The process engine is specialized in the representation of the process logic and is more productive in the process implementation than using a traditional programming environment. Some software solutions [150] supplement the process engine by a separated service bus and other components in order to make them more versatile. The engine has the complete process overview of the execution of individual activities and supports the process controlling with key indicators for evaluating and monitoring the process [110].

2.1.3 Presentation and Notation

Business processes can be modelled by a large number of methods and techniques. In this section we explore in particular some frequently in practice used business process notations with respect of using them in the IoT-A project.

2.1.3.1 The Event-driven Process Chain (EPC)

The Event-driven Process Chain (EPC) is a modelling language for the graphical representation of business processes of organizations. As part of the Architecture of Integrated Information Systems (ARIS), this method was developed for view-oriented modelling of business processes. As part of the ARIS concept the EPC provides business processes in a semi-formal modelling language with syntax rules. In principle, it is possible with EPC to map the control and information flow of a business process. The EPC has been completed to the eEPC, which also contains elements for the organization, data and performance modelling. Thus, non structure-building relationships can be also modelled.

The EPC is distinguished in comparison to other modelling languages by its proximity to standard software systems. Extensive mapping tool support and the ability to model simply event-driven process chains, allow an application in principle in the IoT-A project. It comes to problems with EPC in the identification of organisational changes and system breaks, the mapping of complex activities, as well as in the modelling of monitoring and control activities.

The technical nature of business processes cannot be described by using EPC. To close this gap, a transformation into a more technical orientated view from the business users' requirements is necessary. For this purpose corresponding meta-models already exist [151],[154].

2.1.3.2 The Unified Modelling Language™ (UML)

UML is OMG's most-used specification, and the way the world models not only application structure, behaviour, and architecture, but also business process and data structure. UML is compliant with the object-oriented software development and is continually evolving. The current version, UML 2.0, defines thirteen types of diagrams, divided into three categories: Six diagram types represent static application structure; three represent general types of behaviour; and four represent different aspects of interactions. Although UML will be not used in all the modelling aspects, some of the modelling specifications such as class diagrams will be utilized in elaborating description models for IoT resources.

2.1.3.3 The Business Process Modelling Notation (BPMN)

The Business Process Modelling Notation (BPMN) was developed in 2002 by IBM for the graphical modelling of processes. The Object Management Group (OMG) has adopted BPMN as a standard. The current version is BPMN 1.2 of 2009 and can be accessed as a specification under [141]. The released version 2.0 of BPMN is still expected in 2010, which is already available in draft form [Section BPMN 2.0]. Since BPMN is also a graphical process notation, many meta-models have been developed to convert this into an executable notation. However, the conversions are still limited by several problems, so that current transformations for example to BPEL cannot be considered as a definitive research result.

2.1.3.4 Business Process Execution Language (BPEL)

The Web Services Business Process Execution Language (WS-BPEL) is an XML-based language that allows web services to be composed to more powerful services. These powerful services are usually orchestrated to processes. BPEL was introduced in 2002 in a consortium of large IT companies such as IBM, Microsoft and SAP. Since 2008 BPEL is managed by OASIS and an established standard in the area of the execution languages. The current version 2.0 defines basic activities and structured activities. A standardized graphical representation of BPEL is not available and differs from tool to tool. As demonstrated by the listed sequences and loops, BPEL behaves like a programming language. BPEL is processed block-oriented and brings a rigid control structure. This is an advantage for the process engine and supports various aspects such as error detection or deadlock detection. Nevertheless, the block structure of BPEL heavily differs from the graph based BPMN. Thus the past years have produced many research activities that aim to automate the mapping of the standardized professional models BPMN into the standardized technical models BPEL [118].

2.1.3.5 Yet Another Workflow Language (YAWL)

YAWL [16] is a BPM/Workflow system. YAWL handles complex data, transformations, integration with organizational resources and Web Service integration. It is built in Java and utilises XML Schema, XPath and XQuery for data definition and manipulation. It supports advanced resource allocation policies and dynamic adaptation of workflow policies. YAWL is based on Petri nets and adds

functionality for workflow patterns that are not easy to map onto high level Petri nets. These patterns include involving multiple instances, complex synchronisations and non-local withdrawals.

2.1.4 Services

The term 'service' has been variously defined according to the domain of applicability. The common-sense definition as given in [17] defines a service as "a set of goods or valuable functions offered by a service provider to a customer".

2.1.4.1 Definition

In the telecommunications domain, a service can be seen as "a packaged set of capabilities that is perceived by a human user when interacting with a telecommunications network or a service provider and for which separate billing can be arranged" [18]. The goal of the IOT-A project is to integrate the physical world into the digital world to support more natural machine-to-machine, and human-to-machine interaction and to build more intelligent applications. Under this purview, services can be categorised into two groups: low-level sensor data services (e.g. those represent sensor resources as Web services), and high-level services (e.g. services that provide integration, discovery, semantic reasoning, etc.). The low-level services integrate various data from different resources and provide intermediary results or inputs to high-level services and applications (e.g. reasoning, integration, planning, and recommendation services). High-level services seamlessly integrate the digital world and physical world resources to create context-aware applications and to support various data and event processing tasks.

2.1.4.2 Description and Methodology

The Web Service definition advocates that approaches to interoperable machine-to-machine interaction over a network can vary. Typically, these translate into either SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol)-based or RESTful (Representational State Transfer) Web Services.

SOAP is an XML-based information exchange protocol for a distributed environment. SOAP-based Web services connect service providers and requesters through APIs defined in WSDL for communication and interaction. SOAP uses serialiser and de-serialiser objects to translate an application's native language into SOAP protocols; they also convert data from platform-specific formats into the XML format that SOAP messages use. SOAP-based web services are suited for situations which require a contract between the producer and consumer to be specified in advance through WSDL.

REST services are based on URLs and HTTP's four methods: GET, POST, PUT and DELETE. The principle behind REST is that each unique URL is a representation of some object. The contents of that object can be obtained through HTTP GET and modified through POST or PUT or deleted. REST services provide ease of use as they are lightweight and easy to implement due to the uniform interface. Commercial web services using the REST style include Yahoo WS², Flickr³, del.icio.us⁴ API and technorati⁵. Google implements its WS using SOAP, whereas Amazon and eBay have WS using both methodologies.

2.1.4.3 Web services and semantic service modelling

The shift towards integrating Semantic Web technologies and context information to provide situation awareness to users can be recognised in research initiatives such as the Context-Aware Browser [17] for context-aware Web content on mobile devices and Nokia's smart space shopping mall [18]. The context representation in [19] makes use of the Delivery Context: Client Interfaces (DCCI) [20] method for making context available to Web applications through a browser extension. The application implements RESTful Web Services. Another approach proposes Conceptual Situation Spaces (CSS) [21] to describe situation characteristics as members in geometrical vector spaces, with situation similarity calculated as a function of their Euclidean distance.

Keivanloo et al. [22] outline an architecture for semantic web services by proposing extensions to OWL-S for different input types (explicit, domain-related and general context). A more comprehensive approach is presented in [23] which tackles dynamic service discovery, service engagement, enactment and Quality of Service (QoS). Service discovery involves cached service capability advertisements, which can be filtered in the service engagement step by clients by querying the semantic descriptions.

² <http://developer.yahoo.com/>

³ <http://www.flickr.com/>

⁴ <http://www.delicious.com/>

⁵ <http://technorati.com/>

2.1.4.4 Service models for sensor resource

Abangar et al. describe a service oriented architecture for wireless sensors and actuator networks in [24]. A web service-enabled emergency medical response system using sensor resources in demonstrated in [25]. Priyantha et al. [26] describe an implementation that allows web service clients to use the sensors and at the same the proposed system minimizes code size and energy at the sensor nodes. A service oriented architecture for sensor networks to support network dynamicity, auto-configuration, service discovery is demonstrated in [27]. There also have been a number of works focusing on representation models for sensor data using ontologies, such as [28], [29]. OntoSensor [28] constructs an ontology-based descriptive specification model for sensors by excerpting parts of SensorML descriptions and extending the IEEE Suggested Upper Merged Ontology (SUMO). However, it does not provide a descriptive model for observation and measurement data. The work presented in [29] proposes an ontology-based model for service oriented sensor data and networks, but does not specify how to represent and interpret complex sensor data. The SensorData Ontology developed in [30] is built based on Observations & Measurements" and SensorML specifications defined by the OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE). Some application scenarios with reasoning over the semantically annotated sensor data with rules are described in [31] and [32]. The followings describe common structures and languages to describe services.

2.1.4.5 Web Service Description Language (WSDL)

WSDL [33] is an XML-based language for describing Web Services and how to access them. It functions as a grammar for describing a web service as a collection of access endpoints capable of exchanging messages in a procedure- or document- oriented manner. WSDL includes terminology for defining a web service, the communication endpoint where that service exists, its input and output messages format and an abstract way to declare a binding to a concrete protocol and data format.

WSDL documents are used by service providers to describe their service and then make the service discoverable by publishing the WSDL document in the UDDI repository. When the service is discovered by a client, UDDI sends the description to the client in a SOAP envelope and the client uses the information contained in the WSDL document to locate and use the service. The current WSDL standard operates at the syntactic level and lacks the semantic expressiveness needed to represent the requirements and capabilities of Web Services.

Web Services Description Language 2.0 (WSDL 2.0) provides a model and an XML format to describe Web services. The current specification brings a language for describing abstractions of functionalities provided by a service as well as a framework for describing the concrete details of a service description. In other words, abstract level described inputs and outputs of functionalities, independently from any specific protocol. In parallel, concrete level of service description defines "how" (which protocol) and "where" (which endpoint) functionalities (and therefore service) are offered. These two fundamental stages (abstract and concrete) use a number of constructs to promote reusability of the description and to separate independent design concerns. At an abstract level, the notion of messages describes inputs and outputs of functionalities. Then, an operation concept associates a message exchange pattern with one or more messages. At a concrete level, a binding specifies transport and wire format details for one or more interfaces. An endpoint associates a network address with a binding. And finally, a service groups together endpoints that implement a common interface.

2.1.4.6 Web Service Semantics (WSDL-S)

Web Service Semantics (WSDL-S) defines how to add semantic annotations to various parts of a WSDL document such as input and output message structures, interfaces and operations. In other words, it defines a mechanism to semantically annotate the abstract definition of a service enabling dynamic discovery, composition and invocation of services but does not address the annotation of service implementations. WSDL-S is a W3C member submission since 2005 and gave birth to SA-WSDL, a W3C recommendation. It augments the expressivity of WSDL with semantics by employing concepts analogous to those in OWL-S while being agnostic to the semantic representation language (in other words, WSDL-S does not require service descriptions to be expressed using Ontology Web Language). WSDL-S has been aligned on OWL-S profile model by integrating four main attributes being the **precondition** a service functionality must comply with, the **effect** thrown after the invocation of such service functionality, a **modelReference** conceptualizing input(s) and output that a service functionality can send (respectively receive) and a **category** to further classify a service. In addition to these attributes, another one called **schemaMapping** has been proposed to mediate semantic structures coming from different domain models, in particular when composing services together.

2.1.4.7 OWL-S

OWL-S [34] is a Service Description Framework that provides both rich expressive descriptions and well-defined semantics. OWL-S provides the main attributes to describe services and their functional attributes. OWL-S describes the characteristics of a service by using three top-level concepts, namely ServiceProfile, Service-Grounding, and ServiceModel. Service profile allows for the specification and discovery of services. Within OWL-S the profile offers provider information ('who provides the service?'), a functional description (inputs and outputs, preconditions and effects), and non-functional properties such as categorisation and quality rating. Service model describes the service's operation and enables invocation, composition, and monitoring of a service. Service grounding provides details on how to access a service, i.e. protocol and message formats, serialisation, transport, and addressing. It should be noted that although OWL-S uses WSDL as its grounding mechanism (however it is not only restricted to WSDL). It should be noted that OWL-S does not attempt to replace or reinvent Web service standards but rather attempts to provide a semantic layer enabling Web Services to be defined in an unambiguous and computer-interpretable form.

2.1.4.8 Web Application Description Language (WADL)

The Web Application Description Language (WADL) [119] is an XML-based language for describing REST-like services that are accessible via HTTP. A WADL document describes the services as an application consisting of several resources identified by a URL and specifies the syntax of the request and response for each HTTP method. Compared to other service description languages such as WSDL, the benefit of WADL lies in its simplicity. On the downside however, WADL is restricted to REST-like services and is not yet widely supported. It also competes with WSDL 2.0 that is able to describe REST-like services. WADL therefore seems less suitable to use as a basis for describing services in IoT-A.

2.1.4.9 Universal Service Description Language (USDL)

USDL is developed by the SAP consortium [154] and is presented in the standardization section 2.4.2.1. This section focuses on recent research activities published in November 2010 by Nakazawa [137]. Here, USDL is a new XML-based service description language, which enables semantic descriptions for humans and machines, which is used for native devices in the semantic space of the middleware DuMiddle's. USDL also serves as a means for runtime configuration of translators based on device semantics and enables mapper to configure translators for different device types from a generic implementation. As this service description concepts focuses on functional IoT aspects regarding the description and interaction of real-world resources, there is the possibility to reuse this approach within IoT-A and to match it with more comprehensive description approaches including also non-functional service aspects [138].

2.1.5 Eventing

An important aspect of IoT-A is the monitoring of objects or things that constitute our real, physical world. As these things naturally change their state, e.g. a pallet moving from storage to a truck, it is important to deal with asynchronous events that are triggered by state changes by these things. These include both architectural challenges to deal with large number of events and processing events, e.g. for deriving higher level information describing a state or condition of a more global scope than that of an individual sensor.

2.1.5.1 Complex Event Processing

In Complex Event Processing (CEP) [111] events are used as first class objects. Events are usually described as logic predicates enabling Boolean operations for inferring semantically richer events. While one single event is just a collection of data, a system state is a piece of information at a much higher abstraction level. In particular, events are mostly classified according to a hierarchy of importance, like Information, Notice, Warning, Error, Alert. Systems states and events need to be role-specific. While a system monitor of a production line is just interested in the flow capacity, a maintenance engineer might need to see the state of a particular subsection of the system. Thus different views are necessary and need to be modelled due the requirements of different roles of users. While CEP is very powerful and has been applied to many IoT-relevant domains, a major challenge is to extend it with statefulness in order to detect global states.

2.1.5.2 Stateful Eventing

Another approach to eventing is to model real world state information as first class objects rather than the events. Events then occur as results of subscriptions to a high level state of interest that is modelled within the system. In these approaches, global state detection is simply achieved by transformation, fusion and aggregation of lower level state information and their changes. SENSEI is

an example of such a system (see section 2.2.2): it uses state modelling and state subscriptions as basic approach but also supports an event subscription interface.

2.1.5.3 Event Web

Defining and using event in high-level applications is described in the Event Web [37]. The Event Web (EW) concept is a thin layer on top of the Web that monitors information sources and responds to changing conditions. It is the platform for Sense and Respond (S&R) applications that continuously respond to critical conditions. S&R systems can act as both control and decision-support systems. S&R applications monitor events both inside and outside an enterprise boundary and integrate information from multiple event sources. Since data from such distributed sources may be imprecise or incorrect, S&R systems place great emphasis on asynchrony and imprecision. The EW is based on two building blocks: Service Oriented Architecture (SOA), Event-Driven Architecture (EDA).

2.2 Public project solutions

This section discusses the most relevant publicly funded research projects that are related to the modelling of IoT resources or services. While the primary focus is on FP6 and FP7 research initiatives funded by the European commission, we do also include national activities such as the SemProM project funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research as well as company specific research such as SAP Gravity.

Some of the work presented here is also relevant for other chapters within this deliverable. This is due to the fact that in the case of large Integrated Projects such as SENSEI the research objectives are often rather diverse and broad, so that individual projects might affect different research disciplines. In order to prevent duplication of information we exclusively relate to information relevant to IoT Modelling in this chapter and leave other aspects to different parts of the deliverable.

2.2.1 SemProM – Semantic Product Memories

SemProM [148] is a project funded by the German Federal Ministry for Education and Research under its IKT-2020 programme. The SemProM project as such was already covered in the previous chapter of this deliverable, so that our focus within this chapter is on the contributions of the project specific to modelling and orchestration.

As it has been discussed before, SemProM is primarily concerned with storing information on devices and resources, including the respective data formats and also appropriate hardware platforms. From a modelling perspective, SemProM addresses the orchestration and administration of IoT resources by contributing a runtime and modelling platform called “Real World Integration Platform” that is highly relevant for the IoT-A service modelling tasks, as it is official background IP to the project and will be augmented to cope with the requirements identified in WP6. Essentially, RWIP provides abstractions to IoT devices such as e.g. RFID readers by defining appropriate interfaces and allows for orchestrating them through an Eclipse-based design time modelling tool called “Site Manager”. In essence, the Site Manager connects to different OSGi-“nodes” in which agents are deployed that implement the respective device class specific interfaces and allows for starting, stopping, updating, etc. them based on the standard OSGi mechanisms. Through the “Site Manager” a user can simply configure any smart environment by dragging and dropping respective agent instances as well as the respective relationships between them and then remotely control these “nodes” and the agents running inside the nodes.

While RWIP provides appropriate means of modelling static IoT deployments through interface abstractions and static agent orchestration capabilities, it is not yet capable enough to deal with highly dynamic environments in which resources appear and disappear again, and still provide services and become parts of the execution of business processes. While the static aspects of resource modelling are also appropriate for IoT-A, the dynamics of IoT-A use cases require significantly more versatile modelling and orchestration concepts.

2.2.2 SENSEI

The SENSEI project, quite closely linked to IoT-A for both themes and contributors, was already discussed before. Here, we strictly focus on the modelling aspects of resources. Resources are the core concept in the SENSEI architecture, all sensors, actuators, and processors are modelled as Resources. WS&ANs can be modelled as resources in different ways: for instance, one sensor may correspond to one resource, or the whole WS&AN may be modelled as one or more resources. The Resource concept and the uniform Resource Descriptions enable Resource Users to homogeneously discover and access the heterogeneous substrate of WS&ANs.

The Resource Model [158] clearly models the important aspects of Resources, especially their functionalities, and where and how they can be accessed. Whereas the Resource Model provides a conceptual view, relating the important aspects, the concrete instantiation of this information can be

found in the Resource Description, which is published to the Resource Directory that acts as a service repository.

To allow human users to find Resources, it may be sufficient in certain cases to describe the Resources with a number of keywords or free text tags. However, simple free-style tags are clearly insufficient for any machine-based interaction, where the planning and execution of a request is to be executed by a machine. Here the syntax and semantics of the interfaces need to be clearly defined. These semantic aspects are part of the Advanced Resource Description the tags are part of the Basic Resource Description.

Figure 1. SENSEI Resource Model

The Advanced Resource Description [155] is defined as an ontology that describes the resource semantically by its location, resource type (Sensor, Processor, Actuator), and its operations. The most important aspect for a Resource is the result it can produce. For Sensor Resources and Processing Resources this is the information they can collect; for Actuator Resources it is the post-condition of effect that is achieved after invoking them.

Figure 2. SENSEI Advanced Resource Description

The Semantic Operation Description defines semantically the operations offered by the resource. For each operation it specifies the inputs that a resource takes in order to provide each output, the pre-conditions and the post-conditions derived from invoking an operation and the temporal availability of the operation. The Observation Area describes physical area for which an operation offered by a resource can provide information or perform an actuation task. As example for a satellite resource, the Observation Area would be the area of the Earth which is observed by the satellite, whereas the Location of the satellite is its position in its orbit around the Earth. To discover the Resources available in a SENSEI system a semantic query language like SPARQL can be used to define in what information the user is interested.

An important aspect of SENSEI is accessing sensors and actuators via a single point of access. In SENSEI this has been realized via the Semantic Query Resolver (SQR) that provides interfaces for accessing resources directly or declaratively. Declarative information access is facilitated by using the context layer of the information model that models information as entity/attribute pairs in which an entity typically relates to physical things such as rooms, pallets, or lights. For actuation SENSEI has developed a declarative Actuation Task that supports actuation both on resource level and on context level. For instance, on context level it can be specified that lights of a certain room should be turned on. The language supports scheduling of actuation tasks and conditional execution. For instance, it can be specified that only lights in the vicinity of the user should be turned on. SENSEI actuation tasks thus support a basic way of modelling goal oriented IoT-Aware processes that can be triggered by changes in monitored things.

ALLOW [104] is concerned with developing "a new programming paradigm for human-oriented pervasive applications". The objective of the project is to define so-called Adaptable Pervasive Flows (APF) in pervasive environments. APFs resemble traditional work flows, but have the capability to adapt themselves according to changing environments. The concept of an APF is based on the idea that flow descriptions are embedded in entities such as people or movable things. As the environment and the context of the moving entity changes the executed flow changes according to changes in the environment and may even change itself. ALLOW seeks to execute flows distributed and dynamically across existing devices in the current environment. The ALLOW Deliverable D3.1 [153] describes an initial design in which BPEL flows are annotated with WS-Policy and WS-Policy-Attachment [155] to realize the above concepts. In addition security annotations are used to define constraints on the execution of the flows. ALLOW is a Future and Emerging Technologies (FET) project funded by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Programme.

2.2.4 LPML (SOA4All)

Lightweight process modelling is a combination of techniques that seek to lower the entry barrier for process modelling. This includes fostering a more participative style of modelling and providing a forum for the community of experts. The SAO4All European project [150] introduces the Lightweight Process Modelling Language (LPML) [132][133]. The design principles that we can find in this language can be summarized as: 1.) Context-awareness, the names of the activities and tasks involved in a process model should be unified. 2.) Usability and Reusability through the adoption of BPMN symbols and goal related notations for describing a control flow of a process now, 3.) Flexibility, activities and tasks can invoke different Web services.

This in general allows describing and defining both IoT elements and IoT architecture in an agnostic view. The abstraction allows using different type of communications with the IoT components. The problem that we can find here is that the tools needed to use are developed into this specific project, which will be finished by the next year. We cannot take it for granted that the tools work as expected after the finalization of the project and we will still have some type of support or evolution of the tools. Consequently, IoT-A needs to evaluate them while the project is still ongoing and ensure a smooth transition, if they appear to be appropriate also for the IoT specific aspects of process modelling that IoT-A is mainly concerned with.

2.2.5 SAP Gravity

SAP Gravity [131] is a prototype that SAP Research developed 2009 for the collaborative business process modelling. The concepts of SAP Gravity have been implemented as a gadget for SAP Streamworks and Google Wave. In addition, parts of Gravity were integrated into the SAP product SAP NetWeaver BPM. SAP Gravity enables its participants to use the functionality of business process modelling of the SAP NetWeaver BPM in real time. This allows to model new business processes or to adapt existing business processes across organizational boundaries by various participants. SAP NetWeaver BPM provides the transformation of the graphical modelled process into an executable process, which can be executed by the process engine. Creating a new process model the additions of each modeller is coded in a different colour to highlight the parts of one participant. The process model is documented with the help of the collaborative tool technology. A module checks the syntax of the generated process model and provides a possibility to export the model into a BPMN 2.0 XML document. Since the Internet of Things is not limited to one organization, SAP Gravity would provide IoT-A the possibility to model IoT-Aware business processes in a collaborative context across organizational boundaries. Proven methodologies of Gravity could be used as an input for the IoT-aware business process modelling tool implementation proposed in the project DOW.

2.2.6 E-SENSE

The e-SENSE project [115] is aimed at capturing ambient intelligence through wireless sensor networks (WSNs) to provide a user, seamless access to new application classes. The WSNs considered include body, object and environment sensor networks. It supports the concept of sensor gateways for binding SNs to B3G networks and service platforms. The reference architecture consists of application, management, middleware and connectivity subsystems. The application subsystem hosts sensor applications and performs management or configuration accessing to application requirements. The management subsystem implements service and node discovery and location service and configures and initialises the middleware and connectivity subsystems. The middleware provides publish/subscribe abstraction for information exchange between nodes and back-end applications as well as data transfer services for application data. The connectivity layer implements the physical, MAC, network and transport functions.

The USDL Editor [154] provided by SAP Research is a web-based editor in order to create USDL service descriptions (for details on USDL see forthcoming section **Error! Reference source not found.**). The created service descriptions are stored in USDL files. The current version 3 of the editor prototype can be seen as an expert tool for providing first insights into the new USDL concept. The version 4 of the editor with an improved and more intuitive graphical user interface is expected to be available in 2011 as part of the USDL W3C-standardization process. The USDL Editor is based on the Eclipse development environment and can be obtained at [154] as an Eclipse-Plug-in.

In case of applying USDL as a service description language within the scope of the IoT-A project, WP2 could benefit of the provided tool functionalities. Moreover, in case of extending the USDL concept by IoT-specific aspects, the extendable USDL Editor could be used for creating USDL service descriptions of IoT and IoS services as part of the Future Internet Layer that will be developed in WP2.

Figure 3: Steps of service life cycle

2.3 Commercial products

In this section we describe products for modelling services and processes.

2.3.1 Process

This section describes products for modelling processes. We distinguish between products for desktop computers and web-based modelling tools.

2.3.1.1 Desktop Applications

Various desktop applications for modelling processes exist. In the following subsections we first describe ARIS, an enterprise modelling tool. Then we describe tools for the Microsoft's visualization software Visio. Finally we cover tools for the Eclipse platform, a widely-used tool for software development.

2.3.1.1.1 ARIS

ARIS (Architecture of Integrated Information System) is an enterprise modelling tool useful for defining and running business processes in the enterprise. The ARIS concept was developed by August Wilhelm Scheer at the Institute for Business Computing at University of the Saarland, Germany, while now it is continued by IDS Scheer AG, Saarbrücken⁶. ARIS was intended to achieve a corporate information system which completely meets its users' requirements. This concept relies on subdividing a corporate model into various description views and description levels, which allow for specifying single elements using dedicated methods without considering the complete model. ARIS is build upon the so-called ARIS House, an architecture incorporating five views. These views refer to organisation, data, service, function, and control of a process. This fragmentation is intended to reduce the complexity of the corporate model according to the five views and to ease process modelling: Function view, Data view, Organizational view, Service view, and Control view. ARIS implements the methodology of a sequential development process: it starts with the problem description which is followed by a technical design which is then followed by an ICT design which finally results into the implementation. Here, the technical design specifies the corporate concepts to which the ICT design is the equivalent in an ICT development language. There are similarities to the hierarchy of Computational Independent Model (CIM) and Platform Independent Model (PIM). This development process is applied to those views. First, there is an abstract high-level description language, which is in the next step transferred into a more concrete representation like UML and, finally, into executable code. These steps are applied to all of the views where specific tools are provided to support users in producing technical design, ICT design and code for all data, functions, services, resources and control.

2.3.1.1.2 Visio-based Tools

This section focuses on giving an overview of available business process modelling tools based on Microsoft Visio. Visio is a widely used visualization software for Microsoft Windows. Visio is used to produce graphics by using different templates, tools and symbols. The resulting diagrams are easy to embed as drag and drop, but also as a separate file (*. vsd) in other documents. The application supports the creation of flowcharts, business processes and UML diagrams. The latest version of

⁶see www.ids-scheer.com and [106]

2010 supports in detail the representation of business processes using BPMN templates that contain the BPMN 1.2 shapes and rules [149]. In addition, various plug-ins based on Microsoft Visio are available on the market. A direct BPEL support is currently not possible from Visio, but the possibility to export a created BPMN diagram as .xml file to proceed with a BPEL-based tool. For Visio 2007 a plug-in called Process Modeller BPMN as well as a free Visio BPMN Stencil template offered by the company orbussoftware is available. The Process Modeller BPMN by the company itp-commerce extends Visio by the BPMN notation according to the standard 1.2 and 2.0. The application allows automated process documentation and reporting, simulation, team repository and standard mapping to BPEL, XPD or XLANG / s. In addition to the available shapes and rules for the model creation, it is possible to check the business process for syntax. The plug-in is available in various versions, but the company also offers a free version. The advantage of Visio-based tools is that they provide end-user friendly interfaces to create BPMN or UML diagrams, which could be interesting for the IoT-A project context. However, Visio concentrates on process modelling and does not provide extensive support to model executable processes [130].

2.3.1.1.3 Eclipse-based Tools

This section describes some Eclipse-based products in the area of process modelling. Eclipse is an open source programming tools for software development. Originally Eclipse was used as an integrated development environment for Java, but now it is used for its extensibility for many other development tasks such as the development of a process modelling and execution tool. Eclipse itself is based on Java technology, since version 3.0 on an OSGi framework called Equinox [114]. On the market a variety of different Eclipse-based process modelling tools are available. Due to the length limitations of this deliverable, this section will focus on the selection of eBPMN, Eclipse BPEL and Oracle BPEL Process Manager as well-known tools. Further Eclipse-based solutions are for example UML2, BPMN2, Papyrus, BPMN Modeler and Bonita Open Solution. eBPMN is available as a desktop application. The product itself is therefore fully integrated into Eclipse and can be combined with other plug-ins. As stated by the name, the eBPMN Designer is based on the BPMN language. It mainly targets developers and requires at least a small amount of knowledge on how to use the Eclipse IDE in order to create new models and projects. The full object model is based on the BPMN 1.0 specification [113]. The Oracle BPEL Process Manager provides a developer-friendly and reliable solution for designing, deploying and managing BPEL business processes. It has been one of the first well-known and highly distributed process editors in the market and is available as a standalone application, although being implemented on top of Eclipse. The BPEL Designer Project aims to add comprehensive support to Eclipse for the definition, authoring, editing, deploying, testing and debugging of WS-BPEL 2.0 processes. By providing these tools, this project aims to build a community around support for BPEL in Eclipse. The implementation is extensible to third-party vendors in a number of ways. The Eclipse-based desktop approaches mainly aim technical orientated people and developers that want to create business models for reflecting their IT processes. All approaches do not include an end-user oriented approach and do not include the possibility to share process models with other persons. The process modelling tools are mostly based on BPMN and BPEL, which could generally be complemented with IoT-specific modelling details as the tools are extensible.

2.3.1.2 Web 2.0 and Collaborative Applications

In this section we cover web-based tools for processing modelling. This includes ARISalign, a community oriented tool for business process modelling, and IYOPORO, a Silverlight-based software for workflow and business process management.

2.3.1.2.1 ARISalign

ARISalign is the first social Business Process Management (BPM) platform and community in the world. Launched in spring 2010, it offers tools for both social networking and process design and modelling where users of the platform may cover process users, IT and process experts, and executives, likewise. Since the ARIS originator IDS Scheer was taken over by Software AG⁷. Information is not very rich; most of it comes from the vendor and is more a product marketing rather than a system evaluation. The main motivation for using ARISalign according to the vendor is that process improvement needs effective collaboration. Technical aid is provided by means of social networking tools as a platform for setting up domain independent collaboration and process design and modelling tools with intuitive usability for jointly producing result in the domain of business process

⁷information is available from
<http://www.softwareag.com/corporate/community/arisalign/default.asp> and
<http://www.arisalign.com/>, from Internet publications or from blogs or twitters

management. The social networking approach is basically useful for addressing large groups and within these to identify people for projects collaboration. Its center is an electronic whiteboard with virtual Post-it objects for collecting ideas about processes and particular process steps. These Post-its may be added with comments and may be placed and moved. ARISalign produces a basic process model from the whiteboard and the included Post-its according to their relations. ARISalign supports import and export of several popular formats among which are Aris Express, webMethods, XPDL, and Visio. For read and write of specific company-internal formats some administrative efforts are necessary. ARISalign promises easy installation, simple availability, and high portability of models and artefacts between various popular formats of various Business Process Management (BPM) vendors and tools. It runs in a secure environment. It furthermore enables users to create applications and to offer them in an internal marketplace equivalently to the human resource marketplace for experts from certain locations, verticals, or infrastructures. Applications are posted on the Amazon's Web Service Cloud platform in a Software-as-a-Service manner. It is currently free of charge.

2.3.1.2.2 IYOPORO

IYOPORO is a Silverlight-based software for workflow and business process management (BPM), which includes both the BPMN standard and the future BPMN 2.0 standard (Business Process Model and Notation). The company intellivate was originally focused on process consulting. In the end of 2008 the company launched an implementation of BPMN in a Silverlight application to the BPM market. Thus, the conditions were added to offer Business Process Management as Software as a Service solution. Here, the web application focused on the two core functions: process modelling and process simulation. The intuitive user interface allows users to model processes without having a special IT knowledge. The web application supports location-independent process modelling. The modeled processes are stored in a process repository. By supporting BPMN 2.0 notation, the process models can be created in process and collaboration, choreography and conversation diagrams. The business process modelling IYOPRO is vector-oriented and limited by the process design. The Application provides collaboration features that enable to work in collaboration with partners on process models. Moreover, IYOPRO supports the integration of media such as video communications, voice and text messages. Furthermore, the application supports both a top-down and bottom-up process modelling approach. IYOPRO enables seamless integration of modelling, simulation and workflow execution in one tool. A further functionality enables the user to simulate the modeled business processes, which differentiates between event simulation and business process analysis. By the flow simulation it is possible to perform tasks such as checking for consistency and practicability, the detection of infinite loops, the recognition of loose ends and never reached process steps, the visualization of different process paths and parallel or sequential process steps. Using the functionality of business process analysis, business processes can be analyzed regarding process indicators out of certain business situations such as the utilization of a resource, the costs, process cycle time, capital commitment or efficiency [121].

2.3.2 OWL-S Editor

OWL-S is one of the mayor Semantic Web Service (SWS) description languages for ontologies. OWL-S Editor is a tool whose objective is to allow easy, intuitive OWL-S service development for users who are not experts in OWL-S and to provide a variety of special-purpose capabilities to facilitate SWS design. The editor is implemented as a plugin to the Protégé OWL ontology editor. The OWL-S Editor is developed as open source software⁸. OWL-S supplies a Web service designer with a core set of mark-up language constructs for describing the properties and capabilities of a Web service in unambiguous, computer-interpretable form. Following the layered approach to markup language development, the current version of OWL-S builds on the Ontology Web Language (OWL) Candidate Recommendation produced by the Web-Ontology Working Group at the World Wide Web Consortium. OWL-S introduces ontologies to describe the concepts in the services' domain and generic concepts to describe the services themselves and how they relate to the domain ontologies (via inputs and outputs, preconditions and effects, and so on). These semantically rich descriptions enable automated machine reasoning over service and domain descriptions, thus supporting automation of service discovery, composition, and execution, and reducing manual configuration and programming efforts.

2.4 Standardization activities

This section presents the most relevant standardization activities related to the definition of IoT resources and services. We have divided the content in three subsections, process, service and sensor modelling.

⁸ can be downloaded from <http://owlseditor.semwebcentral.org/>

2.4.1 Process

In this section we describe standards for describing processes. According to the definition of Johansson et al. [123] a process is "a set of linked activities that take an input and transform it to create an output. Ideally, the transformation that occurs in the process should add value to the input and create an output that is more useful and effective to the recipient either upstream or downstream."

2.4.1.1 SensorML

The OpenGIS® Sensor Model Language Encoding Standard (SensorML) [140] specifies models and XML encoding that provide a framework within which the geometric, dynamic, and observational characteristics of sensors and sensor systems can be defined. There are many different sensor types, from simple visual thermometers to complex electron microscopes and earth observing satellites. These can all be supported through the definition of atomic process models and process chains.

The main purposes of SensorML include to provide descriptions of sensors and sensor systems in order to allow the management and inventory of them; provide sensor and process information in order to allow the observation and resource discovery; support sensor observations processing and analysis; support the geolocated observed values (measured data); provide performance characteristics (e.g., accuracy, threshold, etc.); provide an explicit description of the process by which an observation was obtained (i.e., its lineage); provide an executable process chain for deriving new data products on demand (i.e., derivable observation); and archive fundamental properties and assumptions regarding sensor systems.

Besides it, SensorML can, but generally does not, provides hardware description of a sensor. Rather it is a functional model in order to describe the sensor. Additionally, SensorML separates the sensor from its associated platform(s) and target(s). Both are treated as separate entities. Sensors is viewed as being able to measure physical quantities, a platform may be able to determine its own instantaneous orientation and position (although this information would be obtained by others sensors connected to the platform). Typically a sensor will be modelled as consisting of one or more detectors, whereas a platform will be modelled as a System that contains all of the sensors and defines positional and temporal relationships among them.

Through SensorML, it is possible to specify both the information that an IoT Resource can provide (syntactically and semantically) with the O&M definition and the functionality that can provide this resource. Additionally, SensorML allows the definition of Task Plan in order to combine chain of resource to produce a specific measurement of the Real World. Together with it, this solution is adopted by very important group in the M2M industry how the standard solution to provide information with sensors. It drives us to consider it like one of the best solution to be adopted within the project both the standards point of view and integrated solution point of view.

2.4.1.2 OMA NGSI Context API

As part of its Next Generation Service Interface (NGSI), the Open Mobile Alliance (OMA) [129] has defined a Context API [158] that is intended to simplify management and access to context producing software components. Context as defined by OMA relates to information about people, places and things. In particular, the actual context information accessed by the API is not only a measured value such as 29 degrees to indicate a temperature, but is associated with an entity such as a room.

The information model of the OMA NGSI Context API is almost identical to the information model of the context layer in the SENSEI architecture [158] and well suited to model information related to things as required by IoT-A. The modelling approach complements sensor oriented data models such as the SENSEI Observation and Measurement [158] layer or the one used by the OGC Sensor Web Enablement (see Section 2.4.3.4).

The Context API supports operations both for Context Source and Context Information Management. Operations for Context Source Management include registration and discovery of context sources. Context Information Management includes update, query and subscription operations.

2.4.1.3 BPMN 2.0

The new version Business Model and Notation (BPMN) 2.0 promises to bridge the gap between the business and the technical level of process modelling. So far, BPMN 2.0 is a non-released and in the process for being standardized by the OMG. The latest specification is the version BPMN 2.0 Beta 2, which is based on the version BPMN 1.1 and can be accessed at [151].

The biggest improvements compared to further version and in terms of the IoT-A project scope include the introduction of defined execution semantics and an XML serialization format. The following two different XML schemas have been defined:

- **Model Exchange:** The XML schema contains detailed information on transforming a BPMN model to a different modelling tool, so that process models can be exchanged

between different tools by different organizations. This also includes the graphical process information.

- Execution semantics: The XML Schema describes how technical details of the process are stored so that process models can be run directly from BPMN 2.0 compliant process engines.

Therewith BPMN 2.0 is the first notation, which combines an end-user friendly notation with a technical specification of an executable model in the same process model. [157] In particular, the integrated execution semantics promise progress, since the efforts of recent years to translate BPMN to BPEL automatically can be omitted. Additional interesting features of the BPMN version 2.0 for IoT-A include an extended notation, a detailed mapping of BPMN to BPEL, new forms of events and event depended sub-processes [118]. By now there are several large IT companies such as SAP, which offers the new BPMN 2.0-elements on their modelling tools as well as the XML files for serialisation and execution [152].

2.4.1.4 BPEL4People

BPEL4People is the WS-BPEL Extension for People [159] as proposed in a joint white paper by IBM and SAP in July 2005. Web Services Business Process Execution Language, version 2.0 (WS-BPEL 2.0 or BPEL for brevity) introduces a model for business processes based on Web services. A BPEL process orchestrates interactions among different Web services. In practice, however many business process scenarios require human interactions. This specification, based on the WS-HumanTask specification [103], introduces a BPEL extension to address this human interactions in BPEL as a first-class citizen which allows specifying tasks local to a process or use tasks defined outside of the process definition.

Otherwise, it is out of scope of this specification how to be deployed or monitored processes with human interactions.

BPEL4People utilizes the following specifications:

- WS-BPEL 2.0: BPEL4People extends the WS-BPEL 2.0 process model and uses existing WS-BPEL 2.0 capabilities, such as those for data manipulation.
- WS-HumanTask 1.0: BPEL4People uses the definition of human tasks and, notifications, and extends generic human roles and people assignments introduced in WS-HumanTask 1.0.
- WSDL 1.1: BPEL4People uses WSDL for service interface definitions.
- XML Schema 1.0: BPEL4People utilizes XML Schema data model.
- XPath 1.0: BPEL4People uses XPath as default query and expression language.

2.4.2 Service

The term 'service' in this context is defined as "a mechanism to enable access to one or more capabilities, where the access is provided using a prescribed interface and is exercised consistent with constraints and policies as specified by the service description." [139].

2.4.2.1 USDL

The Unified Service Description Language (USDL) is a platform-neutral service description language that was developed by a consortium of SAP, Siemens, DFKI and Attensity within different research projects. Since September 2010 by means of a W3C Incubator Group a standardization activity started, which has focused on the specification and the further development of USDL as an open standard. At this stage there are 8 modules in USDL version 3.0 available.

USDL aims to support the implementation of Web-based services on the Internet. The following types of services are supported by USDL: manual services, transactional services or information services, software services, services related to digital media platform, and infrastructure services. There is already a large number of existing service description approaches which can be divided into different categories [154]. Each category has its own motivation and representation needs. USDL covers in comparison to existing approaches IT and economical aspects, which serve for reference and communication purposes as well as involve information regarding the value chains. The USDL specification consists of a variety of modules, each addressing different aspects of the service description. The modularity supports the improved readability of the comprehensive model. Each module symbolizes the perspective on a particular aspect of the service, at which the parts of the modules interact crosswise and are interdependent from each other. The services may be either automatic, semi automatic and manual services. It is also possible to describe single (atomic) services as well as orchestrated services [126].

For IoT-A there is the option to use USDL as a service description language in the project. Moreover, there is the possibility to participate in the standardization process and to make an IoT specific contribution to USDL in order to close the gap between the Internet of Things and Internet of Services.

2.4.2.2 SoaML

The SoaML (Service oriented architecture Modelling Language) specification [134] is created by the OMG (Object Management Group, Inc.) in response to the UPMS RFP (UML Profile and Metamodel for Services) and describes a UML profile and metamodel for the design of services within a service-oriented architecture. SoaML provides a standard way to architect and model SOA solutions using the Unified Modelling Language® (UML®). The profile uses the built-in extension mechanisms of MOF and UML to define SOA concepts in terms of existing UML concepts.

SoaML allows to support both IT and business perspective on SOA. SOA is an approach to systems architecture, where we can see the architecture how things can best work together. Systems, in this context, include organizations, communities, processes as well as information technology systems. This allows describing sensor like things and the IoT architecture like a system. Besides it, SOA has been associated with a variety of approaches and technologies. In order to resolve the agnostic technology selection, MDA technology is used [135]. MDA allow abstracting the architecture that you use and talk only in bits and byte. Software development in the MDA starts with a Platform-Independent Model (PIM) and continue to the Platform-Specific Model (PSM) in which we have the characteristics of the platform that we want to use.

OMG recognizes three levels of MDA-based specifications:

- The Pervasive Services, including Enterprise necessities such as Directory Services, Transactions, Security, and Event handling (Notification).
- The Domain Facilities, in industries such as Healthcare, Manufacturing, Telecommunications, Biotechnology, and others; and
- Applications themselves, perhaps created and maintained by a software vendor or end user company or enterprise using MDA tools to run an MDA-based methodology, but not standardized by OMG.

2.4.2.3 W3C Activities

The W3C's Semantic Annotations for WSDL (SAWSDL) Working Group [147] has developed a mechanism to enable semantic annotation of WSDL Web Services. Though a formal language, such as ontologies, has not been specified for including semantic elements in WSDL components, the SAWSDL recommendation allows referencing of semantic model concepts by WSDL components as annotations. This has been achieved by extending the WSDL 2.0 elements with three attributes: a modelReference attribute to specify the association between a WSDL component and a concept in some semantic model. This attribute can be used especially to annotate XML Schema type definitions, element declarations, and attribute declarations as well as WSDL interfaces and operations. Two other extension attributes, liftingSchemaMapping and loweringSchemaMapping, are added to XML Schema element declarations and type definitions for specifying mappings between semantic data and XML. These mappings can be used during service invocation.

OWL-S is a W3C submission to provide enriched description for the Web Services (described in section 2.1.2.4.3). The Web Service Modelling Ontology (WSMO) [144] from the W3C Semantic Web Services Interest Group describes various aspects related to Web Services or as they are defined, Semantic Web Services. WSMO is based on Web Service Modelling Framework (WSMF) [117] and extends this framework by developing an ontology and a description language to describe the Web services. WSMO is designed to support automated service discovery, service selection and service composition. Ontologies are used to provide a mechanism to describe and represent services, making the data machine-interpretable. WSMO also introduces the concept of "goals" which is a way of describing what the user wants to achieve. Mediators are then used to ensure interoperability in cases where there is an inconsistency in the data that is used for communication between two services. A limitation of WSMO is that it focuses on describing 'web services' rather than the concept of a 'service' which can be of any type. This makes it difficult to use WSMO to describe other types of services which can be provided in a IOT environment.

2.4.3 Sensor Modelling

This section shows the different approximation, all of them based on XML technologies, that the standard organization are following to model the information and services that sensors have to provide.

2.4.3.1 - IEEE 1451

The IEEE 1451 standard [127] is a universally accepted transducer (sensors or actuators) interface standard. It is a suite of Smart Transducer Interface Standards and describes a set of open, network-independent communication interfaces for connecting transducers to microprocessors, instrumentation systems, and networks. The key feature of this standard is the Transducer Electronic Data Sheets (TEDS) describing the capability and characteristics of individual sensors (identification, calibration,

correction data, measurement range, and manufacture-related information). TEDS does not capture any derived semantics from sensor data, nor does it capture how the sensor is used, or parameters such as the location, or sensor conditions. The object-based schema of IEEE 1451 makes sensors accessible to clients over a network through a Network Capable Application Processor (NCAP), which can act as an interface to OGC services. OGC SWE services can act as clients of IEEE 1451 NCAP services and TEDS documents, thus enabling interactions with heterogeneous sensor systems.

2.4.3.2 - ANSI N42.42

ANSI N42.42 [128] provides a standard to facilitate manufacturer independent transfer of information from radiation measurement instruments. In particular, it provides an XML-based data interchange format for the Department of Homeland Security's radiation instruments. The five instrument types addressed are: alarming personal radiation detectors, portable radiation detection instrumentation, radionuclide identifier detectors, radiation detection portal monitors and spectroscopy-based portal monitors. It provides a single format for all radiation detectors, with XML also acting as a database, with retrieval using XPath. The standard is not concerned with the definition of communication with the instruments, instrument operation or inclusion of data for a unique implementation or algorithm. Each element specified in the body of the standard with its parent and child elements, data types of its contents, accepted attributes and how many times it can appear.

2.4.3.3 - CBRN-CCSI

Common Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear (CBRN) Sensor Interface (CCSI) [124] is a set of common standards that enable CBRN sensor interoperability, net centric operations, and ease of integration into command and control systems. It is the standard for sensor physical and electronic interfaces, including component interconnects, power, external connectors, XML communications and a standard basic command set. The CCSI standard includes summary and architecture, physical interface and electronic interface standards. It provides common sensor interface performance requirements and recommendations for sensor architecture and implementation. The common attributes that were candidates for standardisation are sensor installation, sensor power, sensor communications, sensor operation, sensor environments and sensor security.

2.4.3.4 - OGC sensor description standards

The OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) initiative is aimed at web accessible sensor networks and archived sensor data that can be discovered and accessed using standard protocols and APIs. The standards consist of modelling schemas (O&M and SensorML) and Web Service interfaces (SAS, SPS and SOS) that facilitate the exchange of information through APIs. The defined standards include the following [109]:

- Observations and Measurements Schema (O&M) – XML schema for encoding both real-time and archived observations and measurements from a sensor. The properties of an observation include 'feature of interest', 'observed property', 'sampling time', 'result' and 'procedure'. Feature of interest can include any real world entity such as coverage region, vehicle or weather storm. Procedure refers to a sensor or sensor system defined within a SensorML document.
- Sensor Model Language (SensorML) - XML schemas for describing sensor systems and processes. It is described in detail in section 2.4.1.1.
- Sensor Observation Service (SOS) – standard web service interface for requesting, filtering and retrieving observations and sensor system information. SOS groups observations made by related sensor systems into an 'observation offering', which is a logical collection of sensors that are generally located in proximity to each other and sample their environment at shared intervals. The 'core' service profile includes three operations: 'GetCapabilities' (to request the service description), 'DescribeSensor' (SensorML description) and 'GetObservation' (O&M schema instance).
- Sensor Planning Service (SPS) – Web service interface for requesting user driven acquisitions and observations. It includes interfaces for determining the feasibility of a sensor planning request, for submitting a request, inquiring its status, updating or cancelling the request.
- Sensor Alert Service (SAS) – Web service interface for publishing and subscribing to alerts from sensors. SAS defines an alert as a special kind of notification indicating that an event has occurred at an object of interest. It must be noted that SAS itself acts as a registry rather than an event notification system.
- Web Notification Service (WNS) – Web service interface for asynchronous delivery of messages or alerts from SAS and SPS web services.

2.4.3.5 SSN W3C Ontology

The W3C Semantic Sensor Networks Incubator Group (SSN-XG) [158] has developed an ontology for describing sensors. The SSN-XG ontology models the sensor from device, process and system point of views. It includes different operational, device related and quality of information attributes that are related to sensing devices. The ontology also describes the operational range, battery and power and environmental ranges that are specified for sensor devices. The SSN-XG ontology has been also aligned with DOLCE ontology [112] to include more generic terms to related sensor descriptions to other attributes such as units of measurement and deployment platform.

The SSN-XG ontology focuses on modelling and describing sensor devices; however what a sensor measures (i.e. feature of interest) and also spatial and temporal attributes (i.e. time and location) are not in the scope of this ontology. Another challenge is that the observation and measurement data is assumed to be related to sensor devices that they are obtained from. This means the attributes such as quality of information and accuracy and precision should be traced back to the sensing device. Considering the fact that the sensors could be relatively short-lived components and/or their environmental attribute and location could change over time, this will introduce a challenge in capturing the quality of information related data and providing self-sufficient observation and measurement data when the data is processed and utilised in a global scale and outside of the local networks. Associating the sensor descriptions and also observation and measurement data to the domain knowledge and features of interest is also an important task which has not been covered in SSN-XG activities. Relating sensor data to domain knowledge will make this information widely available for different applications, front-end services and data consumers in a global scale.

3. State of the Art on Communication Protocols

This report contains the state of the art in communication protocols for the Internet of Things. Our emphasis here has been on protocol elements and solutions that can be useful for the work to be carried out within the WP3 of the IoT-A project. In addition to a throughout review of routing and communication paradigms, particular emphasis was given to the review of the work carried out within past as well as running projects, to see whether some existing technology, recently developed, can be useful as a starting point for the work to be carried out in IoT-A.

The approach that has been adopted for this state of the art was that of splitting the review in terms of: 1) protocols, 2) security for networking protocols, 3) existing projects and 4) relevant standardization activities.

As it will be understood by the material in this report, there are many means to communicate in the Internet of Things domain. However, these all seem to be rather ad hoc and interrelated with one another; in other words, the use of a particular solution seem to exclude the concurrent use of a competing one. Also, solutions at different levels of the protocol stack do not always necessarily interact. The aim of IoT-A is that of providing a reference architectural model that will bridge this gap.

In this section we review communication protocols for embedded and communicating objects focusing first on protocols operating across multiple layers. After that, we review protocols operating over a single layer and then specific IP-based solutions. Finally, we thoroughly examine security threats.

3.1 Communication protocols

3.1.1 Protocols operating across multiple layers

3.1.1.1 Layer 4 + Layer 3 – SCTP

Stream Control Transmission Protocol (SCTP) [160] is an IETF proposed standard protocol for the transport layer. It is designed to eventually replace TCP and perhaps also UDP. Like TCP, SCTP is reliable but offers new features such as multi-streaming and multi-homing. In particular, the multi-homing feature of SCTP enables it to be used for mobility support, without any special router agents in the network. Other features included in SCTP are error-free and non-duplicated data transfer, network-level fault tolerance through supporting of multi-homing, and resistance to flooding or masquerade attacks.

As mentioned earlier, the multi-homing ability enables SCTP to support mobility. A host is called multi-homed if it has multiple network layer addresses, or, more commonly, multiple IP addresses. A transport protocol supports multi-homing if the endpoint can have more than one address per transport connection, as is the case with SCTP. The mobility comes here from the ability to change the endpoints (the locators, that is IP addresses) while keeping the end-to-end connection (bound to an identifier) intact.

The problem in SCTP is to perform these address reconfigurations dynamically. The solution is to use the Dynamic Address Reconfiguration (ADDIP) [162] extension for SCTP, which enables SCTP to add, delete, and change the IP addresses during an active connection. SCTP with the ADDIP extension is called mobile SCTP (mSCTP) [163]; it provides a seamless handover capability for mobile hosts that are roaming between IP networks.

An SCTP packet is composed of a 12-byte common header and chunks. In the header, a 32-bit checksum is used to detect transmission errors. SCTP packets with an invalid checksum are silently discarded. A randomly created 32-bit verification tag allows a receiver to verify that the SCTP packet belongs to the current association and not to an old one. The chunks, on the other hand, may contain either control information or user data. Chunks have variable length and there are currently 13 types of them in standard use.

The association establishment in SCTP uses a four-way handshake. The passive side is called a server and the other is a client. The handshake procedure is as follows: first, the server receives an INIT chunk. Using local data, the server generates a secure hash of these values and a secret key. These values along with a Message Authentication Code (MAC) are put into a COOKIE, and returned in an INIT-ACK chunk. The client, using the received COOKIE, assembles a COOKIE-ECHO chunk and returns it to the server. Finally, the server verifies with the MAC, that the COOKIE is the same as it sent, and replies with a COOKIE-ACK chunk. Now the association is established. When one of the communicating parties wants to end the association, it can be done in two ways: either by graceful shutdown, ensuring that no data is lost, or hard termination (abort), not taking care of the peer. Unlike TCP, when either endpoint performs a shutdown, both endpoints stop accepting data.

During association startup, a list of transport addresses (i.e. IP address-port -pairs) is provided between the communicating entities. These addresses are used as the endpoints of different streams. SCTP regards each IP address of its peer as one "transmission path" towards this endpoint. The association spans transfers over all of the possible source/destination combinations, although one of the addresses is selected as initial primary path, and may be changed later if needed. The ADDIP extension used in mSCTP aids in this dynamic address reconfiguration. mSCTP-based soft handover is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: mSCTP soft handover.

Figure 4 represents the following scenario: the mobile node (MN) initiates an SCTP association with the corresponding node (CN). The resulting association consists of IP address 2 for MN and IP address 1 for CN (the primary path). After a while, MN decides to move from network A to network B.

Step 1: Obtaining an IP address for new location. As MN is moving towards network B, at some point it reaches the overlapping region (shaded on Figure 4). Then MN obtains the new IP address 3 from the Access router B with the help of DHCP or IPv6 address auto-configuration.

Step 2: Adding the new IP address to the SCTP association. MN informs CN of the new address by sending an Address Configuration Change (ASCONF) chunk. As a reply the ASCONF-ACK is sent.

Step 3: Changing the primary IP address. While MN further continues to move towards Access router B, it needs to set the new address as its primary address. The changing of addresses is done according to specific rules, for example as soon as a new IP address is detected. However, the configuration of this change triggering rule is a challenging issue for mSCTP.

Step 4: Deleting the old IP address. As MN has moved to network B, the old IP address becomes inactive, and it is deleted from the address list. The knowledge from underlying layers can be used to determine when the address becomes inactive.

These procedural steps will be repeated each time MN moves into a new subnet region.

3.1.1.2 Layer 3.5 + Layer 3 - HIP

The Host Identity Protocol (HIP) [160] is a solution that locates the mobility between the network and transport layers.

HIP introduces a new Host Identity layer (layer 3.5) between the IP layer (layer 3) and the upper layers. The reason for this is to avoid the situation where binding sockets to IP addresses forces the address into a dual role of endpoint and forwarding identifier. In HIP, upper layer sockets are bound to Host Identities (HI, identifiers) instead of IP addresses. In addition, the binding of these host identities to IP addresses (the locators) is done dynamically. The purpose of HI is to support trust between systems, enhance mobility, and greatly reduce the Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks.

A great advantage in this mobility solution is that the hosts can easily have both IPv4 and IPv6 addresses.

Furthermore, there is no need to change the current routing methods. Multi-homing, NAT-traversal, anonymity, and avoiding man-in-the-middle attacks are other features the HIP has to offer.

In HIP, the hosts are identified with public keys, not IP addresses. A typical host identity is a public cryptographic key of an asymmetric key-pair. Each host will have at least one HI that can either be public or anonymous. The HIs can be different in sizes depending on the used public key method.

Therefore, the HI is represented via its 128-bit hash, called Host Identity Tag (HIT), or via a 32-bit Local Scope Identity (LSI). The HIT identifies the public key that can validate the packet authentication, and HITs should be unique in the whole IP universe. They are stored in some public address directory (e.g. DNS) with the exception of anonymous identities.

The fact that the identifier is generated by the node using a public/private key pair, whose private part is not disclosed to any other node, guarantees that the legitimate node will be the only one able to claim ownership of its HI, provided that a collision with another HI does not happen. Proving HI ownership relies on the provision of the corresponding public key, and the proof of possession of the associated private key, through signature or encryption operation.

LSIs are 32-bit localized representations of a HI. Collisions between different LSIs may easily occur, and therefore they should only be used in local scope according to local policies. The main reason for LSIs is to make the use of HIP possible with existing protocols such as IPv4. The LSI's advantage over HIT is its size; on the other hand, the LSI's disadvantage is its local scope.

One of HIP's features is authentication during connection establishment. To achieve this, the transport layer packet (e.g. TCP) must be enclosed with a HIP header, which contains the HIT. Figure 2.4 illustrates the corresponding packet format. Note that for simplicity reason, all non-relevant extension headers are omitted from this figure.

Figure 5: HIP packet structure.

While the HIP header has to be present in every datagram during the connection establishment, the HIP payload can be compressed into an ESP payload (in IPv6) once the connection is established (see Figure 5). Thus, HIP packets are only needed to establish an authenticated connection.

As mentioned above, the HIP protocol is used to authenticate the connection. In addition to authentication, the procedure establishes Security Associations for a secure connection with IPsec ESP. The HIP-protocol uses a four-way handshake with Diffie-Hellman key exchange; hence it is able to bootstrap IPsec security association without relying on the IKE protocol. The entity that wants to establish a connection is referred to as initiator and the other party as responder. Before the actual exchange takes place, the initiator has fetched the responders IP address, HI, and HIT from an address directory (e.g. DNS).

Figure 6 illustrates the exchange, and the four packets it relies on are explained below.

Figure 6: HIP connection establishment.

I1 packet is sent by the initiator to see if the responder "speaks HIP". The packet contains the HITs of the both parties.

R1 packet is sent back as a reply by the responder. As the responder cannot yet trust the initiator, it initiates a three-way cookie exchange. Packet R1 holds the responders public Diffie-Hellman key, HI,

and information about the supported ESP modes as well as a challenge. The impact of a DoS attack is minimized as the responder is the one giving the challenge.

I2 packet contains the initiators public Diffie-Hellman key and a computed response to the challenge. The computation makes the DoS attack unprofitable for the initiator. The ESP options are also sent with the packet.

R2 packet completes the handshake. The responder sends it if the initiators response to the challenge was correct. After the sending of the R2 packet, the ESP encrypted datagrams (see Figure 2.4) can be used to secure the whole connection.

One of the main goals of HIP is to make mobility transparent to the applications.

During the secured connection, mobility in HIP is quite straightforward. As HIs are used to identify the mobile node instead of IP addresses, the location of the node is not bound to the identifier. Therefore only a simple signaling protocol (the HIP protocol discussed above) is needed to take care of the dynamic binding between the node's IP address and HI.

When one of the communicating peers changes location, it simply sends a HIP readdress (REA) packet through the secured ESP channel. The SAs are bound to the HITs and not to addresses, and thus the connection continues uninterrupted.

However, if the responder changes location before the connection has been properly established or if both peers change location at the same time (the double jump problem), a rendezvous server is needed. It is a packet forwarding agent which simply temporarily forwards the initial HIP packet to the responder. All further packets are handled normally between the initiator and responder.

3.1.2 Single layer protocols

Communication-enabled objects have seen to employ different physical communication interfaces that better suite target applications. For example tags used for clothes identification employ wireless RFID physical interfaces with wireless link coverage of few meters, payment devices for toll posts and e-banking employ some RFID physical interfaces but with a link coverage of some centimetres, while appliance communication devices are more bulky, thus employing larger range interfaces, like power line or wireless ZigBee.

The use of specific physical interface implies the protocols employed up to a certain layer of the OSI model. As protocols up to the link layer of the OSI model are tightly related to the hardware of the system, they are addressed together with other hardware-related aspects in section "Link Layer (wp5)". This section addresses protocols from the network and transport layer and upwards.

As most communication-enabled objects are either very small in size and lightweight (applications for daily life-readers, tags, etc) or are very low cost so that they are incorporated in consumer products (e.g. super market tags and readers, toll posts, Bluetooth handsets, home appliances, etc), where price always plays important role, in their majority they do not use protocols of layers higher than the network-level layer. The table below summarizes the protocols exploited today by most communication-enabled objects.

Physical communication interface type	Communication type	Protocols	OSI layer
802.15.X Series (ZigBee, Bluetooth, RFID, etc)	Wireless	NWK/APS/API defined by each standardisation body (all non-IP)	Network/Transport/upper
WiFi	Wireless	IP/TCP-UDP	Network/Transport/upper
UWB	Wireless	Baseband/LinkManager/L2CAP (non-IP)	Network/Transport/upper
Serial	Fixed	Up to data link	Data link
USB	Fixed, wireless	Up to data link	Data link
Sensor network busses (e.g. CAN, Profibus, etc)	Fixed	Up to data link	Data link
DeviceNet	Fixed	DeviceNet network and transport	Network/Transport/upper
ControlNet	Fixed	ControlNet network and transport	Network/Transport/upper
EtherNet/IP	Fixed	IP/TCP-UDP	Network/Transport/upper
Power line (KNX, LonWorks)	Fixed	Network/transport layers according to KNX and LonWorks specifications	Network layer/Transport

Table 1: Protocols of popular physical communication interfaces exploited by communication-enabled objects

As can be seen in the table, most of the protocols and technologies utilized by communication-enabled objects define their own custom network, transport and even application layer protocols, tailored to the particular requirements of each technology. Additionally, there are technologies that address only the lower segments of the OSI protocol stack, mainly the physical and data link layers. Specifically, the 802.15.x series of specifications addressing the area of Wireless Personal Area Networking, define their own network, transport and application layers protocols and do not adopt IP and TCP/UDP for the network and transport layers respectively. Similarly, the DeviceNet and ControlNet technologies, managed by the Open DeviceNet Vendors Association [171] and used in industrial networks, provide their own custom network and transport layer mechanisms.

As mentioned earlier, there are widely deployed technologies that address only the lower layers of the OSI model, such as the serial and USB busses used to connect end devices to host computers, and sensor network busses, such as the Controller Area Network bus and the Profibus used to enable the direct communication of devices and microcontrollers without the need for an intermediate host system. Target application areas for the CAN bus [172] include, but are not limited to, collection of measurements from sensors present in household appliances and in-vehicle networks for engine management and control of comfort devices. Profibus [173] is an industrial computer networking protocol used for real-time distributed control in automation. These kinds of technologies fall outside the scope of WP3, as they do not address networking and transport layers of the protocol stack.

Finally, there are technologies and standards that have either based their network and transport layer functionality on the widely used IP, TCP, UDP protocols, or defined particular compatibility modes with the aforementioned protocols in order to enable their use over the public Internet, which is based on IP/TCP-UDP. The WiFi specification falls under the first category, utilizing IP in the network layer and TCP/UDP in the transport layer. Similarly, the EtherNet/IP technology [175], used as the networking technology in automated manufacturing, brings the widely used Ethernet/IP/TCP-UDP suite into industrial automation. The KNX [176] and Lonworks [177] standards, which are powerline communication specifications widely used in building automation, fall under the second category, as they define modes of operation that allow for interworking with the public Internet; mainly the encapsulation of KNX/Lonworks frames into IP frames. The major usage of this kind of frame tunneling is for enabling the communication of KNX/Lonworks subnets with remote nodes over the IP-based network for configuration/management purposes.

Access of applications on communication-enabled objects is implemented by means of employing specific interworking points realised with standard communication platforms such a home gateways, mobile phones or application specific IP-enabled points of access (e.g. object readers).

Figure 7: Traffic interworking between communication-enabled objects and the IP network

Concerning enhancement of objects communication capabilities a strong trend has been remarked today towards embedding subsets of the IP protocol. So far, several projects have been done about embedding TCP/IP stacks, resulting in prototypes, such as TinyTCP [178], lwIP [179] and uIP [180]. All of them implement a subset of TCP/IP RFCs, but they are able to communicate with usual IP nodes, while they provide a socket-like interface for embedded applications. For example uIP is a

simple event-driven TCP/IP stack based on protothreads, which only requires a few kilo-bytes of RAM. These IP-based protocol capabilities are detailed in the following section.

3.1.3 IP networking technologies

3.1.3.1 Layer 3 - Mobile IP / NEMO

3.1.3.1.1 Mobile IP overview

The Mobile IP protocol is an IETF proposed standard that provides a network layer solution to node mobility across IPv4 (Mobile IPv4, [164]) and IPv6 (Mobile IPv6, [165]) networks.

Mobile IP allows a node to change its point of attachment to the Internet without needing to change its IP address. This is not simply a configuration simplification, but can facilitate continuous application-level connectivity as the node moves from point to point.

The solution developed by the IETF involves protocol extensions whereby packets targeted to a mobile host are sent to its home network (as if the host were not mobile) and passed to a static (non-mobile) node called the mobile host's home agent. The mobile host registers its real location with the home agent, which is responsible for forwarding the packets to the host.

If the mobile host is at home (attached to its home network, at its so-called home address), forwarding is just plain old IP forwarding, but if the host is moving, packets must be tunnelled across the Internet to the host's care-of address, which is the host's actual point of attachment to the network. At the care-of address (the end of the tunnel) the packets are de-tunnelled and read by the mobile host.

Note that this tunnelling process is only required in one direction. Packets sent by the mobile host may be routed through the network using the standard IP procedures (that is, with the care-of address as source address). Yet, it is also possible to route mobile host's outgoing packets through the home agent (reverse tunnelling).

It is worth observing that although mobile IP can be used to address any IP mobility issue, its use within wireless LANs and mobile phone networks might be better served by link-layer (i.e., sub-IP) procedures such as link-layer handoff. These processes are typically built into the link-layer mechanisms and involve less overhead than Mobile IP. Such processes do, however, require that the mobile host remains logically connected within the IP subnet to which its address belongs – it becomes the responsibility of the link layer to maintain connections or virtual connections into that subnet.

3.1.3.1.2 Mobile IP mobility support

There are many potentially unfamiliar terms and acronyms in the mobile world, used in Requests for Comments, Internet Drafts, technical papers, and throughout this project. Mostly taken from [164], the following table explains common Mobile IP terms.

Mobile Node (MN)	A host or router that changes its point of attachment. It keeps its home IP address regardless of the change of location.
Correspondent Node (CN)	Either a fixed or mobile host which is communicating with the MN
Home Address (HoA)	Permanent IP address of the mobile node, to which it is directly reachable when at home, and reachable through the home agent when roaming.
Care-of Address (CoA)	Topologically valid IP Address that represents the actual location of the mobile node, when in a visited network.
IP Tunnel	Virtual channel used to interconnect two networks, and relying on IP encapsulation to deliver packets between them.
Home agent (HA)	A router on a mobile node's home network. It maintains mapping between the mobile node's home address and care-of address, and delivers packets destined to the HoA through a tunnel to the MN's CoA when the MN is roaming.
Mobility Binding	(HoA, CoA) bundle, which is sent by the MN to the Home Agent in a Registration Request (Mobile IPv4) or a Binding Update (Mobile IPv6) message.
Gratuitous ARP	Sent by a Mobile IPv4 HA to update Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) tables for all connected hosts, in order to receive packets sent to the MN's HoA on behalf of MN.

Table 2: Mobile IP terminology.

Each Mobile Node (MN) is identified by its Home Address (HoA, the identifier). The address may be statically fixed, or dynamically acquired from the Home Agent (HA), which is a router supporting mobility services in the nodes home network. Likewise, the home agent address may be statically configured on the MN, or this latter may use the Dynamic Home Agent Address Discovery (DHAAD) protocol if network policy allows it.

If MN operates in its home network, conventional mechanisms are used to route packets addressed to it. When it moves to another network, though, it will acquire a new address called a Care-of Address (CoA, the locator) through either stateless or stateful address configuration.

At this point, it has to be noted that different types of care-of addresses may exist. Mobile IPv6 only considers one care-of address type, which is a care-of address actually configured on the MN itself (assigned to one of MN's interfaces). Yet Mobile IPv4 considers both the "collocated care-of address" (similar to Mobile IPv6) and another type ("foreign agent care-of address"), corresponding to a scenario where the CoA is not assigned to the MN's but is maintained at another node than the MN itself: the so-called Foreign Agent, located in the visited network. Mandating that such a mobility-managing entity be located in every location the MN would possibly roam into is however highly unrealistic. Hence the present work restricts to Mobile IPv4 collocated care-of addresses (and the similarly behaving Mobile IPv6 care-of addresses) and ignores foreign agent –based infrastructures.

Having acquired a care-of address in a visited location, the mobile node informs the home agent of this novel care-of address. The association between MN's home address and care-of address is known as a "binding" for the node. The registration message is called a Registration Request (RegReq) in Mobile IPv4 and a Binding Update (BU) in Mobile IPv6. Mobile IP enables nodes to cache these address bindings into HA's binding cache. Using this information, the home agent forwards any packets addressed to MN towards the new location.

Any node communicating with MN is known as a corresponding node (CN). CN may itself be a stationary or a mobile node. In a basic situation, all traffic from CN to MN is tunnelled through the home agent and traffic from MN to CN is sent in a direct way. In a reverse-tunnelling situation, all bidirectional traffic exchanged between CN and MN passes through the home agent.

When a CN wants to send messages to the MN, it sends IP packets to the MN's home address. These packets will be directed to the home network by normal routing. Since the HA knows that the MN is not in this network, the HA will intercept these packets, using the features of Gratuitous ARP and Proxy ARP. The updated ARP table indicates that the Layer 2 address of MN's HoA is the Layer 2 address of HA, so IP packets sent to the MN will be received at the HA. After that, the HA uses a tunnel (it encapsulates the original packets inside a new IP packet) to forward the packets to the CoA. The source IP address of the encapsulating IP header is the HA address, and its destination IP address is the CoA.

Figure 0.8 illustrates this situation:

Figure 0.8: MN↔CN packet routing with Mobile IP.

Note that Figure 0.8 represents the situation where all exchanged traffic between MN and CN goes through HA; this mode of communication is known as bidirectional or reverse tunnelling [166]. The nice thing about this mode is that the CN does not require to support Mobile IP at all: otherwise, the CN would have to accept packets coming from MN's CoA as valid MN-originating packets, which is not straightforward (packets would have to be sent to MN's HoA and received from MN's CoA).

In order to avoid "triangular routing", in which all traffic between MN and CN has to go through the home agent, MIPv6 also features a "Correspondent Registration" procedure, allowing an MN to register its HoA/CoA binding to a Correspondent Node (CN). This procedure provides "route optimization" by enabling direct routing of IPv6 traffic from the CN to the MN's CoA (i.e. bypassing

routing via the HA). This correspondent registration procedure relies on an exchange of 6 messages. The 4 first ones (HoTi, CoTi, HoT, CoT) form the so-called “return routability” procedure allowing 1) CN to verify MN’s ownership of its Home and Care-Of addresses, and 2) dynamic establishment of a binding key shared by MN and CN and used to secure the subsequent 2 messages of the “correspondent registration” procedure which are the BU and BAck messages. The return routability procedures work as follows: with HoTi and CoTi messages, the MN respectively claims ownership of its home address and care-of address to the CN. The CN then challenges these claims by sending HoT and CoT messages respectively to the claimed home address and care-of address. Actually, the CN sends partial cryptographic material to the MN’s claimed home address and care-of address, and will subsequently accept MIPv6 messages from the MN only if signed with the complete cryptographic material. This implicitly assures that the MN has received both the HoT and the CoT messages, hence that it “owns” both its claimed home address and its claimed care-of address. Of course, this mechanism is not perfect as any node on the path from CN to MN’s HoA and from CN to MN’CoA can intercept both the HoT and the CoT. Hence, it is rather a routability test rather than a true proof of ownership of both HoA and CoA.

3.1.3.1.3 NEMO

Using Mobile IP, it is possible to move a single IP device from point to point on the Internet without losing higher level connections. However, with the proliferation of IP and the desire to always remain connected to the Internet, we are seeing entire networks of IP devices moving together from one place to another. It is possible to enable mobility for all of these devices using standard Mobile IP; however, this would require all devices to be capable of Mobile IP and generate excess overhead as every device would have to perform Mobile IP functions.

Another solution to the problem is Network Mobility (NEMO). NEMO works by moving the mobility functionality from Mobile IP mobile nodes to a moving network’s router. The router is able to change its attachment point to the Internet in a manner that is transparent to attached nodes.

NEMO is an extension of Mobile IP that enables an entire network to change its attachment point to the Internet. Like its host counterpart, NEMO exists under both an IPv4 [167] and an IPv6 [168] form. Under NEMO, a Mobile Router (MR) takes over the role of the MN in performing mobility functions. Nodes that are attached to a MR, Mobile Network Nodes (MNNs), are not aware of the network’s mobility and do not perform any mobility functions. MRs also send binding updates to their HAs. However, binding updates from MRs also contain the mobile network’s network prefix. HAs will bind an entire network prefix to the MR’s CoA and forward all packets for that network prefix to the MR.

Figure 0.9 demonstrates the path of packets using NEMO. IP packets from a correspondent node (CN) that are destined to a node (MNN) on a moving network served by a mobile router (MR) are delivered via standard routing on the Internet to the HA of that MR. The HA tunnels the packets to the MR for delivery to the MNN. Reverse packets take the same path in the opposite direction; the MNN sends packets to the CN and MR tunnels these to the home agent, which eventually sends them out to the CN via standard routing on the Internet.

Figure 0.9: MNN↔CN packet routing with NEMO.

3.1.3.2 Layer 3 – SHIM6

SHIM6 [169] allows two communicating nodes to overcome connection loss problems that may arise if one node changes its IP address (locator) during an established communication. In a nutshell, SHIM6 can be seen as a server-less Mobile IPv6 protocol. The underlying concept of SHIM6 is the following: at one point in an ongoing communication between two nodes (typically, when a sufficiently large number of packets have been exchanged), a shim context is established between the two nodes. This establishment allows both nodes to learn a list of locators for each other.

These locators are bound to the shim context, which is defined as the association between Upper Layer Identifiers (ULIDs) of both nodes and a local context tag.

Upon session disruption, alternative locator pairs are tried in order to resume the communication. At this point, the shim6 extension is used to add the context information to the packets, so that they can be mapped to the initial flow. It is up to the shim layer to determine which locator pair(s) can be used to carry the communication, as well as when to drop a used pair to fall back to another.

The SHIM6 specification states that the locator has to be validated according to two aspects. On one hand, a node wanting to bind a locator to a ULID must prove that it is the same node as the one owning this ULID (ownership test, typically based on hash-based addresses (HBAs) or cryptographically generated addresses (CGAs) – for example, have the private key associated to a ULID sign a claimed locator). On the other hand, it has to make the proof that it is able to actually receive packets sent to that locator (routability test – for example return the content of a packet sent towards the locator). In addition, it is highly recommended that a node receiving locator information perform a locator ownership test, so as to ensure that a node claiming ownership actually owns it (this ownership proof could typically be based on the use of HBA/CGA mechanisms to generate the locator).

3.1.3.3 Summary of Identifier-Locator split solutions

		SCTP	HIP	MIP	SHIM6
	Identifier	SCTP flow identifier	Host Identity (= 128-bit hash of a public key)	Home Address (IP address)	Upper Layer Identifier
	Locator	IP address	IP address	Care-of Address (IP address)	IP address
	Impact of disconnections	SCTP must have been configured to rely on another IP address pair (dynamic address reconfiguration) so that the flow continues uninterrupted	A new locator information must have been sent so that the session continues uninterrupted	MIP must have been configured to use another care-of address (MIP registration) so that the session continues uninterrupted	Disconnection triggers the use, by the SHIM6 layer, of another address pair to maintain the connection.
Security Systems	Identifier ownership	Not provided	Proof of possession of the private key whose corresponding public key, hashed, is the HI itself	Return routability procedure (routability test: only ensures that the node is on the path to home address)	Proof of possession of the private key whose corresponding public key, hashed, is the ULID itself
	Locator ownership	Not provided	Not provided	Return routability procedure (routability test: only ensures that the node is on the path to care-of address)	Recommended: locator IP address should be bound to a public/private key pair
	Identifier-Locator binding	Shared secret used to protect the association startup / address configuration	New locator information is carried within an IPsec ESP tunnel, bound to	Return routability procedure	Locator update is secured in accordance with the mechanism used to generated

	change messages	the identifier		the identifier (HBA/CGA)
Identifier Update	Requires that a new SCTP transport session be established	Generation of a novel public/private key pair and update of the corresponding HI on an address directory	Dynamic home address assignment	Upper layer identifier is bound to an applicative session and may change, if the application supports it
Locator Update	Address configuration change exchange	HIP readdress	Mobile IP registration	

3.2 Public project solutions

3.2.1 AIM

The main objective of the AIM (Assessment, Intervention, Moving on) project [201] has been to foster a harmonized technology for managing in real time the energy consumption of appliances at home, interworking this information to communication devices over the home network and vitalizing it with the final aim of making it available to users through home communication networks in the form of standalone or network operator services.

Behind this concept, the main challenge of AIM is to provide a generalized method for managing the energy consumption of household appliances both in active and stand-by states.

Figure 10: AIM conceptual architecture

Three household appliance types have been addressed concerning AIM solution application:

- white goods (refrigerators, kitchens, washing machines, driers)
- communication devices (cordless phones and gateways for domestic use)
- A/V (audiovisual) equipment (TV Sets and Set-top-boxes).

The figure below illustrates a detailed diagram of the overall AIM architecture [202]. Inter-working with the home network has been done with the introduction of a dedicated functional entity, called Energy Management Device (EMD), that implements, in a generic way and for all the appliance types, **monitoring and control of energy consumption through appliance programs control**.

Figure 11: AIM general concept and architecture

EMDs utilise an independent, common for all appliances, architecture that exploits typical home communication infrastructure, such as power line, ZigBee and WiFi, for connecting the residential gateway. The EMD conveys control and monitoring logic for both active and stand-by appliances. EMD functions become integrated within the home network by means of utilizing a residential gateway that wraps the EMD functions with energy control services for home users (Figure 12).

At protocol level, EMD employs a slim version of the IPv4 protocol that implements only few IP protocol operations needed for the EMD communication with the gateway, such as fixed IP address (user-defined), few frame formats for particular control messages accommodation (no SNMP/DHCP support). Thanks to this IP version, the EMD can get controlled by the users via IP through industry-standard protocol and network application software technologies, like OSGi, UPnP and HTTP. Particularly the use of the HTTP protocol allows implementation of Web Server functionality that run locally on the EMDs and will allow EMD easy configuration. As is depicted in Figure 12, EMDs are accessible either locally, through the residential gateway or via external operator networks.

Figure 12: Integration of EMD with the home network

In the indoor communication scenario, EMD offers power management services to applications hosted on the residential gateway (flow 1) or on PC terminals through the residential gateway (flow 2) or directly (flow 3) via short range wireless interfaces or the GPRS network.

In the outdoor communication scenario, EMD offers its services to users residing in public networks, through operator services running either in cooperation with the residential gateway (flow 1) or in standalone (flow 2).

Realisation of power management applications is possible through the involvement of the “device virtualisation environment” (Figure 13). With this environment, users may access and orchestrate the power management capabilities of home environment by means of using semantics representing, on one hand the possible administration functions (e.g. monitor, control, etc), and on the other hand the addressed household appliances types. The “device virtualization environment” is accessible on the residential gateway and its functions are linked to properties such as service personalisation, user identification and privileged access, all offered by the ESTIA residential gateway architecture.

Figure 13: Device Virtualisation logic architecture

AIM has implemented three use-cases:

- **Use-case for residential users (intelligent service for autonomous energy consumption management):** In this use-case the project has studied and designed an intelligent technological solution for profiling user habits by collecting information by sensors (presence) and by home devices (typical usage). Using this information the home network is able to administrate stand-by devices autonomously and also configure the power consumption of appliances to levels that meet user usability criteria. Overall, the system is based on a wireless sensor network, which has been integrated with the residential gateway and be assisted by a user profiles database, where user activity data, concerning appliances usage are collected and administrated upon creating individual profiles. Using these individual profiles, a number of usage scenarios were created for appliance power consumption management.
- **Use-case for power distribution network operators (metering service for energy planning):** In this use-case, the project has proven the ability of the architecture to perform real time acquisition of power consumption measurements to be massively used for yielding energy utilization statistics and thus be used for power distribution network operators to better plan energy generation and avoid unnecessary resources dissipation.
- **Use-case for legacy services operators (remote monitoring and management):** In this use-case, the project has proven the capability of the architecture to allow the users monitor and control the power consumption of their homes, remotely, while moving outdoors. This type of use-case has be delivered in a set of operator services optimized for mobile phones, through which the user is able to monitor in real time the power

consumption at home and do intelligent configurations, such as assignment of alerts in the event of excess of user configurable values, etc.

3.2.2 CASAGRAS

The first CASAGRAS (Coordination and Support Action (CSA) for Global RFID-related Activities and Standardisation) ended on the 30th June 2009 after 18 months⁹. Its goal was “[...] to consider the international dimensions concerning regulations, standardisation and other requirements for realising the concept known as the Internet of Things, and the role within it of radio frequency identification (RFID)”. In the CASAGRAS final report [203] a thorough state of the art on data collection architecture, technologies, standards, identification solutions and applications is provided. However, this analysis is outdated. From the point of view of protocols, the Final Report provides a complete list (at least at the time of publication) of RFID and WSN protocols.

CASAGRAS2¹⁰ started in June 2010 and will end June 2012. The consortium consists of partners from Europe, the USA, China, Brasil, Japan and Korea. Stated goal is “[...] to address the key international issues that are important in providing the foundations and co-operation necessary for realising the Internet of Things as a global initiative.” The aforementioned key issues are IoT Governance, IoT Identification coding Standards and Regulations, Policy & Intellectual Property, IoT Architecture, Services & Applications, Awareness / Education / Training. CASAGRAS2 aims to collect, review and analyse these issues. The analysis will be carried out at global level, with attention to specific local concerns, context and requirements.

As a supporting action, the project’s deliverables are not technical but geared towards the definition of the roadmap for research and development, the organization of consensus-building events. It was (and is) out of the scope of CASAGRAS projects to make progress beyond the state of the art in the field of networking protocols.

3.2.3 eSENSE

The main contributions of the European project eSENSE¹¹ consisted of providing some of the key enabling technologies for Ambient Intelligent Systems. Specifically, the intent has been that of capturing ambient intelligence through low power, distributed and highly efficient wireless sensor networks (WSNs).

Three applications scenarios were proposed and used within the project. These are: 1) Body Sensor Networks (BSN), 2) Object Sensor Networks (OSN) and 3) Environmental Sensor Networks.

The work that is most relevant to IoT-A was carried out within work package 3, whose goal was that of designing energy efficient physical layer technologies and combine them with cross-layer optimised protocols so as to get a cross-layer optimised protocol stack, with solutions from the physical to the transport layer. WP3 partners have first developed methodologies for optimising existing physical layers for their use within wireless sensor networks. Advanced RF sensing techniques have been designed to support context and situation awareness, e.g., to estimate nodes relative distance between pairs of wireless sensors and to monitor and measure the quality of their radio links. Thus, partners have proposed energy efficient routing schemes designed according to cross-layer paradigms. Roughly speaking, communication protocols have been designed to provide transfer of data in networks spanning across multiple hops particularly focusing on the transfer of sensor readings from distributed sensor nodes to the data collection point (the sink) and the transmission of commands from the sink to the sensor nodes. This led to the design of integrated channel access and routing protocols that can auto-adapt their behaviour according to the node density. Density estimation algorithms are executed in the background and concurrently with MAC actions. These are thus exploited within data forwarding schemes to tune the transmissions rate at the MAC layer. Moreover, physical layer aspects, such as the quality of the links, were accounted for in the selection of the next hop toward the sink. This was achieved through the online calculation of quality metrics for the radio links that can also be exploited in combination with other relevant aspects such as, e.g., the residual energy of the nodes and the state of their transmission queues.

No framework was provided by eSENSE for the connection of wireless sensor nodes to the IP world, but the protocols designed within the project were rather based on customised hardware and software

⁹ see, <http://www.rfidglobal.eu/>

¹⁰ see, <http://iot-casagras.org>

¹¹ <http://www.ist-esense.org>, funded under the FP6 program, project no. IST-4-027227-IP

platforms. As such, eSENSE dealt with WSN islands that were isolated and thought of for dedicated applications.

3.2.4 SENSEI

The SENSEI Project¹² is an Integrated Project in the EU's Seventh Framework. SENSEI (Contract no. 215923) started on 1st January 2008, and will be running until the end of 2010. SENSEI includes 19 partners from 11 European countries.

The main objective of the project is revolved around the integration of wireless sensor and actuator networks (WS&ANs) into the Internet. Toward this end, SENSEI provides an architectural framework to represent and manage WS&ANs in a uniform manner, while adding enhanced features and providing plug & play IP connectivity for smart sensor objects. The architectural framework is based on modern Web-based technology, supporting a Representational State Transfer (REST) approach and enabling the exchange of data and commands to and from WS&ANs using XML. Among the four main project objectives, SENSEI aimed at designing efficient WS&AN solutions. These consist of a set of cross-optimized and energy aware protocol stacks, including IEEE 802.15.4-compliant advanced radio transceivers (targeting energy consumption of 5nJ/bit).

The protocol design work were carried out by Work Package 4, and has led to the definition of protocols covering the following areas:

- **Connectivity:** specialized routing protocols have been designed and implemented to provide communication services.
- **Management:** a very efficient and secure network reprogramming protocol was designed. This solution allows the wireless reprogramming of sensor islands spanning over multiple hops. In addition, advanced solutions have been proposed to check the status of sensor nodes, schedule/re-schedule events, recover from failures, etc.
- **Middleware:** a number of advanced solutions have been proposed to process the data gathered from WS&AN islands.
- **Security:** secure data aggregation and reprogramming services are provided.

At a higher level of detail, in what follows we describe the main solutions provided by WP4:

Localization: the localization module allows self-calibrating localization of sensor nodes through the measurement of the Received Signal Strength (RSS), which is acquired from the radio module (IEEE 802.15.4). It can dynamically adapt to varying propagation conditions by calibrating nuisance parameters (path-loss exponent and reference RSS) from localization measurements, instead of a pre-calibration phase, which is required by most other RSS-based methods.

Secure reprogramming of wireless sensor nodes (SCU): Secure Code Update (SCU) was designed and implemented to wirelessly reprogram all nodes of a (possibly multihop) wireless sensor and actuator network. The protocol self-adapts its code dissemination procedure to the node density, is robust against link failures and provides the following security features: code authentication (to protect the code against bogus image insertion attacks), protection against Denial of Service attacks as well as encryption of data. SCU has been implemented on TelosB nodes and integrated into the PAN European Testbed.

Secure data aggregation (FAIR): FAIR is a secure data aggregation protocol, which ensures continuity of service even in the case of attacks and hardware failures. It provides a means to securely aggregate data coming from multiple sensors so as to increase the efficiency of the data gathering. FAIR has been implemented on TelosB nodes and integrated into the PAN European Testbed.

Management framework (CHECK): CHECK is a framework for the management of WS&ANs. It is composed of three main sub-systems: 1) scheduling, 2) self-healing and 3) monitoring and reconfiguration. The overall purpose of this system is that of monitoring the status of WS&AN resources, detecting possible failures in the system and providing advanced services such as self-healing, i.e., replacing a broken resource with an alternative one, or re-scheduling events to a later time, when they will be available again. CHECK has been implemented and integrated into the PAN European Testbed.

Routing and data gathering: two protocols, namely EMR and ROME, have been proposed to provide routing functionality within WS&ANs. The former is based on a clustering approach: the network is subdivided into clusters of nodes and routing is executed through inter-cluster transmissions. The energy consumption is balanced across nodes through a careful election of cluster-heads. ROME is based on a different rationale: all nodes cover the same role and can be possibly used as relays for the data to be delivered to the sink (or gateway node), relays are elected on the fly as messages travel toward the sink. Special techniques are devised to overcome the connectivity hole issue. Both

¹² <http://www.ict-sensei.org/> - Integrating the Physical with the Digital World of the Network of the Future

protocols have been implemented on hardware and ROME has also been integrated into the PAN European Testbed.

Advanced middleware components: the most important ones are Outliers Detection and Activity Recognition. The former deals with the automated detection of “outliers”, which are data that do not respect the normal behavioural model of the physical process that is being sensed. Outliers are those data that come from hardware failures or external interference that do not represent or are not related with the physical phenomenon under observation. These should be recognized and treated differently from data that do not conform the normal behavioural model but that is due to rare events; in this case the sensors report valid measurements that are however far away from the typical statistics for the data. A second software was developed to perform activity recognition for agents or group of agents through the observation of their actions.

Titan framework: Titan (Tiny Task Network) offers distributed execution of context recognition algorithms within Wireless Sensor and Actuation Networks (WSANs), which is especially designed for Body Area Networks (BAN). Instead of transmitting all the raw sensory data to a centralized point for processing, the data is pre-processed on the nodes as far as possible. Thus, only relevant data is sent to the Resource User. Titan provides the following main features: 1) service Graph: a dataflow representation to describe context recognition algorithms as a set of connected services. 2) Mapping routines: mapping service graphs to existing services (e.g. sensors, actuators, and processing units) in the network. 3) fast network (re-configuration: Fast configuration and execution of context recognition algorithms (represented as service graphs) within the network.

Connection with IoT-A: in addition, and of higher importance for IoT-A, the work within WP5 dealt with the design of a protocol stack for TinyOS as well as Contiki operating systems for the communication with and within WS&ANs using state of the art Web-based technology. According to this protocol stack, sensor nodes communicate among themselves and with gateway nodes using compressed IPv6 packets (exploiting the IETF 6LoWPAN technology), a REST-based approach is exploited for managing resources on the sensor nodes (through an optimized set of primitives, GET/SET/POST/DELETE), which are mapped through Universal Resource Identifiers (URIs). This framework has been implemented in what has been called the “PAN European Testbed” and allows the representation of WS&AN resources in a uniform and Web-compliant manner, which makes WS&ANs easily pluggable into IP networks. Resources within WS&ANs can be accessed and interacted with through their uniform resource locators (similar to Web URLs). A dedicated SENSEI architecture has been designed and partly implemented to provide advanced IP services on top of WS&N islands.

3.3 Commercial products

3.3.1 Wireless HART and HART

The HART (Highway Addressable Remote Transducer Protocol) used in process automation exists since the late 80’s. It was designed to provide a command / response (polling) communication pattern over legacy 4-20mA analog instrumentation wiring. Later additions improve security and allow to have publish/subscribe and event notification communications. The basis of installed wired devices is estimated to 25 million and grows by 3 million per year [204].

The HART 7 specification introduced in 2007 “Wireless HART”; a good overview of the more than 20 documents of the specification can be found in [205]. The 2007 specification adds wireless mesh capabilities for HART process automation devices. As multi-vendor protocol, the specification was supported by 37 companies, among them ABB, Endress+Hauser, Emerson, Pepperl+Fuchs, Siemens. Wireless HART aims at applications in the industrial process automation domain, such as oil & gas, food & beverages and other industrial processes that do not need real time communication (latency > 100ms). Nevertheless, those applications have requirements regarding determinism, security and reliability. These properties are addressed by a central management, which addresses security by key management for the AES encryption of 802.15.4 chipsets, and which manages the network to address determinism and reliability.

The above mentioned properties are implemented by the wireless technology base, which is the TSMP protocol developed DUST Networks. It provides the foundation for the energy efficient, reliable, and deterministic network based on 802.15.4 in the 2.4 GHz band. Energy efficiency and determinism is implemented by a TDMA MAC access, i.e. scheduled communication. A channel-hopping scheme, which is tied to the TDMA schedule, improves the robustness of the communication against interference and fading. A graph routing complements the MAC access and provides alternative links on each hop of the path, which improves the reliability. Both, MAC access and routing are controlled by a central device, the Wireless HART manager.

Wireless HART provides many features that could be useful or even required in an IoT-A communication subsystem. Energy efficiency for battery operation as well as reliability and

determinism for critical applications are such features. These could be used in an extended view from the original scope of Wireless HART even to actuators in eHealth applications. The base mechanisms of the Wireless HART MAC and network layer protocol already are on the way to be standardized in IEEE (802.15.4e) and heavily influence the IETF routing protocol for 802.15.4 in the ROLL working group. The centralized network management in Wireless HART is probably most difficult to integrate in an autarkic IoT architecture.

The Wireless HART application and management protocol has grown specific for process automation applications and contradicts the service based approach of the Internet. Legacy Wireless HART installations may be accessed via a gateway from the IoT architecture.

3.3.2 Bluetooth

Bluetooth [206] is a wireless technology based on the IEEE 802.15.1 specification. It is mainly used as cable replacement for up to seven devices communicating with a single master. Main application areas are communication between phone and headset, PC and mouse/keyboard; low bandwidth data transfer / file access and game controllers which are supported by a variety of profiles. A selection of application profiles is available in almost all current mobile phones, but may differ according vendor and operator specific implementations.

Bluetooth offers in the latest Core 4.0 specification [206] two different incompatible PHY and Link Layers. The Basic Rate/Enhanced Data Rate (BR/EDR) known from Bluetooth 2.0 provides connectivity up to 3Mbps. It is also used for signalling in the Alternate MAC/Physical scheme which makes use of alternative PHY/MAC layers, such as 802.11, to enable the high speed mode of Bluetooth 3.0. Incompatible to those schemes is the Bluetooth low energy (LE) stack that offers only up to 1Mbps connectivity. Bluetooth LE improves the energy usage by optimizing the time needed for link establishment and wakeup from sleep. It also leverages the restricted number of devices in a network and optimizes broadcast.

Application interoperability in Bluetooth is obtained via the definition of profiles. All devices need to implement/provide the Generic Access Profile (GAP) which defines the basic stack and provides the foundation for discovery of devices and services. The main success of Bluetooth is given by typical cable replacement profiles, e.g. Advanced Audio Distribution Profile (A2DP) and Hands-Free Profile (HFP) for headset usage, Human Interface Device Profile (HID) for wireless keyboards and mice, Phone Book Access Profile (PBAP, PBA) for car kits, Generic Object Exchange Profile (GOEP) as basis for the exchange of images and files. For devices that are not directly connected to the internet the Personal Area Networking Profile (PAN) may provide access via other internet connected devices. Since Bluetooth itself is not an IP based protocol stack, its use in the IoT Architecture may be limited. Nevertheless, the access to mobile phones – which are certainly considered as “Thing” in the IoT – may be implemented by IP protocols carried over Bluetooth. The current trend in this area is clearly dominated by WiFi and data over cellular wireless networks. While the concept of device and service discovery is an important building block for the IoT-A, the Bluetooth approach may be far too limited for a general IoT architecture.

3.3.3 BACnet

BACnet represents a data communication protocol for Building Automation and Control Networks that has a high market share in the applications HVAC, security, fire detection, and lighting control. It was developed since 1985 by the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning (ASHRAE) and later standardized as “DIN EN ISO 16484-5” [207].

BACnet is based on a number of predefined objects and properties, which can be extended by vendor specific extensions [208]. Objects can be grouped and can reference each other. Interoperability is maintained by a set of mandatory properties, that every object needs to support. Examples for objects are Analog Input, Calendar, Event-Enrollment, and Device. The communication between the objects is done with services, - a simple example is the “Read_Property” service, which fetches a property from an object.

A special role play the discovery services, these are “Who-Is”, “I-Am”, “Who-Has”, “I-Have”. These services are used to find out which devices are in the network and what the capabilities of these devices are.

BACnet provides the ability to communicate based on MAC addressing over many physical layers, such as Ethernet, MS/TP, PTP, and LonTalk. IP networks are integrated by BACnet over IP tunnelling and BACnet/IP. For BACnet over IP special devices called BACnet-IP Protocol Packet Assembler-Disassembler (BACnet-IP PAD) encapsulate the BACnet messages and transfer them to the other subnetwork. This involves a large overhead in network planning and management. For BACnet/IP a combination of IP address and port number is used for addressing and communication. Thus, multiple BACnet IP devices can reside on the same subnetwork. Since broadcasts are – for good reason – not routed in IP networks, the required broadcast functionality is emulated by special purpose devices,

called BACnet Broadcast Management Device (BBMD). The addressing and naming is not finally solved yet, e.g. consider private networks that are commonly used in company buildings.

BACnet contains concepts that are relevant for an IoT-A: especially an object model and a discovery will be needed for the future IoT architecture. BACnet/IP reveals also very clearly the problems that occur by an incompletely defined addressing and naming scheme.

3.3.4 KNX

KNX [223] is a standardized network platform based upon more than 20 years of experience in the market, amongst others with predecessor systems to KNX: EIB, EHS and BatiBUS. With Internet technologies integration (like RSS) and CISCO joining this year the KNX association it seems clear the trend of unleashing KNX from the intranet borders towards the internet.

The KNX system offers the choice for the manufacturers to choose between several physical layers or combine them. The different media supported by KNX are

- TP1, providing a solution for twisted-pair cabling. Its main characteristics are: data and power transmission with one pair, and asynchronous character-oriented data transfer and half duplex bi-directional communication. TP1 implements a CSMA/CA collision avoidance, whereas its transmission rate is 9600 bit/s.
- PL110 enables communication over the mains supply network. Its main characteristics are: spread frequency shift keying signalling, asynchronous transmission of data packets and half duplex bi-directional communication. PL110 uses the central frequency 110kHz and has a data rate of 1200 bit/s. PL110 implements CSMA.
- RF enables communication via radio signals in the 868,3 MHz band for Short Range Devices. Its major features are Frequency Shift Keying, maximum duty cycle of 1%, Manchester data encoding.
- KNX has also provisioned for IP-enabled media such as Ethernet (IEEE 802.2), Bluetooth, WiFi/Wireless LAN (IEEE 802.11), "Firewire" (IEEE1394).

On top of the Physical Layers and their particular Data Link Layer, a Common Kernel model is shared by all devices on the KNX network. KNX includes a 7 layers OSI model-compliant communication system. Above the medium-specific Data Link Layer, a general Data Link Layer provides the medium access control and the logical link control. The Network Layer provides a segment-wise acknowledgement telegram, whereas it also controls the hop count of a frame. It is of interest mainly for nodes with routing functionality. The Transport Layer enables 4 types communication relationship between communication points: one-to-many connectionless (multicast), one-to-all connectionless (broadcast), one-to-one connectionless, one-to-one connection-oriented. KNX does not define session and presentation layers, however it has provisioned for an Application Layer, in order to offer a variety of application services to the application process. The actual services are different depending on the type of communication used at transport layer. Additionally, KNX defines 2 additional stack sub-categories, the router stack and the bridge stack. Routers are used to guide information through disparate KNX net topologies (think the equivalent of a network multiplexer). Bridges function as re-transmitters, to connect distant net topologies (e.g. as links between different power phases in 3phase systems), or to amplify a weakened KNX signal source – since the maximum length in a KNX copper power-line is around 400-600m.

It should be noted that the KNX protocol is layer flexible. It allows the KNX developer to turn stack layers on or off (starting from the top and moving downwards) up-to the data link layer. Certain applications are expected to run in very simple KNX network topology configurations, thus they need the first 2 layers to function properly. By disabling the overlaying stack segments, the stack implementation can be hosted in very minute and cheap microprocessors (typically in just 8 Kbytes of memory). When more complex topologies are necessary, the application designer must deploy additional layers, which support more complex net configurations, but need stronger micro-processors, both in terms of processing power and memory. A full PL110/PL132 device stack implementation can be expected to be hosted in 70Kbytes of code on an 16-bit micro-processor base, including support for network management procedures and net topology administration.

With **22279** partners (ranging from system integrators to equipment producers) in **109** countries the KNX association is clearly wide spread and offers to many products to present a list.

KNX Bus devices can either be sensors or actuators needed for the control of building management equipment such as: lighting, blinds / shutters, security systems, energy management, heating, ventilation and air-conditioning systems, signalling and monitoring systems, interfaces to service and building control systems, remote control, metering, audio / video control, white goods, etc.

The main focus of KNX installation is to deal with single-family houses or office complexes growing requirements for: comfort and versatility in the management of air-conditioning, energy efficiency, metering, lighting, surveillance and access control systems.

3.3.5 LonWorks

LonWorks [225] is a network platform offering an alternative to KNX. It has been originally designed by Echelon Corporation and nowadays it is fostered by the LonMark International, the California-registered, non-profit successor to the original, unincorporated Association, since 2003. Commercial products based on LonWorks are less focused on houses and offices compared to KNX, trying to address also factories and infrastructures needs.

LonWorks presents the world's largest smart meter deployment success story. Before 2005 Enel Spa, the major energy provider in Italy, deployed smart meters to its entire customer base (around 30 millions customers). These meters are fully electronic and smart, with integrated bi-directional communications, advanced power measurement and management capabilities, an integrated, software-controllable disconnect switch, and no moving parts. The communication happens over low voltage power line from the meter to data concentrators via IP from data concentrators to Enel's enterprise servers. Those smart meters feature the ability to remotely turn power on or off to a customer, read usage information from a meter, detect a service outage, detect the unauthorized use of electricity, change the maximum amount of electricity that a customer can demand at any time, and remotely change the meter's billing plan from credit to prepay as well as from flat-rate to multi-tariff.

The Lonworks network platform uses the LonTalk protocol. Lontalk is a control network specific protocol, defined by ANSI standard ANSI/CEA 709.1. The LonTalk protocol has been ratified by standards setting bodies in various industries and regions. Recently, aspects of Lontalk have been recognized by international standardization bodies, mainly ISO/IEC (ISO/IEC 14908 standard number). ISO and IEC have granted the communications protocol twisted pair signalling technology, power line signalling technology, and Internet Protocol (IP) compatibility standard numbers ISO/IEC 14908-1, -2, -3, and -4. The twisted pair physical layer operates at 78kbit/s and uses differential Manchester encoding, while the power line physical layer achieves either 5.4 or 3.6 kbit/s, depending on frequency. The [IP](#) tunneling standard - ISO/IEC 14908-4 (ANSI/CEA-852) – is utilized by a number of manufacturers to connect the devices on previously deployed and new LonWorks platform-based networks to IP-aware applications or remote network-management tools.

The Lontalk protocol can optionally provide end-to-end acknowledgement of messages, authentication of messages, and priority delivery to provide bounded transaction times. Support for network management services lets remote network management tools interact with devices over the network, so they can configure network addresses and parameters, download application programs, diagnose network problems, start/stop/reset device application programs.

Networks based on Lontalk are built on a flat, peer-to-peer architecture. Therefore, devices are free to directly communicate with each other, thus reducing bottlenecks and preventing system-wide failures that may occur in master-based architectures. As a result, Lontalk-based networks offer high reliability and performance.

3.3.6 Sensinode

Sensinode [226] is a pioneering IP-based wireless sensor network solution provider. It claims to offer seamless internet integration to embedded device and chip manufacturers through all industries. Their offering ranges from software to hardware products. NanoStack, which the current version is 2.0, a communication stack for IP-based wireless sensor networks leveraging on 6LoWPAN. Key features include small code footprint, as little as 32 k of flash, and the support for 2.4 GHz (CC2430 and CC2530) and 868/915 MHz (CC1110) Texas Instruments chips, and extreme robustness. NoveView is a network analyzer and site survey tool for 6LoWPAN network researchers, designers and integrators. This tool gives a graphical analysis of 6LoWPAN networks, including full node statistics, network topologies, routing information and map support. NanoRouter is a router software and platform solution between IP-based 6LoWPAN low-power wireless networks and backbone IP networks. NanoRouter aims to offer scalable, reliable and seamless connectivity between Internet and leading edge wireless sensor networks. NanoSensor is an evaluation, development and testing sensor node based on NanoStack firmware, it comes with 2.4 Ghz or Sub Ghz radio.

The only Sensinode based final product seems to be the integration of the Sensinode platform in the radiocrafts [54] solution for automatic metering infrastructures (AMI), which integrates KNX as well, enabling IP communications for all wireless meters, submeters and home automation devices and in addition seamlessly integrates M-Bus and Wireless M-Bus devices into IP. NanoStack is integrated into electric meters, sub-meters and home automation devices, providing an all-IP network using inexpensive radio chips, yet allowing for reliable mesh networking. The solution allows for battery-powered devices with a lifetime of years. NanoRouter products provide routing between the wireless

devices running NanoStack and the utility backbone. NanoRouter is also available for integration into electric meters which act as the gateway to the utility backbone network.

3.3.7 ZigBee

ZigBee [224] addresses the area of Wireless Personal Area Networking, focusing on limitations imposed by other WPAN protocols, mainly Bluetooth and WiFi. It shares the same low layer with 6LoWPAN (802.15.4) but it doesn't exploit Internet Protocol for networking, introducing ZigBee own ad hoc networking and defining its own high level API.

ZigBee is a very low-cost, very low-power consumption, two way, wireless communication standard. Its stack architecture is made up of a set of layers, having each layer perform a specific set of services for the layer above. ZigBee stack data entities provide data transmission services, whereas management entities provides all other services. Each service entity exposes an interface to the upper layer through a Service Access Point (SAP) and each SAP supports a number of service primitives to achieve the required functionality. The ZigBee protocol builds upon the physical and medium access control layers defined by the IEEE 802.15.4-2003 standard. Specifically, it provides a network layer and the framework for the application layer, which comprises the application support sub-layer and the ZigBee Device Objects (ZDO).

The ZigBee network layer supports star, tree and mesh topologies. In a star topology, the network is controlled by a single device, the ZigBee coordinator, which is the device responsible for associating and disassociating devices into the Personal Area Network it controls. The coordinator initiates and maintains the devices on the network; all other devices communicate directly with the coordinator. In the case of mesh and tree topologies, the coordinator is responsible for starting the network and choosing key network parameters. ZigBee networks may also be extended via devices that incorporate ZigBee routing functionality, thus acting as ZigBee routers.

The ZigBee application layer consists of the APplication Support (APS) sublayer, the ZigBee Device Objects (ZDO) and the manufacturer-defined application objects. The APS sub-layer provides an interface between the network layer and the APplication Layer (APL), through a general set of services used by both the ZDO and the manufacturer-defined application objects. APL services include data transmission between two or more application entities located on the same network, as well as security services, binding of devices and maintaining a database of managed objects. ZigBee Device Objects are the portion of the application layer responsible for defining the role of a device within the network (i.e. ZigBee coordinator or end device), initiating and/or responding to binding and discovery requests and establishing a secure relationship between network devices. ZDO satisfies common requirements of all applications operating in a ZigBee protocol stack. Finally, manufacturer-defined application objects are used to model end devices (i.e. a light switch).

There are a number of available ZigBee products and they seem to focus on three different sectors: Smart Energy, Home automation and Telecom Services. ZigBee Smart Energy is a world's leading standard for interoperable products that monitor, control, inform and automate the delivery and use of energy and water. These products enable utilities and governments to deploy smart grid solutions. Manufacturers providing ZigBee Smart Energy products are available at [227]. ZigBee Home Automation offers a global standard for interoperable products enabling smart homes that can control appliances, lighting, environment, energy management, and security as well as expand to connect with other ZigBee networks. Smarter homes focus revolved around safety, greenness and cost reductions. Manufacturers providing ZigBee Home Automation products are available at [228]. ZigBee Telecom Services offers a global standard for interoperable products enabling a wide variety of value-added services, including information delivery, mobile gaming, location-based services, secure mobile payments, mobile advertising, zone billing, mobile office access control, payments, and peer-to-peer data-sharing services. Manufacturers providing ZigBee Telecom Services products are available at [229].

3.4 Standardization activities

3.4.1 IETF

IETF Working Groups are created to address a specific problem or to produce one or more specific documents aimed at speeding up the standardization process. The duration of these groups depends solely on the achievement of their objectives and they manage almost all the work through mailing lists. Each Working Group (WG) has a charter, which specifies the scope of the work to be carried out and lists how the objectives will be achieved. Currently, there are three active working groups dealing with protocols for the Internet of Things, these cover routing, IP-based addressing and application domains:

ROLL (routing): Routing Over Low power and Lossy networks;

6LoWPAN (IP addressing): IPv6 over Low power WPAN;

CORE (application domain): Constrained RESTful Environments.

In addition, a WG for the implementation guidance for lightweight TCP/IP protocol suites for constrained devices is also under proposal. Currently, this WG is under evaluation by IETF. The WG goes under the name of:

Lwip (Lightweight IP Protocol Stacks for the Internet of Things).

3.4.1.1 ROLL – Routing Over Low Power and Lossy Networks

The ROLL charter has been created to design efficient routing algorithms for Low power and Lossy networks (LLNs). These networks are composed of energy and in general resource constrained devices that communicate through a variety of technologies, such as IEEE 802.15.4, Bluetooth, Low Power WiFi, wired or low power PLC (Powerline Communication). Also, communication links are typically characterized by high loss rates, low data rates, and instability (variable error rates as a function of time). In the literature, several routing protocols such as OSPF, IS-IS, AODV and OLSR were proposed for distributed ad hoc networks, but the ROLL WG has decided to design a new protocol, as prior solutions are not suitable to the specific requirements of routing in LLNs. This new protocol is called routing protocol for Low power and Lossy Networks (RPL) [210]. RPL is focused on the specific routing issues of LLNs, targeting a number of important applications: 1) home and building automation, 2) urban WSNs and 3) industrial sensor networks. For these application scenarios, the Working Group focuses on an IPv6-based architectural framework and pays particular attention to security and manageability, such as self-configuration of the routing algorithm.

In addition to the RPL document, the WG has delivered a number of parallel RFCs which define the application scenarios, the requirements and touch upon addressing issues, with particular regards to IPv6 addressing. These documents are briefly commented in what follows.

Routing Requirements for Urban Low-Power and Lossy Networks [211]: this document details application-specific IPv6 routing requirements for Urban Low-Power and Lossy Networks (U-LLNs). A U-LLN is a network composed of three key elements (sensors, actuators and routers) that communicate wirelessly over a variety of links such as IEEE 802.15.4, low-power IEEE 802.11, or IEEE 802.15.1 (Bluetooth). U-LLNs, given the limited radio range of their devices and the large number of nodes therein, require the use of suitable routing protocols.

Industrial Routing Requirements in Low-Power and Lossy Networks [212]: this RFC focuses on the functional requirements for a routing protocol for industrial Low-power and Lossy Networks (LLNs). These networks are composed of wireless “field” devices: typically, these are physical devices placed in the plant’s operating environment. The industrial market classifies process applications into three broad categories and six classes; each category has specific requirements in terms of routing performance (as an example, delay or throughput) as well as security:

Category 1: Safety

Class 0: Emergency action - Always a critical function.

Category 2: Control

Class 1: Closed-loop regulatory control - Often a critical function;

Class 2: Closed-loop supervisory control - Usually a non-critical function;

Class 3: Open-loop control - Operator takes action and controls the actuator.

Category 3: Monitoring

Class 4: Alerting - Short-term operational effect;

Class 5: Logging and downloading / uploading - No immediate operational consequence.

Home Automation Routing Requirements in Low-Power and Lossy Networks [213]: in future houses we will probably find a large number of wireless devices such as actuators (relays, light dimmers, heating valves), sensors (wall switches, water leak, blood pressure) and advanced controllers (radio- frequency-based AV remote control, central server for light and heat control). These devices are usually resources limited; hence, multi-hop routing is often necessary to enable communications among them (which may be impeded by obstacles which cause adverse shadowing effects). This RFC presents the specific requirements to home control and automation applications for Routing Over Low power and Lossy (ROLL) networks. All traffic in a ROLL network is typically carried as IPv6 packets.

Building Automation Routing Requirements in Low-Power and Lossy Networks [214]: this RFC defines the IPv6 routing requirements for building automation. It provides recommendations on how Building Management Systems (BMSs) should be built. In short, a BMS is a hierarchical system of sensors, actuators, controllers and users interfaces that interoperate to provide a safe and comfortable environment. This RFC gives some guidelines about the device density as a function of type of application and its specific installation. Also, it contains some references that explain the issues of device mobility along with the required manageability for the routing protocol.

In addition to previous RFCs, the ROLL WG is working on a number of Internet-Drafts, which are currently under review by the Internet community. These Internet-Drafts are briefly discussed in what follows:

RPL: IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low power and Lossy Networks [210]: RPL is the main endeavour of the ROLL working group; this protocol is designed in order to match the requirements of networks characterized by limited energy resources and lossy transmission links. The RPL protocol defines a Destination Oriented Direct Acyclic Graph (DODAG) rooted at the sink (the data gathering node), which minimizes the cost of reaching the sink from any node in the network, as defined by a suitable Objective Function (OF) [215]. This algorithm periodically sends control messages in the network to build and maintain the routes, and it can connect, in a completely transparent way, to any application that needs to perform multi-hop transmissions. Mainly, there are two types of messages: DODAG Information Object (DIO) messages and Destination Advertisement Object (DAO) messages. DIO is always sent in broadcast using the Trickle algorithm [216] and it is used to build and maintain tree connectivity specifying the necessary parameters to configure the root node. Instead, DAO is transmitted upwards to the sink and it is used to determine the downroutes (routes from the sink to the network nodes), thus sink and intermediate nodes (called forwarder nodes) are able to build their own routing tables.

The Trickle Algorithm [216]: the Trickle algorithm allows nodes in a shared lossy medium to exchange information in a highly robust, energy efficient and scalable manner. The basic idea behind it is to limit the number of concurrent transmissions by close-by nodes (and thus the number of packet collisions) through a careful, and density aware, listen before talk approach. If the channel is found busy, the nodes adapt their own transmissions windows to limit, as much as possible, the number of colliding packets. A simple suppression mechanism and transmission point selection allows Trickle's communication rate to scale logarithmically with density. In the case of RPL, the Trickle algorithm [216] is used to broadcast of DIOs (through multiple hops). Specifically, retransmissions are suppressed if a prescribed number of messages K is overhead within a given interval. Therefore, increasing K has the effect of suppressing a lower number of DIO retransmissions (up to $K=255$, which conventionally eliminates the suppression function), while a lower value of K poses a stronger limit on the retransmission rate, possibly slowing down the dissemination time, but also yielding a good side effect, as it reduces the packet collision probability.

3.4.1.2 6LoWPAN – Ipv6 over Low Power Wireless Personal Area Networks

6LoWPAN is an acronym of IPv6 over Low power Wireless Personal Area Networks and this is the name of the Working Group that has defined to devise encapsulation and header compression mechanisms that allow IPv6 packets to be communicated Low Power and possibly energy/communication constrained networks. Even though the emphasis is on the IEEE 802.15.4 PHY layer transmission technology, the IP header compression scheme defined within 6LoWPAN can also be used in different settings.

Two complete RFCs have been released so far: “IPv6 over Low-Power Wireless Personal Area Networks (6LoWPANs): Overview, Assumptions, Problem Statement, and Goals” [217] and “Transmission of IPv6 Packets over IEEE 802.15.4 Networks” [218]. The first RFC discusses the issues to be tackled to implement IPv6 addressing in Low Power Wireless Personal Area Networks, while the second defines the format for the adaptation between IPv6 and 802.15.4.

IPv6 over Low-Power Wireless Personal Area Networks (6LoWPANs) [217]: this RFC gives an overview of Low Power Wireless Personal Area Networks (LoWPAN) and describes how they benefit from IP and, in particular, from IPv6 networking. LoWPANs are characterized by:

- **Small packet sizes:** as an example, IEEE802.15.4's standard packet size is 127 octets. A maximum frame overhead of 25 octets spares 102 octets at MAC layer. The addition of link-layer security leaves, in the best case, 81 octets for data.
- Support for both 16-bit short or IEEE 64-bit extended MAC addresses.
- **Low data rates:** 250 kbps, 40 kbps or 20 kbps.
- **Topology:** support for star and mesh topologies.
- **Constrained devices:** low cost, low power, energy / computationally constrained and inherently unreliable devices.
- **Device deployment:** location of the devices is typically not predefined, as they tend to be deployed in an ad-hoc fashion.
- **Duty cycling:** Devices connected to a LoWPAN may sleep for long periods of time in order to conserve energy (radio duty cycling), and are unable to communicate during these periods.

Finally, this RFC describes problems associated with enabling IP communication across devices in a LoWPAN, and defines methods to address these in a prioritized manner.

Transmission of IPv6 Packets over IEEE 802.15.4 Networks [218]: this RFC defines the frame format for transmission of IPv6 packets and the method that shall be used to create IPv6 link-local addresses and stateless auto-configured addresses in IEEE 802.15.4 networks. It also defines an adaptation layer to support native IPv6 packets as well as an header compression mechanism to make IPv6 practical for IEEE 802.15.4 networks. The header compression mechanism, called HC1, is the most important contribution of this RFC, as it allows to represent native IPv6 headers with just a few bytes, so that they can be efficiently transmitted by energy constrained devices. Using HC1, the only IPv6 header field that always needs to be copied in the compressed address is the Hop Limit (8 bits) field; often all the other necessary fields can be inferred from the rest of the frame. The use of HC1 is made possible by stateless address auto-configuration, defined either by RFC 2464 or by link local addressing as defined by 6LoWPAN. Similarly, parts of the next header fields (UDP, TCP, ICMP) can be deduced from information available elsewhere in the frame. For UDP, only the length field can be deduced. However, some of the non-deducible information can be compressed thus reducing the UDP header up to 4 octets at best. The method of derivation of Interface Identifiers from IEEE 64-bit MAC addresses is intended to preserve global uniqueness when possible. However, there is no protection from duplication through accident or forgery. A sizeable portion of IEEE 802.15.4 devices is expected to always communicate within their PAN (within their “link”, in IPv6 terms). In response to cost and power consumption considerations, the devices of a LowPAN will typically implement the minimum set of necessary features. Accordingly, security for such devices may rely quite strongly on the mechanisms defined at the link layer by IEEE 802.15.4. However, the only security mechanisms currently defined are the advanced encryption standard (AES) modes for authentication or encryption of IEEE 802.15.4 frames that do not, in particular, specify any technique for key management.

3.4.1.3 CORE – Constrain RESTful - Representational state transfer Environment

CoRE (Constrain RESTful – Representational state transfer Environment) is a Working Group in the applications area of IETF with the target of providing a framework for resource-oriented applications intended to run on constrained IP-based devices. This WG aims at specifying a RESTful Web-based protocol for even the most constrained embedded devices and networks. CoRE is a major enabler for all kinds of sensor networks such as LowPANs, M2M and other Internet of Things applications. The framework takes into consideration the manipulation of simple resources on constrained networks, which is implemented through a dedicated protocol called Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP).

Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) [219]: CoAP is developed to run in special environments that have strict constraints in terms of limited energy resources, high packet loss rates, limited hardware capabilities and so on. The main features of CoAP are reported below:

- Low-overhead;
- Able to run in devices with highly constrained hardware;
- UDP-based for resource-constrained IP networks and nodes;
- Ability to deal with sleeping nodes.

For more detail about these features and other requirements see [220].

CoAP defines two types of transmissions among end-points (i.e., devices that can communicate with each other):

- **Synchronous interaction:** regular client/server interaction;
- **Asynchronous interaction:** when a client has requested one or several services at server in the network and it sends the response when the data are ready. Thus, the client does not wait for the response from the server.

CoAP is developed to run in the face of high packet losses while at the same time providing a congestion control algorithm (transport layer for constrained devices) to decide when to retransmit packets (in an end-to-end fashion) by also taking into consideration the overhead caused by these retransmissions. For more a more detailed discussion of the CoAP congestion algorithm see [220].

CoAP communication follows a Web-based communication paradigm, where resources are accessed through four simple methods: GET, PUT, POST, DELETE, transactions can be both synchronous and asynchronous. CoAP shall support multicasting, due to efficiency considerations, and efficient device/resource discovery algorithms should be provided. The preferred format for the exchange of DATA and COMMANDs is XML and, in particular, its compressed representation (EXI). Resources are addressed through Universal Resource Identifiers (URIs). All of this is in line with modern Web-based communication paradigms and, as such, enables the direct integration of constrained networks into the IP world.

3.4.1.1 Lwip: Lightweight IP Protocol Stacks for the Internet of Things

IP technology is envisioned to provide a highly interoperable environment for the smart devices that will be populating the Internet of Things. Implementing TCP/IP protocols on these very constrained devices is a challenging task. There are many techniques that can be used to implement lightweight

TCP/IP protocol suites. These include lightweight design of data structures and packet processing, smart memory management, TCP window optimizations as well as cross-layer optimizations. Currently there are no clear design guidelines for these efficient and lightweight TCP/IP implementations. The aim of this IETF WG is that of providing these guidelines.

The current work items of the WG are:

1. Provide an informational documents, “the problem statement”, that shall formalize the problem and specify the common known issues met by implementers.
2. Provide a document describing implementation techniques that met the challenges listed in the problem statement document. Particular emphasis will be given to guidelines for the realization of implementations which minimize the memory occupation and as well as optimize the energy consumption of the constrained devices.
3. Develop a number of the profiles for lightweight, minimal IP implementations. The IP protocols, either IPv4 or IPv6, include multiple mechanisms. Some of them are not required for interoperability. One of the aims of this WG is that of providing guidelines for the design of IP implementations including the minimum number of functionalities required for interoperability with existing TCP/IP stacks.

This WG was recently proposed and is currently under evaluation by IETF. An Internet draft was recently proposed and is named: “Stack Analysis for Lightweight IP Implementation”.

3.4.2 IEEE 802.15.4e

The amendment 802.15.4e [221] describes a number of extensions to the 802.15.4 MAC layer. The Low Latency (LL) MAC, that can be used for critical applications mainly in the factory automation and control scenarios. The LL MAC implements a TDMA based star network with reduced headers to allow for cycle times as low as 10ms. Regarding the Internet of things, the LL mode does not allow IP on the device level and has to be interfaced by an application layer gateway. The amendment contains further, the distributed synchronous multi-channel extension (DSME), which tries to extend and overcome some limitations of the 802.15.4 beacons mode. Finally, the amendment will contain two well-proven options for meshed low power 802.15.4 networks: the Low Energy (LE) mode and the Time Synchronized Channel Hopping (TSCH) mode. Due to their relevance for the Internet of Things these will be described in more detail.

The LE (Low Energy) mode implements two mechanisms that provide a best effort medium access with sleeping devices without the need for synchronization. Coordinated Sampled Listening (CSL) makes the receiver listening shortly for activity once in a period, while the sender has to transmit a wakeup sequence with the address of the receiver and the time remaining to the transmission. With help of the acknowledgement of the receiver, the sender can optimize its sending schedule to reduce the length of the wakeup sequence. Receiver Initiated Transmission (RIT) inverts the principle; here the sender waits for a ready-to-receive packet of the receiver before transmitting the packet. The scheme is useful in regions, where sending long back-to-back packet trains is not allowed by regulation. The mechanisms are applicable for use cases that have no stringent latency requirements – at duty cycles below 1% delays might sum up to multiple seconds. Both mechanisms are well understood in the sensor network community, e.g. the Low Power Listening (LPL) available in TinyOS is a variation of CSL.

TSCH (Time Synchronized Channel Hopping) implements a TDMA MAC access with channel hopping. It represents a similar mechanism to the protocol used in the industry proven Wireless HART protocol. The application areas are seen mainly in process automation, oil & gas industry, green energy production. The basic structure of the media access is given by cyclic repetition of slotframes that contain slots reserved for specific communication, e.g. between two nodes. Due to this structure the whole network is synchronized and allows for hopping through the available channels based on an absolute count of the slot numbers. These features provide a foreseeable performance and make the TSCH MAC robust against packet collisions and interference. To achieve the mentioned properties, the TSCH MAC layer needs to be managed. i.e. the slots need to be assigned to proper positions in the slotframe. The management is out of the scope of the IEEE specification and needs to be addressed in IoT-A, e.g. as module or layer.

3.4.3 DPWS - Device Profile for Web Services

The Device Profile for Web Services (DPWS) [222] standardizes the process of consuming and exposing Web Services in a lightweight footprint. DPWS targets resource-constrained devices explicitly so that it can be applied to a variety of embedded devices. A key concept is the creation of a distributed SOA within heterogeneous environments. The basic messaging within DPWS is based on SOAP using HTTP and SOAP-over-UDP.

DPWS was inspired by Universal Plug'n'Play (UPnP), which was the first specification of a service-oriented infrastructure for embedded application scenarios, and defines a minimal set of web service standards and specification:

- Sending secure messages to and from web services
- Dynamic discovery of web services
- Description of web services
- Subscription to and Reception of web service events

In detail the following web service standards are used by DPWS: WSDL 1.1, XML Schema, SOAP 1.2, WS-Addressing, WS-MetadataExchange, WS-Transfer, WS-Policy, WS-Security, WS-Discovery and WS-Eventing.

The first definition of DPWS was published in 2004, the standardization is driven through the foundation of the OASIS Web Services Discovery and Web Services Devices Profile (WS-DD) Technical Committee in the year 2008.

Currently there are two software stacks supporting DPWS, both offering implementations for Java and C/C++: SOA4D¹³ and WS4D¹⁴. DPWS is also natively integrated in Windows Vista and Windows Embedded platforms through the WSDAPI stack.

For IoT-A DPWS is an interesting protocol for communication between distributed devices. Since DPWS is standardized, has a quite good dissemination and there exist several implementations the relevance for IoT-A is high.

¹³ <https://forge.soa4d.org/>

¹⁴ <http://www.ws4d.org/>

4. State of the Art in Identification and Resolution Frameworks

4.1 Introduction

In the Internet of Things (IoT), Entities of Interest (EoI), resources and their services are spread globally. Thus, there must be a sort of identification and resolution infrastructure to discover and lookup the services that allow accessing information about EoIs as well as controlling them. The overall objective of work package 4 (WP4) is to build a resolution infrastructure for the IoT considering security and privacy issues. The first step towards a resolution infrastructure for the IoT is given in this document. It aims to provide an extensive analysis of the state of the art in identification and resolution frameworks and related areas and serves partially as a basis for WP1 and its reference architecture.

The structure of this document is divided into 4 main sections to cover each important aspect concerning identification and resolution frameworks. In subsection 4.2 the latest research developments are presented, along with some background to the topic. Subsection 4.3 describes results from recent public project in the context of the IoT that seem to be particularly relevant to an Internet of Things architecture. Subsection 4.4 presents the commercial usage of relevant technologies regarding identification. Finally, subsection 4.5 addresses recent standardization activities for different technologies and domains.

4.2 Latest research developments

4.2.1 Identification, Naming and Addressing

As more computer resources are accessed in a remote and distributed manner, their identification needs to be globally unique. Resource Identification can essentially encompass both the naming and addressing of a resource, or either of them. In the Web, the identification of a resource that represents some form of information has been achieved by the development of the Universal Resource Identifier (URI) [235], which is a global agreement on the identification of a particular resource based on specified schemes. These schemes usually provide an indication to the type of the resource. But also, the resource itself could have multiple names or 'aliases'. In IoT, similar to the Internet and the Web, objects and resources need to have common naming and addressing schemes and also discovery services to enable global reference and access to them. In this section, we review common identification, naming and addressing schemes and frameworks that can contribute to designing a naming and addressing scheme in IoT-A.

According to [299], a name is an access index applied to a set of objects in order to identify a single particular object. More concrete, names are pieces of information assigned to persons, things, organizations, or terms or nouns. Thus, a name is a label or an attribute of an object used for individualisation within a larger set of objects. In addition to names that identify individuals, names are also used to identify groups or subsets of objects (generic names) as in taxonomies or classification hierarchies. Both names and addresses are used to identify objects, but in case of addresses the identification refers to the location of the object within a space. Since physical objects are usually located at some place, an address is a mandatory attribute of an item while a name is optional.

As in computing, a data object may have a name or – as part of an array – not. It definitely has a memory location and, hence, an address in the memory space. To access the object, the address must be known or must be derived (or resolved) from further information about the object. In the real world, objects may assume variable locations in case they are mobile and, therefore, addresses may not be constant attributes of objects. On the other hand names usually are constants.

In IC technology, names and addresses are required to be unique: even an object can have more than one name, each name is assigned to not more than one specific object (in a given context) and an address cannot refer to two or more locations. Naming is the procedure of assigning a name to an object while addressing refers to placing the object into the space. Look-up of objects refers to finding a suitable object with respect to a request, resolving its name to get an address and then resolving the address to get the object.

Some concepts to identify a resource may or may not have a semantic relevance to the resource itself. In SENSEI [298], the resource ID is formed through a concatenation of several parameters; the domain of resource's provider, the type of device, a name representative of the resource's function, and a unique identifier that differentiates the resource from others of the same device type. In the

Ubiquitous ID (uID) framework [339], identification is represented by the 'uCode', which is a unique identifier for either physical or logical entities. The uCode itself is a 128-bit number that has no relationship to what it represents, but rather the relationship is retrieved from dedicated database servers. The structure of the uCode is formed in a manner to support its management.

In the field of RFIDs, EPCglobal [260] have promoted the adoption and standardization of Electronic Product Code (EPC), which has been used as a means of uniquely identifying RFID tags. It is based on the URI model. ID@URI developed by the DIALOG research project [252] is also another identification model that takes the same properties of the EPC/ONS standard but can also be manifested in barcodes as well.

Resources are also expected to be mobile and hence their location changes. Usually the identification of a remote resource is bound to its location, as originally happened with IP addresses. It has been argued that this should not be the case and that the ID should remain consistent, and its location should be dynamically mapped. An example of this is the concept of the locator-identifier split adopted in the Host Identity Protocol (HIP) [277].

In another project related to the IoT, the identification of Connected Objects (CO) [260] is achieved using namespace members which can be global or local, and could either be unique or overlapping. For uniqueness, it makes use of Host Identities (HI) [277], which is a namespace based public and private keys.

In the mobile telecoms domain, the International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI) [278] provides means for unique identification for mobile phones. IMEI is formed through a set of digits that represent the manufacturer, the unit itself and the software installed on it.

Types of Addresses

When talking about the Internet of Things, the addressing is an important issue; because the addresses are used to identify and access the objects and to bind objects/resources to machine addressable and identifiable names. There is the well-known postal address which contains codes or names for country, city and city code, street, street number in any order. There are about as many formats for postal addresses as there are countries in the world. The other physical address is the spatial position given by a geographic coordinate system with values for latitude and longitude. As well, there are different formats for geographic coordinates. Today, GPS is the technique used to determine a position.

The following, however, refer to addresses and names of electronic objects at various levels of the OSI stack along with their related protocols: MAC Address [291], IP Address [282], E-Mail Address [259], Uniform Resource Name (URN) [340], Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) [341], Uniform Resource Locator (URL) [342], Peer-to-Peer Address using Distributed Hash Tables [253].

The identification schemes reviewed above aim for the unique identification of a resource. Some use an arbitrary set of numbers, or numbered in a manner that assists its management by the resolution framework. The advantage of this approach is that it limits the size of the ID. However using an arbitrary set of numbers provides no indication to what it is represented. On the other hand, some approaches have employed the use of a structure that indicates the type and function of the resource. Although this approach is easier to relate to it is very likely it will not be viable for heavily constrained resources. Therefore it seems that the use of both identification approaches needs to be adopted to encompass all types of resources. This will then likely lead to the use of a presiding unified identification scheme for the IoT-A that then translates to the identification scheme of the corresponding technology in question.

4.2.2 Resolution Frameworks

Resolution frameworks are used for resolving queries to object abstractions (whether they are information providers/users) that represent physical and/or virtual entities intended for capturing and/or managing context from the physical world. The object abstractions are the virtual representation of physical objects. Queries to object abstractions would return the description and the ways of interaction with the objects, Resolution in IoT-A has been identified as involving three main functionalities: discovery, lookup and monitoring. As mentioned in section 1.1, lookup refers to finding an object that can fulfil a given request or task, including resolving its name and address in order to interact with it. A lookup framework generally involves a repository with a known location identifier that stores the object information and can be searched with different levels of query interfaces. Discovery includes lookup but the associated framework may or may not include a fixed repository. Thus, it may

include peer-to-peer device interactions, where devices announce their capabilities on a known network channel. Monitoring in the IoT-A project context refers to keeping the dynamic links between resources and entities up-to-date. The entities refer to real world entities such as persons or objects such as buildings, cars, tools etc.

As identified in [262], many of the existing use cases involve RFID for identification and tracking of objects. The Electronic Product Code (EPC) global architecture [260] includes servers for EPC Information Services (EPCIS), which provide data about the objects that are in turn identified by Object Identifiers (OIDs). The EPCglobal implements the notion of OIDs with the EPC numbering scheme. Thus, the resolution framework is organized as a lookup service that stores references to EPCIS linked to EPC numbers about which they provide data. The BRIDGE project [240] is targeted at RFID implementation in Europe. The resolution framework proposed therein consists of directory services, deployed either as a single server or as a network of federated servers that provide lookup for EPCIS. The servers store data on the objects, which are identified by EPC numbers. The Dialog project [252] is aimed at developing a worldwide tracking and tracing system and proposes the ID@URI naming system for object resolution. The two components of this system are client and object agent. The object agent is identified by the ID@URI identifier, where the URI part is the object's domain name belonging to the object's manufacturing company and the ID is locally assigned by the company. Any existing naming system, such as EPC, serial numbers etc. can be used for the ID part. The client is used for reading product identifiers and connecting to the object agent. Since all the data about a product is managed by one object agent and stored in its domain, only that data source needs to be discovered for resolution. However, this framework requires the core infrastructure to be hosted and maintained by the host manufacturer of the tagged product, which is restrictive for the IoT-A project aims.

In the sensor network domain, several research initiatives have looked at interconnection between sensors and the Internet through middleware architectures [234], [269], [288], [330]. The Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) data is then made available as a service on the Internet. The IP overlay over the WSN is achieved by IPv6-based architectures like 6LoWPAN protocol, with additional management features like auto-configuration and neighbour discovery at the TCP/IP level. Several of these research solutions use the Device Profile for Web Services (DPWS) standards for providing the WSN functionalities on the Internet. DPWS is a lightweight subset of Web Services technologies that brings plug-and-play features to resource-limited devices. The resolution framework in these approaches consists of a gateway that mediates data exchange between sensor nodes and Web applications. The address mapping between WSN and Internet applications is performed at the gateway by employing the IPv4/IPv6 support in the WSN architecture. A service directory in the gateway stores the offered functionalities of the sensors and their endpoints. Some approaches [269] include additional service metadata such as execution environment requirements and installation instructions for on-demand provisioning. A survey [337] of WSN middleware concludes that a SOA model for WSN-Internet connection guarantees flexibility and provides a higher level of abstraction. The SOA-based middleware approach can be utilized in the IoT-A project, but the approaches reviewed here rely on the DPWS standard, which offers only WSDL-based descriptions of the sensor resources. This needs to be augmented to include semantic descriptions and also resources that may offer only RESTful interfaces.

The SENSEI Resolution Framework is responsible for exposing IoT-resources with unique identifiers. It requires that SENSEI resource providers use resource identifiers which are unique within their administrative domain [332]. Peered Resource Directories concatenate the resource identifier with the domain name they belong to. In consequence, the resources are unique globally, assuming the domains are unique too. The schema to be used for describing SENSEI resources is mandatory for all resource providers so that Resource Users are able to interpret the descriptions no matter who has published them [344]. SENSEI resource descriptions are extensible and can be reused in IoT-A. SENSEI is designed to cope with several Entity models. Entities are identified by their namespace and their RDF instance identifier. As long as IoT-A uses entity models expressed in RDF, SENSEI components can be reused.

4.2.3 Resource Discovery

In the IoT-A project, we are interested in discovering resources that can provide information about the entity of interest. In the future Internet, resources will offer their functionalities through Web Services or RESTful APIs, enabling interaction with other components. As the resources provide a window to the physical world, their functionalities are referred to as 'real-world services' [269]. The discovery process will be employed to return a list of real-world services that can fulfil a given request. The other aspect is resource discovery for tracking a known resource, as applied in RFID-based supply chain management. The following paragraphs provide the state of the art for both these aspects.

In RFID-based approaches, such as the EPCglobal [260] and BRIDGE project [240], resource discovery requires clients to be aware of the EPC number of the resource whose data they require. The EPCIS repositories are updated with event information by the relevant companies. A query with a given EPC number to the discovery service (DS) returns the references to the EPCIS that hold event information related to the queried EPC number. The references are submitted to the DNS to be resolved into IP addresses. The IP addresses are then used to query the EPCIS that provides the data regarding the concerned EPC. The BRIDGE project also considers alternative discovery architectures, which include resource notifications, notification of clients and query propagation. These follow the publish-subscribe mechanism for providing detailed resource data to clients.

In the ID@URI system [263] developed by the Dialog project [252], an application that wants to publish data about an object ID-related event first resolves the URI of the object to the IP address of the corresponding object agent, which is then contacted to store the event in the local event repository. When a client wants to access events that refer to an object identified by some ID, a querying application resolves the URI to an IP address and connects to the object agent, which uses the object ID for retrieving the data from the event repository to send it back to the query application.

When resource data is exposed through services, such as those in the DPWS-based solutions [234], [269], [330] the WS-Discovery specification of the DPWS stack is used to find new resources as they connect to the network and dynamically retrieve metadata about it and the services it hosts. The metadata categories include location or access rights-based scopes, device type and message types. The discovery process works as follows: when a new resource joins the network, it multicasts a 'hello' message via the UDP protocol. By listening to this message, clients/gateway middleware can detect new resources and in a second step, retrieve their metadata. To locate a specific resource or a set of matching resources for a given filter, a client can send a 'resolve' message to the same multicast group and the matching resource sends back a response directly to the client. In addition to the DPWS WS-Discovery method, the SOCRADES middleware [269] implements a RESTful network discovery mechanism for devices that do not support DPWS, but only HTTP. This mechanism requires devices that support HTTP to register themselves in the service repository with a PUT request. Discovery is achieved by issuing a GET request on the device page registered at the repository, which then retrieves the necessary information from the device and its services. The discovery mechanism adopted in the WSN-SOA architecture [288] follows the publish-subscribe method based on a 'topic'-based message filtering system. Producers publish messages to named logical channels called topics, with subscribers receiving all messages published to subscribed topics. Topics are created ad-hoc as they become available and are organised hierarchically, e.g. /notes/*/acceleration/tilt. Topics are exposed by the DPWS WS-Eventing specification.

The SENSEI resource discovery can be seen from three different perspectives. The first perspective is resource oriented and focuses on the resource discovery by unique Resource IDs or other parts of the Resource Description [344]. The discovery of Resources works over administrative domains. Another discovery mechanism provided by SENSEI Resource directories is a simple string matching based resolution method using free text tags defined in Resource descriptions [332]. Resource providers are allowed to use any text description there, which makes that approach error-prone and should not be followed in IoT-A. SENSEI's semantic oriented resolution method using SPARQL [345] queries on Advanced Resource Descriptions [332] of SENSEI Resources and Entity models [332] contributes to better interoperability of IoT services and is a good candidate for being used in IoT-A again.

The IoT-A discovery approach will need to investigate how semantic queries can support discovery of heterogeneous resource descriptions and interfaces in different application contexts. This will facilitate finding the relevant resource(s) even when queries may be worded differently by different applications or there may be gaps in the resource context information.

4.2.4 Search and Indexing Technologies

Indexing technologies are important for efficiently finding information that represents the result of a search. Indexing is widely used in databases, information management systems and search engines [327]. For simple one dimensional aspects like String indexing, there are a lot of off-the-shelf solutions. When searching Resources or for Entities of Interest, multiple dimensions may have to be considered. Of special importance is searching according to geographical location. To support such kinds of searches, multi-dimensional index structures are needed, e.g., grid indexes [318], quadtrees [319], octrees, Rtrees [272], kd-trees [297] and UB-trees [311]. However, these are typically used only in specialized systems like spatial databases [325] that are mostly centralized systems. Some of the recent work on indexing techniques and also discovery of distributed resources is also discussed in [286], [273], [326].

The resolution infrastructure will be a distributed system, so distributed index structures are needed. Examples of distributed index structures are known from peer-to-peer systems. They are suitable to maintain large distributed information bases in a robust and efficient manner [285]. Some of the recent

P2P protocol approaches are discussed in [331], [312]. In recent years there has been some work on efficiently retrieving information from large distributed systems especially regarding range queries [271] in so called Distributed Hash Tables (DHT) or other index structures [264], [233], [289].

For IoT-A it will be important to investigate how lookup and discovery of Resources and Entity of Interests can best be supported. This requires finding suitable index structure, especially spatial index structures. As the Internet of Things will be highly distributed and be composed of multiple domains, the distribution of index structure across multiple index servers has to be investigated.

4.2.5 Associations between Real World Entities and Resources

Developments in sensor technology have led to research initiatives that aim to add real world sense to various Web applications.

The SENSEI project realises associations between real world entities and resources with ‘bindings’, where attributes of real world entities are bound to an operation of a SENSEI resource. Operations can be related to attributes as input, output, precondition, and post condition. Examples of bindings are:

- Room123.hasTemperature (Output) <—> tempSensorABC/getTemperature
- Room123.isLocked (Postcondition) <-> lockActuator123/setLock

Other approaches use Semantic Web technologies to form associations between sensor data and real world entities. Standard representation formats (RDFS/OWL) are used for modelling various sensor data (sensor node and interface descriptions, and also observation and measurement data collected from sensors) at different levels to support interoperability. Semantically annotated sensor data is also amenable to logical reasoning to support advanced query and retrieval tasks. Sheth et al. [328] implement semantic extensions to the OGC SWE [301] standards to realise the concept of the semantic sensor web. The idea behind it is that with the semantic representation of the sensor observation and measurement model, one could add semantic annotations in terms of time, location, and thematic data into the actual sensor data to facilitate advanced query and reasoning. Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL) [346] rules are then defined to derive new and implicit knowledge from the semantic sensor data, such as ‘potentially icy’ condition from stored weather data [276]. An example of a SWRL rule that infers a ‘potentially icy’ weather condition by evaluating observed temperature measurements and the presence of rain [276] is given below:

```
Observation(?obs) ^ measured(?obs, ?precip) ^ Rain(?precip) ^
measured(?obs, ?temp) ^ Temperature(?temp) ^ temperature_value(?temp,
?tval) ^ lessThanOrEqual(?tval, 32) ^ unit_of_measurement(?temp,
Fahrenheit) -> described(?obs, Potentially_Icy)
```

The research works in [237], [347] propose using the “linked data” principle to connect the sensor data to existing knowledge represented in different ontologies. The approach followed employs annotation of the sensor description [237] and measurement data [347] with concepts already existing on the semantic Web; by creating RDF links, i.e. data published by authoritative sources using the linked data principle such as DBpedia [250]. Making connections from the real world resources to the existing semantic Web ontologies naturally promotes the idea of traversal of the semantic Web through the dimensions of time, space, and theme. The approach is illustrated by a mashup application that overlays sensor locations on a Google map, with access to related sensor descriptions. This is achieved by annotating sensor observation and measurement data and linking it to geographic data published by DBpedia.

The linked data principles can be used in the IoT-A project to reuse existing domain knowledge to provide semantic descriptions of resources. Dynamic associations between resources and entities can be inferred through rules, and it would require knowledge of both resource and entity description models. Both global and local mechanisms need to be considered in combination to dynamically track the inferred associations.

4.2.6 Entity Tracking and Localization

In the last few years, ICT services provided a new kind of added-value: location-based provision. In IoT applications, where context awareness will likely be an essential feature, knowing where the user or an Entity of Interest is, is very important.

In the following, this chapter relates about the state of the art of object localization and tracking, with focus on those methods and technologies which are of interest in IoT. For this reason we will analyze Internet-, wireless-network- and presence-based tracking methods for geo-localisation.

First of all, it is important to make a difference between technologies that provide **presence** and those providing proper **localisation**. Presence implicitly provides localization with maximum localization error roughly equal to the read range of the system, but such systems can only provide this data if the object is actually in the field of one of the active devices. This means that no information on the position of the device can be inferred when the device is out of the readers' range.

In the context of IoT, it is also important to distinguish between **implicit** and **explicit localisation** in networks. Implicit localisation means retrieving geo-localisation information (generally without the explicit consent of the user) from the routing information that is transported along with packets in the network. This kind of localisation is generally less accurate, with an accuracy that can drop to even tens of kilometres. Explicit localisation on the other hand uses specific localisation infrastructures (Global Positioning System (GPS), wireless networks, RFID, etc).

Systems can also be divided in **tracking** and **positioning**, where the former term defines systems that provide the coordinates of an object by calculations performed externally to the object while the later use hardware (or, generally speaking, processing or localization components) internal to the object. As an example the typical tracking technology is RFID, where localization is performed at middleware level, while GPS is the classical example of positioning system, which uses external infrastructures but performs calculations internally. Some positioning systems can be of either type. For example, WPAN positioning can be performed using RSSI and trilateration methods but such calculations can be performed either autonomously on the device (provided this has the coordinates of the reference points) or externally, generally by a middleware, in order to economize device resources.

In the following we provide a categorization of localization approaches with some examples. A more detailed version can be found in the appendix of this Internal Report.

Implicit localization

- IP Geolocation [247] [324]
 - DNS LOC (*RFC 1876*)
 - IANA Root-Zone Whois Information.
 - IP Geolocation databases [265]
- Network-based localization [270] [236].

Explicit localization

- Signal Strength / Quality
 - Reduced Signal Strength Indicator localization [287], [238]. [294].
 - Link quality indicator (LQI) localization [239].
- Time of arrival (TOA)
 - GPS [338] [317]
- Triangulation [313]

4.2.7 Identity Management

The need for identity management systems has been identified [246] and various frameworks for Identity Management have been developed in the recent years, each of them among other things providing the user with a single sign-on experience and allowing to share the attributes known about the user between the provider of the service and the management site of the identity¹⁵. These authentication features are necessary for a privacy preserving IoT-A, which has to take into account not only services, but also discovery through user devices. In addition, the user's identity has to be federated not only between different services, but also between different IoT networks.

The OASIS SAML work provides a set of messages and protocols for the exchange of assertions regarding the authentication of users and their related attributes, as well as resolution of user names [139]. The messages are encoded as XML and could be digitally signed. The protocols allow various bindings in addition to those standardized [244] for HTTP, proposals utilizing SIP as an underlying protocol have been made [336]. The Shibboleth project [329] is utilizing the SAML protocols with a main focus on the user scenario in University environment. Liberty Alliance [290] has extended the SAML protocol and focuses on a centralized system which forms a so called circle of trust around one identity provider.

In contrast to this centralized approach, OpenID allows a completely decentralized deployment of the identity management services called OpenID provider [305]. It is up to the provider of the service

¹⁵ Each standard is naming these two entities in a different way, eg. Service Provider (SP) and Identity Provider (IdP) for SAML, Relay Party (RP) and OpenID Provider (OP) for OpenID

whether he accepts the OpenID provider regarding the assertion of the user's identity or not. All information is exchanged as attribute value pairs in the HTTP headers, the security completely relies on the protocol level.

The Identity Metasystem with its client software CardSpace provides the user with a convenient and consistent interface which associates user attributes and identities to a specific "card" [293]. This information could be provided by some trusted parties, but the user is enabled to create its own cards with a combination of attributes. A set of web service protocols standardized by OASIS is used to exchange the information.

The Kantara Initiative is taking up the work of Liberty Alliance and is focusing on the harmonization of identity standards as well as on the handling of personal information [284].

These frameworks provide a silo, allowing only authentication and exchanging of information within their realm. Some EU projects are trying to overcome this boundary. In the EU project SWIFT finished in 2010 the bridging functionality between several protocols have been addressed and a generic architecture for identity management framework has been developed [333].

The PrimeLife is an ongoing EU FP7 project focusing on privacy aspects related to individuals using the internet and the related collection and storage of data [308] especially through a new kind of policy language coupled with the related data.

4.3 Public project solutions

4.3.1 SENSEI

- **Short Description:** The SENSEI project is a EU FP7 project on "Integrating the Physical with the Digital World of the Future". It integrates wireless sensor and actuator networks into a common infrastructure based on the concept of a resource, providing a sensor framework and context framework on top of it. The SENSEI architecture is discussed in [280], the communication-related aspects in [281]. Sensors and actuators are modelled as resources that are described as resource descriptions, which are presented in [279]. These resource descriptions are stored in the Resource Directory, where they can be looked up based on a resource identifier, free-form tags, or an RDF-based advanced resource description. In the latter case a SPARQL query can be provided for retrieving fitting resource descriptions. On the context level, the world is models as entities of interest, e.g., persons, places and things that can have attributes describing them. Resources can provide the values of these attributes, e.g. there may be a temperature resource that can provide the indoor temperature of a room. The mappings between entities/attributes and resources are provided as bindings in the Entity Directory.
- **Relevant References:** [321],[323]
- **Relevance:** The Resource Directory and Entity Directory can be compared to the two levels of the Resolution Infrastructure in IoT-A, but specialised on Sensor and Actuator Resources, which are important IoT Resources. The SENSEI approach of Resource and Entity Directory is a highly relevant input for the IoT-A Resolution Infrastructure.

Table 3: Core Relevant Components of the SENSEI Project

Feature	Type	Relation to other WPs	Relevance to IoT-A
Resource Directory Stores resource descriptions that can be looked up based on resource identifiers, free-form tags and advanced resource descriptions. Distribution aspects are only considered as peering between different domains, but no geographical distribution is addressed.	Component	WP1, WP2	Score: ++ Can be used as a basis for building a semantic search engine
Entity Directory Stores bindings between entity/attributes and Resources that provide information about these attributes or allow actuation, i.e., changing the physical status of the entity in the real world. Distribution aspects for the Entity Directory have not been considered.	Component	WP1, WP2	Score: ++ Can be used as a basis for building a semantic search engine

BRIDGE is an extension of the EPC network architecture, which provides for storage and retrieval of filtered and processed information about different events within the supply-chain in RFID networks. In the decentralized EPC system, BRIDGE aims to provide a **secure** lookup service for locating all the providers of the fragments of information that constitute the complete supply-chain or lifecycle history for an object. The key component of BRIDGE relevant to WP4 in IoT-A is the serial-level lookup service and its security aspects. The **core work** completed in BRIDGE is relevant to the IoT-A project since privacy and security is necessary to establish trust in the IoT-A when resolving and identifying resources. The work completed in BRIDGE in looking up information from resources can give insight on similar functions in IoT-A. This project took place between 2006 and 2009 and was developed, prototyped and tested on hardware, software and business levels. Industry adaptation is in progress.

Table 4: Core Relevant Components of the BRIDGE Project

Feature	Type	Relation to other WPs	Relevance to IoT-A
"Synchronous Resources of Information" Discovery Service	Architecture Component	Presents & implements two architecture topologies of a discovery service (WP4), and compares & evaluates them	+ BRIDGE was built only for RFIDs, but interfaces with other IS are defined and thus adaptable to IoT.
Security Strategies in Discovery Service	Architecture Component	Strategies for enhancing security in DS (T4.4) are proposed (ex. ACI & access control techniques, minimal information storage, controlled visibility)	+ Security strategies in DS can be adapted to WP4

4.3.3 SmartProducts

SmartProducts develops the scientific and technological basis for building "smart products" with embedded proactive knowledge. Proactive knowledge encompasses knowledge about the product itself (features, functions, dependencies, usage, etc.), its environment (physical context, other smart products) and its users (preferences, abilities, intentions, etc.). Therefore, smart products "talk", "guide", and "assist" designers, workers and consumers dealing with them.

The SmartProducts project has many aspects that are relevant to IoT-A: the communication between heterogeneous objects is handled by an already-developed code, the MundoCore, which addresses the same problems that IoT-A must solve. The horizontality built into the system is attractive. Much of the implementation is based on open source standards and therefore can be accessed by the public with some additional work. However, exact details on implementation are often kept in references which are not publically available, and the project is work in progress.

Table 5: Core Relevant Components of the SmartProducts Project

Feature	Type	Relation to other WPs	Relevance to IoT-A
Communication Middleware "MundoCore" - enables flexible M2M communication (product-to-product, product-to device, product-to-backend system).	Architecture Component	Handles communication, discovery & routing of resources. However, the link might be stronger to WP3 rather than WP4.	+ MundoCore is open & available. Modifications for IoT-A might be needed.
Contextual Processing – acquire context and react to context for entities, and can also generate higher level context data. Semantic data stored as RDF triplestore, entity reaction to context via rule-based problem solving	Architecture Component	Probabilistic state identification of real world entities. The components in the Contextual Processor are also drawn on semantic technology and concepts that could be used in IoT-A.	+ Uses open standards such as RDF triplestore.

4.3.4 SWIFT

The objectives of the EU FP7 Project SWIFT have been the usage of identities in order to converge between networks, services, application and content across different network layers, as well as the usage of different persona in order to avoid the linkage between some activities of a user. The project

has developed an identity-focused framework, whose main requirements are, overcoming the identity fragmentation, a cross layer identity management and improved privacy features, as well as the support of multiple devices. As shown in Figure 15 three major concepts have been identified in which the identity of the end user is the key to protect the related information and at the same time allow the service provider to deliver innovative services [333].

In addition to the known roles the identity management of the SWIFT framework has been split up into three roles, where the authentication provider asserting the identity of an end user, the attribute provider managing the information related to a specific identity and the identity aggregator coordinating the activities and manages the different user profiles. These are identified through a so-called virtual identity **VID**, known by the authentication provider under several **Authentication ID**. The related information could be queried through **Attribute ID** by the end user. Different pseudonyms are used between the other roles to refer to these IDs but make them untraceable at the same time.

Figure 14: SWIFT Concepts and Roles

Figure 15: Roles of the SWIFT Framework and their relationship between identifiers

Table 6: Core Relevant Architectures of the SWIFT Project

Feature	Type	Relation to other WPs	Relevance to IoT-A
Framework for Identity Brokerage, Authentication and Attribute Management	Architecture, Prototype based on SAML and OpenID	WP2	Relevance score: + Architecture should be used as basis for Service Architecture, Prototype Implementation could be made available for demos
Distributed Authorization Framework	Architecture, Prototype	WP2	Relevance score: + Extensions for IoT-A possible
Resolution of Attributes	Architecture	WP 1	Relevance score: 0 Resolution Framework could be utilized

4.4 Commercial usage

4.4.1 QR Code

The Quick Response (QR) code is a 2 Dimension bar code created by Denso-Wave in 1994 and was at first mostly popular in Japan. QR codes were first used by Toyota to track part of vehicles. They are mostly known for the possibility they provide to transmit a message that can be recognized by camera equipped devices like smart phone. Since the content of a QR code can be any kind of string, they are commonly used to transmit a URL to a device. Therefore, a smartphone user can visit the webpage encoded by the QR code instead of typing the URL in its browser. Smartphone applications can directly interpret the content of a QR code and render it over the picture captured by the camera. QR code error correction rate ranges from 7% to 30% depending on the chosen encoding level.

QR code composition: A QR code is composed of three position detection patterns that are placed at corners and used to determine the QR-code position. A timing pattern links the three detection patterns and is used to determine the coordinates inside the code. Format information is placed around the upper-left corner pattern.

Relevance: IoT-A should consider printable codes to store ID of unconnected objects. Among the printable 2D-codes, QR-Codes is the most adopted solution, thus guaranteeing a large base of

compliant devices. Furthermore, QR-codes have a higher capacity than other 2D-code technologies [59] and therefore should be preferred to these other technologies.

4.4.2 Digital Object Identifier

The Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is an Internet based global naming and resolution system. Although it can be used to identify any kind of Intellectual Property representation, DOI is currently mostly used to identify and retrieve publications (e.g. Journal, Papers, and Books).

Unlike URLs that are identifiers reflecting a resource location, DOIs are location independent and are well adapted to identify resources that are mobile or duplicated in multiple places.

A DOI is composed of prefix that identifies the resource publisher and a suffix (specified by the publisher) that identifies the resource within the prefix-holder hierarchy. The granularity of the suffix (journal, book, article, chapter...) is decided by the prefix holder. DOI is based on a central repository that is queried to retrieve a resource location. To update the location of a resource, the owner only has to update the corresponding entry in this repository. Since no meaning can be inferred from the identifier, metadata are attached to the resource to help the user ensuring that he has retrieved the expected resource.

Relevance: DOI is mostly used to reference articles and books. Although it is only used to identify a specific category of things (books, papers and journals), DOI comes with some principles that may be of interest for IoT-A. Notably, the “Handle System” designed to support multiple protocols and allowing therefore the implementation of more suitable processes than the current DOI system; “Multiple resolution” allowing several values to be returned back from a resolution request, enabling then the requester to select the appropriate value according to its context of use. “Metadata” refining object description an allowing objects with common behaviour to be inferred and grouped using “DOI Application profiles”.

4.5 Standardisation activities

4.5.1 GS1 EPCglobal

GS1 EPCglobal is a subsidiary of the international not-for-profit association GS1 which provides the GS1 System (see Figure 16, [267]). The GS1 keys are incorporated into GS1 Data Carriers which, in turn, interact with the Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) by using the GS1 Communication Standards.

Figure 16: The GS1 System

The focus of GS1 EPCglobal is leading the development of the RFID technology, thus it is responsible for the worldwide adoption and standardization of the EPC (Electronic Product Code) technology. On the one hand the GS1 EPC serves to identify each unique EPC/RFID tag and on the other hand it enables the use of the EPC Information Service (EPCIS) of the GS1 Communication Standards. As part of the EPC Network Architecture the EPCIS was developed to ensure EPC-related data sharing with partners along the supply chain. At first tag data is read by an EPC reader which conveys the information to the middleware layer (e.g. Fosstrak ALE Middleware). This in turn is responsible for the filtering and aggregation process of the collected raw data and is supported by the Application Level Events (ALE) interface which hides the RFID infrastructure's details from the client applications [335]. The EPCIS closes the gap between physical objects and business systems. Therefore there are the Object Name Service (ONS) and the EPC Discovery Service as supporting services. Similarly to the Domain Name System the ONS is a lookup service to get a reference to an EPCIS service associated with an EPC [268]. In a multi-party supply chain where data about a specific item might be stored

among many partners, the EPC Discovery Service acts as a registry of all involved EPCIS which contain information about the respective item [334].

From IoT-A perspective the GS1 EPCglobal standardisation activities are important because they are closely related to RFID and this identification technology, in turn, is always mentioned in the context of the IoT.

4.5.2 uID Center

uCode is a 128-bit fixed length identifier that can be assigned to different kinds of resources (object, place, content, concept). A uCode can be allocated to a relationship between objects (logical uCode). The uCode number is not derived from the resource that it identifies and part of it is set arbitrarily (see Figure 17, [339]).

uCode Allocation

There are two levels in the uCode allocation hierarchy. Top Level Domain (TLD) management organization assigns the SLD code and the Identification code while Second Level Domain (SLD) organization manages only the Identification code. A SLD eventually provides other organization with a sub-space of the Identification Code allowing these entities to sub-allocate uCode. The uCode status changes from 'allocated' to 'issued' when it is registered in the uCode resolution server managed by the allocating entity.

uCode Resolution

In order to retrieve the resource corresponding to an uCode, a user should query the uCode decentralised database that will find the entry corresponding to the item.

Figure 17: uCode decomposition

Relevance: uCode is designed to identify and resolve objects, places and content. This technology does not depend on application fields or business types and allocates a unique identifier for any objects. Finally, it is driven by uIDCenter, an important actor in the field of ubiquitous computing. Therefore, uCode should really be considered in the IoT-A project, either as an identification method or through bridging functions passing from uIDCenter to the future IoT-A identification scheme and vice versa.

4.5.3 Automotive

The Car to Car Communication Consortium (**C2C-CC**) [245] aims at providing means to improve road safety by defining vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communications mechanisms. Originally initiated by European vehicle manufacturers, it is now open to other partners. In the overall architecture defined in C2C-CC, multiple Road Side Units (RSUs) are deployed along roadsides. These devices communicate and act as gateway for vehicular On Board Units (OBUs). Only one OBU is featured within a vehicle. On the other hand, multiple Application Units (AUs) exist within the car, that communicate using dedicated technology (e.g. short-range wireless) with their serving OBU. C2C-CC requires that the AU be an IPv6 node.

Vehicle identifiers – as per the locator-identifier split paradigm – are therefore IPv6 addresses that are owned by the vehicles' OBUs. Yet, routing does not require that the OBU has been explicitly resolved. In order to be more flexible, it is enhanced to enable geographical routing, which allows a sender's application to issue a message targeting recipients located in a certain geographical area, identified with a set of coordinates and optionally a minimal information relevance radius.

ISO TC204 WG16 [242] is drafting a series of standards under the acronym **CALM** (Continuous communications Air interface for Long and Medium range). The objective of this standard is to provide architecture and a set of protocols for vehicle-roadside communications that separate applications

from the communication media. A wide selection of media is covered, and a basic network protocol (IPv6) is used together with a comprehensive management stack [242], [243].

With the use of the NEMO protocol, a vehicle is assigned a (long-term) network prefix that uniquely identifies it and allows it to assign a globally routable IPv6 address to all devices it contains. Reaching these devices by a distant peer relies on the classical Internet mechanisms, namely DNS resolution in the home domain. In addition to standard Internet applications, CALM also support specific critical ITS applications through CALM FAST, which also defines geographical routing. With its Facilities framework, CALM defines a simple solution for interfacing applications with the networking stack. Facilities especially a Local Dynamic Map referencing "all dynamic objects that are directly sensed or indicated by other road users by means of cooperative awareness messages" [261] and allowing to issues spatial queries so as to determine object dependencies and relationships.

Another set of standards for vehicle to infrastructure communications is **WAVE** (Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments), which relies on a modified 802.11(p) MAC/PHY layer, on top of which both IP and non-IP applications can be carried.

More precisely, IEEE1609.1 defines the resources management part, IEEE1609.2 defines the WAVE security architecture and services, IEEE1609.3 defines WAVE networking services and IEEE1609.4 defines WAVE multi-channel operations. IEEE1609.1 defines how multiple applications can register to a roadside resource manager and use it to access onboard equipment, after this latter has explicitly agreed to access the offered service at resource manager.

4.5.4 Pharma

Considering identification and coding standards in the European pharmaceutical sector there is a lack of harmonization recognizable (see Figure 18, [258]). In some cases the particular national standards exist in parallel to the GTIN (e.g. German Pharmazentralnummer) but are not the prior identification numbers.

Figure 18: National Coding Systems throughout Europe

To solve this issue, the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA) made an approach for a standardized coding and identification system for pharmaceuticals in Europe consistent with existing international standards (GS1 EAN). The main objective of harmonizing is an increased patient safety. For this purpose a end-to-end product verification was proposed by the EFPIA based on the 2D data matrix ECC-200 although RFID would fit as well [258], but due to various issues, such as security and privacy, it has been rejected. Concerning business impacts, i.e. supply chain transparency, this decision affects the positive side effect since RFID without the need of a line of sight is nearly the perfect solution for a fast and transparent supply chain. Thus, the possibility of

tracking and tracing of pharmaceutical products gives a greater protection against fraud and counterfeiting [283].

Today the threat of counterfeit drugs already exists and will increase in the future if there won't be any countermeasure. For this reason IoT-A must consider this issue regardless of any technology and provide an identification system which enables a pharmaceutical pedigree in order to protect the society from possible harmful or inoperative counterfeit drugs.

4.5.5 Telecom Number and Identification

There are several ways to identify a specific resource through the operator network. This depends mainly on the type of network that we are using. For public switched telephone network (PSTN), the operator has the possibility to identify uniquely the resource with the E.163 [255]/E.164 [256] addresses (more commonly known as telephone numbers). For GSM, WCDMA, and iDEN mobile phones, the operator uses International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI) conforming to the 3GPP TS 22.016 5, which is associated to the mobile equipment, and the user through the International Mobile Subscriber Identifier (IMSI) conforming to the recommendation ITU-T E.212 [257] stored in the SIM card and often used as a key in the HLR ("subscriber database"). Besides it, operators provide the Mobile Subscriber ISDN Number (MSISDN) following the ITU-T recommendation E.164. This unique number is used for routing calls to the operator network and identifies a subscription in a GSM or a UMTS mobile network (PSTN).

For circuit switched networks, some network functions as Signalling Point Codes (SPC) are used to address networks, e.g. ITU-T Signalling System No.7 (SS7) [309]. In the international signalling network, some of the signalling point codes (ISPCs) are used according to ITU-T Q.708 [310] recommendation. Moreover, if we are using packet switched networks like the Internet and other IP based networks, identifiers are names used in the form of Domain Names according to RFC 1035 [295].

Additionally, we can have the possibility of have an IP Multimedia Subsystem, better known as "IMS", which is an architecture for the convergence of data, speech and mobile networks and is based on a wide range of protocols developed by the IETF [307]. In this subsystem, the identity of the user is managed through the definition of public and private user identity. The concepts of Private User Identity (IMPI) and Public User Identity (IMPU) are introduced in 3GPP TS 23.228 [232] and 3GPP TS 23.003 [231] specification. The IMPU, IMPI and home domain are derived from IMSI, being suitable for those devices that have a Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) Application.

Last, but not least, included within the IMS world, we have to mention the Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) [315], which is the core of the IMS and can be seen as an application layer protocol continuously standardized by the IETF. SIP protocol defines a group of messages to exchange the information about the session signalling. These messages are compound by three components: a method name, a request-URI and the protocol version. The request-URI is a SIP [275] or a SIPS URI [315] that identifies a resource to which the request is addressed. But the identification of the resource can be done also with the utilization of a telephone URI (TEL URI) [320] which allows the use of a phone number as identification in the SIP message.

4.5.6 ETSI TC M2M

An overview of the group is presented in section 1.3.1. The architecture that is being defined is intended to facilitate the development of vertical applications using a horizontal platform. Providing shared memory blocks, named Resources and modelled following the REST approach, applications can exchange information. The content of the information is not standardized and could contain things like measurements, sensor descriptions, etc. These resources contain metadata (modelled as attributes) to keep information like the policies, modified times, etc.

The platform provide means of discovering resources by applying string pattern matching techniques on an special attribute of the resource called SearchStrings, that is quite relevant for IoT-A. Resources can be located using URLs that follow a standardized structure, that allows to reach the resource in the machine (either server or device) wherever it is. The identification of resources is not still specified, however there is work progressing that should be considered in the future.

An important part of the M2M ecosystem is the devices, where a huge number of them are expected, and, consequently, managing them is a challenge. For that, the ETSI M2M will rely on two existing standards, the OMA Device Management [306], for managing wireless devices, and the Broadband Forum TR-069 [241] for wired devices; both commonly used in the Telco world.

Another important feature the current standard is defining are the groups. The platform allows to group resources so regular operations can be performed on all the resources that belong to the group (like for example executing an action on all of them). The current definition just envisions the interaction with a set of static elements belonging to the group; however, for the future, it is envisioned to extend the group concept to handle dynamic groups, where the members of groups can appear and

disappear. For example, a group could be defined as the sensors in a particular spatial area. This grouping schema is also relevant for IoT-A.

4.5.7 OGC® SWE (Sensor Web Enablement)

The architecture and data models defined by this group have already been reviewed in sections 1.3.4 and 2.4.3.4 respectively.

From a functional point of view, the set of standards define how to request and publish information; support for notification and support to request the execution of tasks (like for example call an actuator). They are provided by a set of services, the SOS, SAS and SPS as defined in section [280]. For example, a service implementing the SOS [304] interface represents an Information Provider and the system might have several ones. In order to discover the different existing services the OGC defines a Catalogue Service [302]. Considering that an SOS service will probably provide access to the descriptions and measurements coming from multiple IoT resources, and taking also into account that the Catalogue does not contain the metadata of a single IoT resource, the discovery of IoT resources is a two-step approach: In the first one we discover the SOS service that can provide the information about the IoT and in the second step we access directly the service to get the detailed metadata.

The OGC does not define any particular identification schema, but the SensorML [303] supports multiple IDs. The OGC does not consider either the concept of a resolution infrastructure able to provide associations between Eol and resources; however, in the SensorML description it provides a field (featureofInterest) intended to associate IoT resources to externally defined Eol.

The SOS service encapsulates in a homogeneous way sensor and data repositories. It is also used to provide both the resource descriptions and the data provided by them. The integration of both, metadata and data into a single service might cause scalability problems.

4.5.8 ISO/IEC JTC1 WG7 (Working Group on Sensor Networks)

The architectural vision of this group has been reviewed in section 1.3.3. However, the work in this group has not yet evolved enough for generating any precise information that can be useful from a WP4 perspective. In any case, since it is envisioned that some of their work might impact IoT-A, the project needs to monitor their activity.

4.5.9 Domain Name System

The Domain Name System (DNS) enables networks on the Internet to use globally unique names. This creates a "human" environment, where people can use easy-to-remember names for things like web pages and mailboxes, rather than long numbers or codes. A less obvious, but equally important benefit is that DNS allows names to be separated from locations. Services and devices can move to a totally different network location, without the need for a name change.

The Internet maintains two principal namespaces, the domain name hierarchy and the Internet Protocol (IP) address system. The Domain Name System maintains the domain namespace and provides translation services between these two namespaces. Internet name servers and a communication protocols implement the Domain Name System. A DNS name server is a server that stores the DNS records for a domain name, such as address (A) records, name server (NS) records, and mail exchanger (MX) records; a DNS name server responds with answers to queries against its database.

The Domain Name System is maintained by a distributed database system, which uses the client-server model. Each domain has at least one authoritative DNS server that publishes information about that domain and the name servers of any domains subordinate to it. The top of the hierarchy is served by the root name servers.

Since the Internet of Things will be integrated in the existing Internet, compatibility of the name resolution mechanisms of the Internet and Internet of Things must be taken into account in the IoT-A architecture.

Additionally, several extensions to DNS have been developed over the years of which DNS-SD or dynamic DNS in general might be worth looking at into detail for the name resolution of devices in an Internet of Things context.

DNS based Service Discovery (DNS-SD) uses DNS SRV, TXT, and PTR records to advertise Service Instance Names. The hosts offering services publish details of available services.. Service types are given informally on a first-come basis. A service type registry is maintained and published by DNS-SD.org [254].

A mechanism based on DNS-SD can be used to discover the presence and properties of devices. It can also be used to find out which services are available in the system.

The use of a discovery mechanism has the advantage that applications can dynamically bind to devices and services at runtime. All parameters and properties needed for exchanging messages are published and maintained by the devices and services that are active.

5. State of the Art on IoT Objects Platforms

5.1 Introduction and SOTA approach

This section contains the state of the art review on communication technologies for embedded objects, and its aim is to provide a thorough and updated list of existing hardware, software solutions, physical layer technologies and so forth. This list will be used to make a selection of the most suitable technologies (both in terms of hardware and software) that shall be used to build the WP5 IoT-A demonstrators. The review is subdivided into four macro-sections.

- The first section deals with **hardware modules and physical layer technologies (PHY)**. For the hardware, we focused on the most widespread CPUs and radio chips for embedded and resource constrained communicating objects. In addition to that, we also reviewed the most commonly used transmission systems at the PHY layer, including ZigBee, Bluetooth, Bluetooth-Low Energy, Z-Wave, UWB technology, etc.
- The second section deals with **commercial control network technologies**, that are used to connect objects through specialized communication channels of some kind. In our review we focused on Lonworks, KNX and CAN technologies as these find a large application in the industrial arena.
- The third section reviews existing **operating systems for embedded and resource constrained objects**, underlying design principles, pros and cons of existing solutions and also giving guidelines for future developments within the IOTA project.
- The focus of the fourth and **last section is on security aspects**. Here we first discuss a few general principles about security and in particular privacy, discussing pros and cons of communication architectures. We thus delve into the analysis of physical layer security issues, taking RFID tags as the target technology for our review.

5.2 Technologies

5.2.1 Wireless Sensors Networks

Hereafter we summarize the most widespread technologies used within the Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) domain. We start by describing the most popular microcontrollers and radio chips by subsequently reviewing the most prominent wireless technologies (modulation, coding, etc.) that can be adopted for communication across devices.

5.2.1.1 CC2420 Radio Chip

The CC2420[230] is a single-chip radio-transceiver from Texas Instruments compliant to IEEE 802.15.4. It provides MAC support and is designed for low power and low voltage wireless applications, finding wide use into commercial products for building/home automation, ZigBee systems and wireless sensing in general. CC2420 includes a digital direct sequence spread spectrum baseband modem providing a spreading gain of 9 dB and an effective data rate of 250 kbps. The CC2420 is a low-cost, highly integrated solution for robust wireless communication in the 2.4 GHz unlicensed ISM band. It complies with worldwide regulations. The CC2420 implements the PHY IEEE802.15.4 standard, adopting CSMA for the channel access and performing a clear channel assessment (CCA) before transmitting. If the channel is not clear, the radio backs off for some short, random period of time before attempting to transmit again. Amongst its main features, it has a Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum (DSSS) baseband modem with 2 MChips/s and 250 kbps effective data rate, low power consumption, programmable output power, 128 (transmission) + 128 (reception) bytes of data buffering capabilities, digital RSSI (Radio Signal Strength Indicator) and LQI (Link Quality Indicator) support, hardware AES encryption and battery monitor.

The CC2420 radio chip can still be found in many sensor network architectures even though newer system on chip solutions (described below) are now available; these generally have lower energy consumption and more advanced features such as larger FLASH and RAM memories, faster transition times between power states, etc.

5.2.1.2 CC2430 System on Chip Radio

The CC2430 is a System-on-Chip (SoC) solution from Texas Instruments with more advanced features with respect to its predecessor and with lower energy consumption. It is IEEE 802.15.4 compliant as the CC2420 but it has a very low energy consumption, which is of just 0.5 mA in power down mode and of 0.3 mA in stand-by mode. In addition, it has very fast transition times from low-power modes to active mode, which allows for reduced energy consumption when the radio is duty cycled (which is commonly the case for modern WSN applications). It features a low power 8051

microcontroller core with 32,64 or 128 kbytes of in-system programmable FLASH memory, 8 kbytes of RAM, it has several timers (two 16-bit and one 8-bit), DMA functionality a 12-bit ADC with eight inputs and configurable resolution and an AES security co-processor. It provides RSSI/LQI support and full CSMA/CA support for the MAC functionalities.

5.2.1.3 CC2530 System on Chip Radio

The CC2530[349] is a SoC solution from Texas Instruments for IEEE 802.15.4. It is a further evolution of the CC2430 (it has many functionalities in common with CC2430 but more FLASH memory, which is useful for modern applications and full ZigBee support). As the CC2430, it has a 8051 microcontroller core with 32, 64, 128 or 256 kbytes of programmable FLASH memory and 8 kbytes of RAM. It provides many advanced features such as very low power consumption, variable output power, a five channel DMA, 12-bit ADC with eight inputs and configurable resolution and an AES security co-processor and full CSMA/CA hardware support.

5.2.1.4 MSP430 F54xx (Texas Instruments) MicroController

The Texas Instruments MSP430 family [350] provides ultralow-power microcontrollers with several devices and peripherals targeted for various applications. These microcontrollers feature five different power modes and are optimized to achieve extended battery life in portable applications. The MSP430 has a 16-bit RISC CPU, 16-bit registers and constant generators. In addition, a digitally controlled oscillator allows the microcontroller to wake-up from low-power modes to active mode in less than 5 ms. The MSP430F543x and MSP430F541x series are microcontroller configurations with three 16-bit timers, a high performance 12-bit analog-to-digital (A/D) converter, up to four universal serial communication interfaces (USCI), hardware multiplier, DMA, real-time clock module with alarm capabilities, and up to 87 I/O pins. The capacity of on board FLASH and RAM memories are 48 kbytes and 10 kbytes, respectfully, and the clock is 1 MHz.

The MSP430 microcontrollers have been and are currently being used extensively into commercial as well as experimental (i.e., for the scientific research market) products. Examples are the Crossbow TelosB sensor nodes as well as boards from Sensinode.

5.2.1.5 Atmel Radios – AT86RF2xx

Popular radios from Atmel [351] are the AT86RF212 for the sub-1GHz frequency bands and the AT86RF231 for the 2.4 GHz ISM band.

AT86RF212: it is a low power, low-voltage radio transceiver that operates in the 700/800/900 MHz and is designed to be compliant with the IEEE 802.15.4 PHY standard, 6LoWPAN and ZigBee. It implements direct sequence spread spectrum with different modulation schemes and data rates: low data rates of 20 and 40 kbit/s (BPSK modulation) are provided as defined in the IEEE 802.15.4-2003/2006 standards [352][353], whereas additional rates of 100 and 250 kbit/s (O-PSK modulation) are defined in the 802.15.4-2006 standard and its amendment IEEE 802.15.4c-2009 [354]. Lastly, proprietary data modes allowing rates up to 1000 kbit/s can be employed. This radio has a low energy consumption, specifically being of 2 mA in the SLEEP mode, 17 mA in TX mode (with a transmission power of 5 dBm), of 9.2 mA during reception of data, and 0.4 mA when idle. The radio chip has hardware acceleration of the following actions: 1) automatic acknowledgment and retransmission, 2) CSMA-CA and listen before talk as well as 3) automatic frame filtering. Among other features it provides AES 128-bit hardware acceleration (providing ECB and CBC modes), true random number generation for security support and programmable transmission power up to 10 dBm.

AT86RF231: the features provided by this radio chip are entirely similar to those provided by the AT86RF212 model except that this radio operates in the 2.4 GHz ISM band.

5.2.1.6 AtmelMicroControllers

Atmel [351] produces various series of microcontrollers addressing the manufacturing industry, home automation, auto-motive, etc. The series that are most suitable for wireless sensor nodes, home automation and energy metering are: 1) the ATmega series and 2) the ATxmega series. Microprocessors of the ATmega series have program memory (ROM) ranging from 4 to 256 kbytes, whereas the ATxmega series provides microprocessors with 16-384 kbytes of ROM and extended features such as DMA and cryptography support.

ATxmega products [355] are most promising for future WSN boards due to their advanced features as well as their reduced energy consumption. They operate from 1.6V to 3.6V and achieve up to 32 MIPS (Million Instructions Per Second) at 32 MHz. They use a second generation pico-Power technology which allows a power consumption as low as 1 mA. Moreover, true 1.6 V operation allows the microprocessors to perform all functions at this voltage (including FLASH reprogramming, note that the MSP430 family require more than 2.3 V to assure reliable reprogramming of FLASH memories). In Power Down mode with RAM retention, the current consumption is 100 nA. The ATxmegaADC has 12-bit resolution and provides up to 2 million samples per second with hardware support for

oversampling. ATxmega products also include 12-bit DACs and advanced analog comparators. Finally, they provide a hardware crypto engine that supports the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). This new generation of Atmel microcontrollers is superior in performance with respect to TI MSP430 especially in terms of amount of internal memory, clock speed and encryption routines implemented in hardware.

These microcontrollers are very popular and have been used in different sensor platforms. We cite here the sensor nodes from Berkeley: René and dot nodes adopt an ATmega163 (having 16 kbytes of ROM and 1 kbyte of RAM), Mica and MicaDot exploit the ATmega128 (having 128 kbytes of ROM and 4 kbytes of RAM). In addition, the RAVEN kit supports wireless development using Atmel's IEEE 802.15.4 chipsets, for ZigBee and other wireless stacks. The kit includes two AVR Raven boards, each with 2.4 GHz transceiver supporting IEEE 802.15.4 (and a freely licensed ZigBee stack). The radios are driven with ATmega1284p processors, which are supported by a custom segmented LCD display driven by an ATmega3290p processor.

5.2.1.7 ZigBee Physical (PHY) interface

The ZigBee Alliance [356] has developed a very low-cost, low-power consumption, two-way wireless communications standard. Solutions adopting the ZigBee standard are being embedded in consumer electronics, home and building automation, industrial controls, PC peripherals, medical sensor applications, toys, and games. The ZigBee is a complete protocol stack from the physical (PHY) layer up to the application (APP) protocol. At the PHY, ZigBee adopts the IEEE 802.15.4 [357] wireless technology, which we describe next. The IEEE 802.15.4 technology is designed for short-range communication systems with relaxed throughput and delay requirements. Its key features are: low complexity, low to medium range communication, low power consumption and low cost. Currently, the IEEE 802.15.4 technology is the preferred technology for the Medium Access (MAC) and the Physical layer of the ZigBee protocol stack. It is also the most commonly adopted standard for the radio communication part of many commercial products in the wireless sensor network domain. The IEEE 802.15.4 physical layer operates using the three following unlicensed bands: 1) 868 [MHz]: here a single channel with data rate of 20 Kbps is available. The required sensitivity at the receiver is -92 dBm and ideal transmission range of 1 Km; 2) 915 [MHz]: this band hosts ten channels with data rate of 40 Kbps; receiver sensitivity and transmission ranges are the same as for the previous band; 3) 2.4 [GHz] ISM band: this band offers 16 channels with data rate of 250 Kbps. The receiver sensitivity is -85 dBm and the ideal transmission range is 220 meters. Ideal transmission ranges are obtained considering a transmission power of -3 dBm. A duty cycle can be exploited at the physical layer to put the radio to sleep for most of the time. IEEE 802.15.4-compliant radios allow devices to work even when the radio is inactive for up to 99% of the time. The spread spectrum technology is used at the transmitter to spread the signal over a larger bandwidth prior to its transmission over the channel; this is done using a known pseudo-random sequence that is then used at the receiver to demodulate the signal. Spread spectrum allows for more resilience against environmental noise (interference or signal distortion due to multi-path propagation, especially indoors).

5.2.1.8 Bluetooth physical interface

The Bluetooth physical layer technology [358] is intended to replace cables in Personal Area Networks (PANs) and Body Area Networks (BANs). Its key features are: low range communication, low power and low cost. Originally, this technology was designed and standardized by the Bluetooth Special Interest Group, which was created by Ericsson, Intel, Toshiba Corporation, Nokia Corporation and IBM. The first specification of this technology was released in 1999. The Bluetooth physical layer operates in the unlicensed ISM band (2.4 GHz). It provides 79 channels ($f=2402+k$ MHz, with $k=0, \dots, 78$), each 1 MHz wide. In the base (and most used) transmission mode, referred to as point-to-point, the Bluetooth technology manages the transmission within the nodes of a single hop network, where a master unit orchestrates the transmission to and from a number of slaves according to a polling channel access scheme. The time is slotted according to a TDMA frame and at each time slot either the master or one of the slaves can transmit. In each transmission slot a particular frequency is selected according to a frequency hopping technique (which uses a pseudo-random sequence for the frequency selection at both master and slaves) with a nominal hop rate of 1600 hops/s. Frequency hopping allows for interference reduction (in the face of other master-slave pairs transmitting in the same geographical area) as well as resilience against multi-path fading phenomena.

The point-to-point transmission mode is the most used in the commercial products available on the market. Nodes can also be organized in so called "piconets", which connect multiple point-to-point networks. However, this second transmission strategy, due to complexity and stability reasons is less common. The Bluetooth technology is rarely used for WSN applications due to its limitations in single as well as multi-hop networks. In the former case, the number of slaves is in fact limited whereas in the latter mesh and tree topologies are hard to obtain and require substantial energy consumption for

the coordination of nodes (in particular for their time/frequency synchronization). Overall, this limits the usability of this technology for single as well as multi-hop networks with medium and dense deployments.

5.2.1.9 Bluetooth Low Energy (LE) Technology

This is an ultra-low power Bluetooth technology [359] whose development started with the EU FP6 project MIMOSA. The technology was released in 2006 under the name “Wibree” and is a simplified version of Bluetooth. This transmission technology is up to 15 times more efficient than Bluetooth and achieves these gains by optimizing: 1) the way nodes are discovered and connected to an existing point-to-point link, 2) the number of packets transmitted during the connections and 3) the size of the data packets transmitted. In Wibree only three channels are used for advertising (when a device needs to connect to an existing network) against the 32 channels that are used by Bluetooth and this leads to discovery processes that are up to 17 times more efficient. Other major differences reside: 1) in the data modulation, 2) in the number of channels used for transmission (that are fewer with respect to Bluetooth) and 3) in a more aggressive sleeping behaviour of the devices when they do not have data to send. This technology does not support multi-hop or mesh topologies unlike ZigBee and Z-Wave. Development of this technology is currently under way: Texas Instruments [360] and Nordic Semiconductor [361] are in fact developing Bluetooth LE-compliant devices but products cannot be found on the market yet.

5.2.1.10 Ultra-Wide Bandwidth (UWB) Technology

Ultra-Wide Bandwidth [362] is a fast emerging technology in the WSN domain. These systems transmit signals across a much larger frequency than conventional systems: the amount of spectrum occupied by such signals is at least 25% of its carrier frequency. The most common technique to generate such signals is to transmit pulses with durations less than 1 ns. This technique is also referred to as Impulse Radio-UWB and is as well the most promising for WSN applications. The IR-UWB technique has been selected as the physical layer of the IEEE 802.15.4a task group [363] for WPAN Low Rate Alternative PHY. In addition to the PHY techniques specified by 802.15.4-2006, the IEEE 802.15.4a standard specifies two additional PHYs using ultra wideband (UWB PHY) and chirp spread spectrum (CSS). The UWB PHY is designated frequencies in three ranges: below 1 GHz, between 3 and 5 GHz, and between 6 and 10 GHz. The CSS PHY is designated to the 2450 MHz ISM band. UWB PHY in addition to communication capabilities will allow for high precision ranging of devices.

5.2.1.11 Z-Wave

Z-Wave [364] is proprietary wireless technology developed by the Danish company Zensys, which has been standardized by the Z-Wave Alliance. This technology is specifically designed for remote control applications. Unlike 802.11-based Wireless LANs, this technology is designed to operate in the sub Gigahertz frequency range and has been optimized for short commands such as on-off, control of thermostats and transmission of medical data (health-care applications). Due to the operation in the 900 MHz frequency bands, this technology is largely unaffected by interference from commonly used (and crowded) 802.11 bands in the 2.4 GHz frequency. Note that the band adopted by Z-Wave is subject to European regulations to operate with duty cycles of 1% or smaller. However, such duty cycles can suffice for most home-control applications. The technology supports mesh topologies allowing a maximum of 232 nodes in the networks and transmission rates of 9.6 Kbps and 40 Kbps. The Z-Wave radio transceiver allows the reliable communication of devices placed 100 meters apart. The radio standard is closed and available to Z-Wave customers under non-disclosure agreement. Many companies, due to its low cost and good performance, are currently adopting this standard.

5.2.2 RFID/NFC

5.2.2.1 Introduction

The term of RFID encompasses different kinds of technologies. They can be distinguished by their capability of reading distance and the induced applications. On one hand, proximity cards also known as contactless smartcards can only be read from less than 10 cm and follows the ISO 14443 standard and is also the basis of the NFC standard. This reading distance enables them to offer a large range of possibilities of computation resources required for example to implement cryptographic protocols for security purpose.

On the other hand, we find RFID tags or vicinity tags dedicated to identification of objects with reading distance which can reach 7 to 8 meters. Due to high constraints of cost (0.10€ per tag is targeted), their capabilities are reduced and their chip is only a wired logic without microprocessor. These tags can work with an important variety of frequency: 135 kHz, 13.56 MHz, 433 MHz, 860 to 950 MHz, 2.45 GHz and 5.8 GHz. ISO 18000 standard describes the features of these tags for each carrier frequency.

EPC Class 1 generation 2 UHF RFID tags has been introduced in the ISO 18000-6 (860 to 950 MHz band) by the EPCGlobal2 consortium and is being introduced in ISO18000-3 (13.56 MHz band).

A standard even if it can be named RFID tag is between contactless smartcards and RFID tags: this is the ISO 15693 which operates in the 13.56 MHz band with a reading distance around 1 meter and a tag format which is identical to a smartcard. Its application is mainly identification of person like access control or transport ticketing for example.

5.2.2.1.1 Specificity of RFID (principle of functioning)

The specificity of RFID tags or contactless smartcards is that they can be totally passive with no source of energy on board. Even if active RFID tags can be found, this technology has been designed to be passive. The system requires a reader which emits a carrier frequency to power the card. In the 125 kHz or 13.56 MHz band, the reader can be seen as the primary of a transformer and the card as the secondary. The two coils are not coupled with a ferrite core but via the air. As a consequence the coupling factor is bad but enough to see the carrier frequency at the two terminals of the card antenna. This signal is then rectified to power the card. A simple amplitude modulation of the signal sent by the reader enables the communication from the reader to the tag. To answer, the card modulates the field emitted by the reader with the switching of a load at the two terminals of its antenna: this is a passive load modulation. The principle is the same in higher bands except that the handled field is no longer magnetic but electrical. The card to answer modifies the load of its antenna to change its back propagation features.

The NFC technology is based on the ISO 14443 standard with the possibility for the device (a NFC phone for example) to switch from a mode where it emulates an RFID reader and a mode where it emulates a contactless card. As a consequence, peer to peer communication becomes possible.

Figure 19 NFC working principle.

5.2.2.1.2 Features of the technologies

Contactless smartcards

ISO	reading distan	consumption		Forward link				Return link			
				Carrier freq.	Modulation	Coding	Data rate	subcarrier fre	Modulation	Coding	Data rate
10536	10 cm	10 mW		4.9412 MHz	4 PSK	NRZ	9.6 kbps	307 kHz	BPSK	NRZ	9.6 kbps
14443	10 cm	10 mW	Type A	13.56 MHz	ASK 100%	Mod. Miller	106 - 847 kb	847 kHz	ASK	Manchester	106 - 847kbp
	10 cm	10 mW	Type B		ASK 10%	NRZ			BPSK	NRZ	
15693	1 m	0.1 mW	Low	13.56 MHz	ASK 10 - 100%	1/256 PPM	1.65 kbps	423 kHz or	ASK or FSK	Manchester	6.62 kbps
	1 m	0.1 mW	Fast			1/4 PPM	26.5 kbps	423-485 kHz			26.5 kbps

RFID tags

ISO	Reading distance/consumption			Forward link				Return link			
				Carrier freq.	Modulation	Coding	Data rate	subcarrier freq.	Modulation	Coding	Data rate
18000-2	2 m	0.1 mW	Type A FDX	125 kHz	ASK 100%	PIE	5.1 kbps		LSK	Man. Or Dual	4 or 2 kbps
	2 m	0.1 mW	Type B HDX	134 kHz	ASK 100%	PIE	1.3 or 2.3 kbps	124.2 & 134.2	FM	NRZ	8 kbps
18000-3	1 m	0.1 mW	Mode 1	13.56 MHz	ASK 10% 10	PPM 1/4 or 1	26.5 or 1.65	Low 423 kHz	LSK	Manchester	6.62 or 26.48
	1 m	0.1 mW						Fast 423-484	LSK	Manchester	6.67 or 26.69
	1 m	0.1 mW	Mode 2	13.56 MHz	PJM	MFM	473.75 kbps	8 sub carriers	LSK	MFM	106 kbps
18000-4	2 m	0.1 mW	Mode 1	2.45GHz	ASK 99%	Manchester	40 kbps		Backscatter	FM0	40 kbps
	2 m	0.1 mW	Mode 2	2.45 GHz	GMSK		384 kbps	384 kHz	DBPSK	Manchester	384 kbps
18000-6	10 m	0.05 mW	Type A	860-930 MHz	ASK 30%	PIE	33 kbps		Backscatter	FM0	40 kbps
	10 m	0.05 mW	Type B	860-930 MHz	ASK 11-99%	Manchester	10-40 kbps		Backscatter	FM0	40 kbps
	10 m	0.05 mW	Type C	860-960 MHz	ASK 90%	PIE	27-128 kbps	40-640 kHz	ASK	FM0	40-640 kbps
									PSK	Miller	5-320 kbps
18000-7	10 m	0.1 mW		433.92 MHz	FSK	Manchester	27.7 kbps		FSK	Manchester	27.7 kbps

5.2.2.2 Topology of the EPC Network

RFID systems could not be reduced to tags and readers. It is the origin of the “Internet of things” and it should be seen as a global system to manage objects. Each tag only stores an ID named EPC code which is a pointer on a distributed database (an EPC Information Service: EPCIS) where any kind of information related to this object can be accumulated like a URL is a pointer on data of a web page. Different EPCIS can be interconnected thanks to an ONS (Object Name Service like the DNS in the Internet) which is able to route an EPC code query to the right EPCIS. Finally, a search engine named EPC Discovery Services enables to find any information about an EPC tag.

Figure 20 The EPC Network.

5.3 Control Networks Protocols

5.3.1 PLC Lonworks

Lonworks technology has been launched by Echelon Corporation¹⁶. In 1999 the communications protocol (then known as LonTalk) was submitted to ANSI and accepted as a standard for control networking (ANSI/CEA-709.1-B). Echelon's power line and twisted pair signalling technologies (two types of physical interconnection technologies) were also submitted to ANSI for standardization and accepted. Since then, ANSI/CEA-709.1 has been accepted as the basis for IEEE 1473-L (in-train controls), AAR electro-pneumatic braking systems for freight trains, IFSF (European petrol station control), SEMI (semiconductor equipment manufacturing), and in 2005 as EN 14908 (European building automation standard). The protocol is also one of several data link/physical layers of the BACnet ASHARE/ANSI standard for building automation.

China ratified the technology as a national controls standard, GB/Z 20177.1-2006 and as a building and intelligent community standard, GB/T 20299.4-2006; and in 2007 CECED, the European Committee of Domestic Equipment Manufacturers, adopted the protocol as part of its Household Appliances Control and Monitoring – Application Interworking Specification (AIS) standards.

¹⁶ <http://www.echelon.com/>

During 2008 ISO and IEC have granted the communications protocol, twisted pair signalling technology, power line signalling technology, and Internet Protocol (IP) compatibility standard numbers ISO/IEC 14908-1, -2, -3, and -4.

As of now LonWorks meets wide use in the US, on home devices control automation systems, appliances and power sockets that implement the X10 standard (international and open industry standard for communication among electronic devices used for home automation).

5.3.1.1 Technology overview

Lonworks has two physical-layer signalling technologies; twisted pair "free topology" and power line carrier. The two-wire layer operates at 78 kbit/s using differential Manchester encoding, while the power line achieves either 5.4 or 3.6 kbit/s, depending on frequency.

Additionally, the LonWorks platform uses an affiliated IP tunneling standard—ISO/IEC 14908-4 (ANSI/CEA-852) -- in use by a number of manufacturers to connect the devices on previously deployed and new LonWorks platform-based networks to IP-aware applications or remote network-management tools. Many LonWorks platform-based control applications are being implemented with some sort of IP integration, either at the UI/application level or in the controls infrastructure. This is accomplished with web services or IP-routing products available on the market.

An Echelon Corporation-designed IC consistent of several 8-bit processors, the "Neuron chip" was initially the only way to implement a LonTalk protocol node and is used in the large majority of LonWorks platform-based hardware. Since 1999, the protocol has been available for general-purpose processors or 32-bit chips.

5.3.2 KNX

KNX is an open European standardized protocol, defined by manufacturers of electronic automation devices to communicate information among their devices, using either twisted pair wires, RF transmission or power-line communication¹⁷.

Today KNX provides the foundation for all applications within home automation:

- Lighting Control;
- Blind and Shutter Control;
- Heating, Ventilation & Air Conditioning Control;
- Audio/Video Control;
- Appliances operation and visualisation;
- Buildings security and safety.

KNX has several communication media which can be used in combination with one or more configuration modes, allowing each manufacturer to choose the right combination for the targeted market segment and application:

- Twisted pair (KNX TP): KNX is transmitted across a separate bus cable, hierarchically structure in lines and areas.
- Power Line (KNX PL): KNX is transmitted on the existing mains network.
- Radio frequency (KNX RF): KNX is transmitted via radio signals. Devices can be uni- or bidirectional.
- IP/Ethernet (KNX IP): This widespread communication medium can be used in conjunction with the 'KNXnet/IP' specifications, which allow the tunneling or routing of KNX frames encapsulated in IP frames.

Several KNX manufacturers offer gateways to other networks, i.e. to other building automation systems, telephone networks, multimedia networks, IP networks, etc. KNX systems can be mapped to BACnet objects (as documented in the international standard ISO 16484-5) or offers the possibility to interface with the DALI technology.

¹⁷ www.knx.org

5.3.2.1 Protocol stack overview

Figure 21: Protocol stack overview.

Figure 21 illustrates an overview of the KNX protocol structure. The term ‘Network Stack’ indicates the ubiquitous OSI-7 network layer. Indeed, KNX PL110/132 specifies 5 out of the 7 OSI network layers, namely Physical, Datalink, Network, Transport and Application. Session and Presentation layers are not defined, and are thus considered transparent to their adjacent layers.

KNX defines two additional stack sub-categories, the router stack and the bridge stack. Routers are used to guide information through disparate KNX net topologies (think the equivalent of a network multiplexer). Bridges function as re-transmitters, to connect distant net topologies (e.g. as links between different power phases in 3phase systems), or to amplify a weakened KNX signal source – since the maximum length in a KNX copper power-line is around 400-600m. The router stack and the bridge stack present differences in the network, transport and the application layers compared to the PL device KNX stack. Since one can buy standardized PL110/132 KNX routers and bridges from a number of vendors, we do not need to address this issue.

Among other features, KNX provides flexible protocol exploitation. Namely it is allowed to turn stack layers on or off (starting from the top and moving downwards) up-to the data link layer. Certain applications are expected to run in very simple KNX network topology configurations, thus they need the first 2 layers to function properly. By disabling the overlaying stack segments, the stack implementation can be hosted in very minute and cheap microprocessors (typically in just 8 Kbytes of memory). When more complex topologies are necessary, the application designer must deploy additional layers, which support more complex net configurations, but need stronger micro-processors, both in terms of processing power and memory. A full PL110/PL132 device stack implementation can be expected to be hosted in 70Kbytes of code on an 16-bit micro-processor base, including support for network management procedures and net topology administration.

5.3.3 Controller Area Network CAN

CAN is a specification addressing the physical and data link layers of the OSI protocol stack. It was originally developed by Bosch in 1985 for in-vehicle networks, to replace the point-to-point wiring systems widely used at that time to connect in-vehicle electronic devices. The automotive industry quickly adopted CAN and in 1993 it became the international standard known as ISO 11898. Though the CAN physical layer and data link layer protocol was originally developed for use as in-vehicle network, several CAN-based higher-layer protocols have been defined to incorporate the CAN data link protocol into specific application requirements. Besides proprietary CAN-based higher-layer protocols, there are also several internationally standardized ones: CANopen for embedded control

systems, DeviceNet for factory automation, J1939-based solutions (J1939-71, Isobus, ISO 11992, CiA 501/2) for trucks and other vehicles, ISO 15765 for passenger car diagnostics.

5.3.3.1 Overview and Target Applications

CAN provides an inexpensive, durable network that helps multiple CAN devices communicate with one another. It is a high integrity, multi-master, broadcast, serial bus standard used for networking intelligent devices. The devices that are connected via a CAN network are typically control devices, such as sensors and actuators. Apart from its use in in-vehicle networks, CAN has been adopted for a wide variety of applications¹⁸. Railway applications such as streetcars, trams, undergrounds, light railways, and long-distance trains incorporate CAN. You can find CAN on different levels of the multiple networks within these vehicles -- for example, in linking the door units or brake controllers, passenger counting units, and more. CAN also has applications in aircraft with flight-state sensors and navigation systems.

Additionally, CAN is used in a broad variety of manufacturing industries, mainly for embedded machine control, but also for factory automation, process automation, and power generation. Furthermore, it is used in building automation, for example in lift control, embedded door control and heating, ventilation and air-conditioning. In retail and finance, CAN is used for embedded control within vending machines, including gas station equipment, automatic teller machines (ATM), and in the control systems of utility machines such as household appliances (coffee machines, washing machines), copy machines and printers. Medical equipment manufacturers use CAN as an embedded network in medical devices. In fact, some hospitals use CAN to manage complete operating rooms. Hospitals control operating room components such as lights, tables, cameras, X-ray machines, and patient beds with CAN-based systems. Lifts and escalators use embedded CAN networks, and hospitals use the CANopen protocol to link lift devices, such as panels, controllers, doors, and light barriers, to each other and control them. CANopen also is used in non-industrial applications such as laboratory equipment, sports cameras, telescopes, automatic doors, and even coffee machines.

5.3.3.2 Communication Mechanism

Each node on the CAN bus is able to both send and receive messages, but not simultaneously. As CAN is a broadcast bus, all devices on the bus see all transmitted messages. Each device can decide if a message is relevant or if it should be filtered. In addition, every message has a priority, so if two nodes try to send messages simultaneously, the one with the higher priority gets transmitted and the one with the lower priority gets postponed. A message consists primarily of an ID, which represents the priority of the message, and up to eight data bytes. The message priority is based on the number of dominant bits - a bit is dominant if it is equal to 0 - that make up the CAN node ID. Practically, the node the ID of which contains more zeroes, overwrites the ID of nodes containing less zeroes. Via this prioritized arbitration mechanism, the most dominant node gets ownership of the CAN bus. The aforementioned arbitration scheme makes CAN very suitable for real-time prioritized communication systems. Furthermore, CAN incorporates error detection mechanisms in its frame format, hence it is a very reliable system with multiple error checks, such as checksum errors, frame errors, message acknowledgement errors.

CAN defines several different physical layers. Each of the physical layers classifies certain aspects of the CAN network, such as electrical levels, signalling schemes, cable impedance, maximum baud rates. High-speed CAN is by far the most common physical layer. High-speed CAN networks are implemented with two wires and allow communication at transfer rates up to 1 Mb/s. Other names for high-speed CAN include CAN C and ISO 11898-2. Low-speed/fault-tolerant CAN networks are also implemented with two wires, can communicate with devices at rates up to 125 kb/s, and offer transceivers with fault-tolerant capabilities. Other names for low-speed/fault-tolerant CAN include CAN B and ISO 11898-3. Single-wire CAN interfaces can communicate with devices at rates up to 33.3 kb/s (88.3 kb/s in high-speed mode). Other names for single-wire CAN include SAE-J2411, CAN A, and GMLAN.

5.3.3.3 Frame Formats

A CAN network can be configured to work with two different message (or "frame") formats: the standard or base frame format (or CAN 2.0 A), and the extended frame format (or CAN 2.0 B). The basic difference between the two formats is that the "CAN base frame" supports a length of 11 bits for the identifier, and the "CAN extended frame" supports a length of 29 bits for the identifier, made up of the 11-bit identifier ("base identifier") and an 18-bit extension ("identifier extension"). The distinction between CAN base frame format and CAN extended frame format is based on the IDE bit, which is transmitted as dominant in case of an 11-bit frame, and transmitted as recessive in case of a 29-bit

¹⁸ <http://www.can-cia.org/>

frame. CAN controllers that support extended frame format messages are also able to send and receive messages in CAN base frame format. All frames begin with a start-of-frame (SOF) bit that denotes the start of the frame transmission.

CAN defines four frame types. The Data Frame is the only frame used for actual data transmission. There are the base data frame format, using 11 identifier bits, and the extended frame format, using 29 identifier bits. The CAN standard requires the implementation must accept the base frame format and may accept the extended frame format, but must tolerate the extended base format. The Remote Frame is used to request the transmission of a specific identifier. Generally data transmission is performed on an autonomous basis with the data source node (e.g. a sensor) sending out a Data Frame. It is also possible, however, for a destination node to request the data from the source by sending a Remote Frame. Error Frames are transmitted by any node detecting an error, whereas overloaded frames are used to inject delays between data and/or remote frames.

The basic CAN data frame format is depicted in the following figure, see also: <http://zone.ni.com/devzone/cda/tut/p/id/2732>

Figure 22 Basic CAN data frame format.

The SOF (start-of-frame) bit indicates the beginning of a message with a dominant (logic 0) bit. The Arbitration ID identifies the message and indicates the message's priority. The base frame format incorporates an 11-bit identifier, whereas the extended frame format extends the identifier by 18 bits, yielding a total of 29-bits wide message identifier. The SRR (Substitute Remote Request) bit is only present in the extended frame format and is always set to 1. The IDentifier Extension (IDE) bit allows for differentiating standard and extended frames; it is set to 0 in the base frame format and 1 in the extended frame format. The complementary 18-bit arbitration ID is present in the extended frame format to form the total 29-bit message identifier. The Remote Transmission Request (RTR) bit is set to 0, the r0 bit is a reserved bit and the Data Length Code (DLC) indicates the number of bytes the data field contains. Following the DLC field are the actual data bytes to be transmitted and the CRC code used for error detection by the message receiver. The ACK field is 2 bits wide and is used by the message receiver to acknowledge reception, whereas the End Of Frame (EOF) field is used to denote the end of the current message and is always set to 1.

5.4 Operating Systems

The basic task of any operating system is resource management that is both efficient and flexible for a broad set of applications [403]. At the same time, low-level details of the underlying hardware shall be hidden behind a clear set of interfaces and abstractions. In contrast to “traditional” distributed operating systems, though, the design of run-time platforms for wireless sensor networks (WSNs) is primarily influenced by three very specific characteristics: resource constraints, high dynamics, and potentially inaccessible deployment. Considering the severe resource constraints of most mote platforms in combination with the rather limited and low-level debugging facilities, it further becomes clear that operating systems for WSNs cannot be evaluated in isolation but only in combination with their respective development tools.

The remainder of this section is organized as follows. First, in Subsection 5.4.1, the different design issues and challenges for WSN operating systems and development tools are introduced in more detail. Next, in Subsection 5.4.1.4, the key features of the three most advanced and widely used platforms are discussed, namely TinyOS, Contiki, and FreeRTOS. Finally, in Subsection **Error! Reference source not found.**, our take on features currently missing but considered crucial for future WSN operating systems is presented. This analysis will also serve as the general guideline for work on this topic within IoT-A.

5.4.1 Design Issues and Challenges

The designer of an operating system for WSNs is challenged with issues in three different areas [411]. Firstly, at the node level in terms of different types of hardware and constrained resources which have immediate impact on portability and resource management. Secondly, at the network level in terms of connectivity and bandwidth which have immediate impact on communication protocols and scalability. And thirdly, at the tools level by creating a development environment which complements the operating systems both in terms of achieving optimal run-time efficiency and providing powerful abstractions to developers.

5.4.1.1 At the Node Level

The primary design challenge at the node level is how to make the most out of very limited resources. Foremost this means power consumption as motes are typically expected to live for months to years on one set of batteries or solely on energy harvested from the environment [412]. The main source of power consumption is wireless communication considering that transmitting or receiving a single bit of data is equivalent to thousands of instructions executed by the mote's CPU [408]. It is the responsibility of the operating system to provide mechanisms and abstractions that allow power consumption to be minimized by, for instance, sleeping in the most energy-preserving mode that will not violate timing constraints. At the same time, the APIs shall be designed in a way, which avoids mixing hardware-specific with application-specific code as much as possible. This firstly leads to cleaner, easier-to-understand, and less error-prone code, and secondly facilitates porting application code to different hardware platforms running the same operating system.

Next, processing power is often provided by nothing more powerful than a 8-bit CPU running at, say, 8 Mhz [408]. In combination with equally scarce memory resources (e.g., 8 KB of RAM, 128 KB of Flash), this has significant effect on the processing model [407]. Threads, for example, a widely used abstraction on desktop machines and servers, impose non-negligible overhead, which can be prohibitive on a mote platform. Each thread needs some stack space and context information, context switches burn cycles, and shared memory access must be synchronized. Furthermore, since most embedded CPUs are single-core only, there is no real parallel processing of threads and therefore also no speedup [410]. An alternative is the event-driven run-to-completion model. In this model, applications register callback methods with the operating system to be invoked by the operating system in response to matching events occurring. Once triggered, such an event handler will run to completion. Events happening in the meantime, though, are either lost or delayed. Application developers can circumvent this by modelling long-running event handlers as split-phase operations, yet this requires additional effort by the developer and makes application code more difficult to read.

Finally, as WSNs are typically heterogeneous by nature with different motes of different roles and performance characteristic cooperating within the same network, scalability is an import design challenge [406]. In essence it is preferable if the same operating system can be used across a broad range of different mote hardware, efficiently making use of additional resources as available. By designing an operating system in a way so that it is easy reconfigurable and customizable, it also can be more easily tailored to match specific application requirements with a minimum of overhead. Using the same operating system on different motes further enhances application portability. In a first step this would reduce porting an application basically to recompiling its source code for the new hardware platform. One step further is the use of a virtual machine which not only hides the particularities of the underlying hardware from the application but allows using the same application binary to be deployed onto different mote hardware.

5.4.1.2 At the Network Level

Motes in WSNs are loosely coupled and sometimes deployed across a large geographical area with the network being at a scale in the order of thousands of sensor nodes.

A core design issue at the network level then is whether to make the WSN appear as a single entity or to expose its distributed nature. A single-entity view allows interactions among components to appear as being on the same node while the system has to place the components across different nodes in the network so that communication cost is minimized. Bandwidth variations, link failures, or the general (temporal) inaccessibility of nodes should further be masked from the application developer. With a distributed view, in contrast, developers have to be aware of where components are located in the network and deal with all the aforementioned problems at the application level. Such application(-domain)-specific solutions, though, can be more efficient than a system-provided automatism, no matter how clever. Currently all systems implement the distributed view.

Furthermore, so far no single network protocol has been identified that works efficiently across at the least the majority of application domains. For rather static installations with stringent latency and failure-masking requirements as seen, for example, in industry automation, Wireless HART might be a good match. Applications in more dynamic environments might benefit from protocols such as ZigBee, while WSNs connected to IP back-ends might favour 6LoWPAN. Let alone the myriads of application-specific protocols as the closest match to application-specific requirements. This also includes aspects of scalability to ensure that the performance of the WSN is degrading in acceptable ways with an increase in the number of nodes [414]. It is therefore crucial that the operating system avoids hard-coding a single network protocol but rather focuses on base mechanisms and abstractions which help building more specific high-level network protocols.

5.4.1.3 At the Tools Level

A crucial component for embedded systems development in general and WSNs in particular is tool support. The design challenge here is to perform as much processing as possible off-mote, that is, before an application is actually deployed. This includes, for example, pre-calculations of jump tables, reformatting of code and data for more efficient processing on the mote, or minimizing the code size. At the same time, the level of abstraction for the application developer shall be kept as high as possible. That is, instead of forcing development in, say, assembler or C, the ability to use object-oriented programming languages such as Java or C# would be highly preferable.

Furthermore, as the debugging facilities of embedded systems tend to be rather limited and low level while test setups become increasingly complex, a simulation environment in combination with a sensor-feeding framework is indispensable. Such a simulation environment not only helps bridging the gap between high-level languages by allowing source-level debugging, but more importantly provide the prerequisite for repeatable regression tests in dynamic environments. Examples are testing application behaviour when motes change their position and consequently influence network topology, or reading certain sequences of sensor data potentially triggering specific actions in response.

5.4.1.4 State-of-the-Art Platforms

Given the design issues and challenges identified in Subsection 5.4.1, this section takes a look at three widely used operating systems: TinyOS, Contiki, and FreeRTOS. While TinyOS and Contiki are explicitly targeting WSNs, FreeRTOS is more of a general operating system for embedded systems.

5.4.2 TinyOS

TinyOS [413] is a free open-source component-based operating system for wireless sensor networks written in the nesC programming language as a set of cooperating tasks and processes. It started as collaboration between the University of California, Berkeley, Intel Research, and Crossbow Technologies, and since then has grown into a TinyOS Alliance consortium.

The basic architecture of TinyOS is monolithic with an underlying component model at compile time and a single static image at run time. It follows an event-driven execution model with a concurrency model based on commands, asynchronous events, and tasks. Function invocations, or commands, are separated from their completion notification, or events. Both commands and event handlers may post so-called tasks which are executed by the TinyOS scheduler in FIFO order. Tasks can only be pre-empted by events but not by other tasks; long-running event handlers therefore shall outsource their processing to a task, which then resembles a split-phase operation. Data race conflicts during task pre-emption must be resolved by means of atomic sections.

The behaviour of TinyOS programs can be changed only through hard-coded transitions or source-code modifications. The latter requires a recompile with TinyOS and placing a new image onto the mote, effectively losing all state information without taking specific precautions at the application level. For power management TinyOS provides APIs which allow the application to conserve power properly. Both the CPU and the radio controller can be managed.

Wireless communication TinyOS is by means of a proprietary MAC layer based on the 802.15.4 physical layer and frame formats. A full 802.15.4 implementation is work in progress. At present, it further provides higher-level protocols for data gathering and command dissemination while additional protocols can be implemented on demand.

Both application and system development is done in nesC, short for network embedded systems C. nesC is loosely based on the C programming language but enforcing a strict separation of construction and composition.

For TinyOS the simulation environment TOSSIM [409] is available which simulates TinyOS applications in a homogeneous network environment. The same code can be used for both the simulation as for real-world deployments. TOSSIM actually provides a simulation at the bit level for experimentation with low-level protocols. An extensible GUI tool can further visualize simulations runs.

5.4.3 Contiki

Contiki [405] is a free open-source operating system developed for use on memory-constrained networked systems including wireless sensor networks. It has its origin at the Swedish Institute of Computer Science which still coordinates the development.

Contiki's architecture is modular in the sense of microkernel designs. Communication, device drivers, and sensor data handling are implemented as services, each one consisting of an interface and an implementation. The execution model of Contiki is a hybrid of events and threads. Primarily event-driven, it supports multi-threading as an optional application library. Events are classified as synchronous or asynchronous. The former are scheduled without any delay with the latter may be executed at some later point in time.

Service implementations can be changed at run time since applications accessing services only link to stub libraries, which serve as the glue between an application and the services used. Instead of reflashing the entire system as with TinyOS, for example, only the required application services can be dynamically replaced. Code is assumed to be position-dependent, though, which can cause memory allocation problems if code size increases.

Contiki does not explicitly provide high-level power management abstractions but provides an application with access to some of its internal state such as event queues. This way an application can decide, for instance, to power down the system to deep-sleep mode if no events are pending.

For communication, Contiki provides a rather flexible network stack that can accommodate a wide range of MAC layers from 802.15.4 to UDP to proprietary implementations. In terms of higher-level protocols Contiki strongly favours an IP protocol suite, both IPv4 and IPv6. It also serves as the prime example of a 6LoWPAN implementation.

Contiki uses the C programming language for system implementation and application development.

The Contiki simulation environment runs as a user-level process on BSD Unix with each simulated mote being represented by another user-level process. Since mote processes are not synchronized and scheduled by the BSD scheduler independently, simulation behaviour is nondeterministic to a certain degree. More advanced simulation environments for Contiki are under development.

5.4.4 FreeRTOS

FreeRTOS [404] finally is a real-time operating system for embedded devices in general with no specific relationship to wireless sensor networks. It is mostly written in C, and designed to both small and simple. Like TinyOS it follows a monolithic approach but provides both pre-emptive and non-preemptive scheduling of tasks. Each task executes within its own context with no coincidental dependency on other tasks within the system or the scheduler itself. In addition to tasks, FreeRTOS also provides lightweight co-routines for short running activities. Inter-task communication and synchronization is performed via queues, semaphores, or mutexes.

For wired communication different TCP/IP implementations with different constraints are available; no explicit support for wireless communication is provided. No specific support for power management is provided either.

FreeRTOS uses C and assembler for system and application development.

For development and debugging, simulation environments for both Windows and Linux are available. The simulators only simulate a single embedded system, though.

6. Security and privacy

IoT has the potential to change many of our daily activities, routines and behaviours. The physical pervasiveness of the novel sources of information can mean that a great amount of data pertaining to possibly all aspects of human activity – both public and private – will be produced, transmitted, collected, stored and processed. In this scenario it is paramount that users – private citizens, enterprises or public bodies – have the tools to manage their privacy and that their settings are correctly and strongly enforced by security features.

In this context it is useful to define the relationship between security and privacy. A secure system is one that you can trust for sensitive but not necessarily personal information exchange and processing. Security in information systems is characterized by a set of interdependent security goals, mainly:

- Authentication (Access restriction);
- Confidentiality;
- Integrity.

However some security functions used to protect sensitive information like financial data can oppose to or may be difficult to align with Privacy principles when they are used to process personal information. This is the case for principle like.

- Transparency (Privacy) vs. Confidentiality (Security);
- Verifiability (Privacy) vs. Access restriction (Security);
- Right purpose (Privacy) vs. Data Retention (National Security).

6.1 Privacy

Attention to privacy is rapidly gaining momentum in an increasingly connected world. Mobile consumer devices and contactless electronic identification means are going to become essential tools in the future digital environment. At the same time the concept of the Internet of Things is coming into existence, where everything is connected and communicating with one another. This gives rise to

cooperative scenarios where applications are no longer running in isolation but operate at a distributed system level, tapping into all the knowledge and intelligence gathered there. In this context new business models are developing without enough anticipative and protective considerations regarding the engendered security risks.

Privacy is a difficult investigation area that requires integration of social, legal and technological aspects. From that perspective Governments, industry, service providers and distributors at large, consumers, citizens are all actors of this multifaceted game, requiring appropriate technologies, awareness and legal framework. The worldwide dimension of the problem makes this equation even more complex.

6.1.1 Definition

It is difficult to provide a single definition of Privacy as no universal consensus can be found. Instead we can try to answer a more fundamental question: what is Privacy aiming for and what is the scope of Privacy?

Daniel J. Solove (George Washington University Law School) argues there is no unique definition of Privacy, instead there are various forms of privacy that are context dependent and therefore taking into account historical changes and cultural differences are important to address Privacy in a certain domain and at a certain place [389].

Privacy measures how individual freedom is protected, defining the zone of personal life that a person can make free of external intrusion. Again the metrics will vary according to the observed domain. In bioethics matters for instance the Portuguese National Council of Ethics for the Life Sciences (CNECV) is of the opinion that Privacy spans a four-dimensional space [390]:

- Physical Privacy which restricts physical accessibility, of any kind, without individual consent;
- Mental Privacy, forbidding any illegitimate interference on person's mind or will;
- Decisional Privacy, which refers to the freedom on individual choice;
- Informational Privacy, that protects against unlawful access to individual information.

As such Privacy mostly refers to constitutional texts in democratic countries and more generally to Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms as the original source.

6.1.1.1 International Privacy

Many countries recognize the need for dedicated laws on Privacy. The dynamics of innovation forces governments to adapt legal texts for a better coverage in the related business sectors, addressing more specifically new Privacy issues raised by the introduction of those technologies.

Nevertheless it remains a real challenge to achieve worldwide harmonization of Privacy legislations. As a matter of fact modern concepts of Privacy result from the long phase-in of economic development in Western countries with the occurrence of invasive marketing and surveillance techniques supported by fast evolving technology instruments. Such changes are somewhat negatively perceived as a deterioration of freedom rights historically acquired long time ago in those regions. In contrast those conditions are not fulfilled yet in Asia where cultural influences are still dominant and continue to exist independently of the economic growth and social evolution. Two examples illustrate the mindset difference:

- The Chinese word for Privacy is “Yinsi” which actually indicates matters that could be shameful to disclose. Therefore offended people traditionally tend to solve invasion of their Privacy by themselves instead of going to courts as they would not like the topic be publicly exposed [391].
- There is no Japanese term for Privacy. Modern Japanese language simply integrates the English noun, pronounced “puraibashi”. The Buddhist worldview that Humanity is suffering because of the desires of self, refrains individual's behaviour in such a way that privacy is effectively applied in day-to-day personal relations.

In developed countries globalization and technology advances have created fears that technology advances would threaten people existence conditions through more tracking and surveillance. Instead China, India and South-Asia widely support the international competition model as it stimulates their own growth, hence creating significant improvements of life conditions for the middle-class at least. Most people in Eastern countries are not very much considering the protection of personal data as a top priority today compared to high profits of technology progresses. As a consequence governments do not urge to regulate on Privacy. They preferably adopt an approach that largely integrates regional mentality and conventions. In addition data protection laws like the one India voted this year are generally adopted more in response to Western countries instigation due to the massive outsourcing of services to low-cost regions than because of local community explicit claim [392].

6.1.1.2 Privacy in the era of electronic data exchange

In the electronic and telecommunication sectors mental, decisional and informational Privacy may be affected by Systems and Applications that - directly or indirectly - participate to the human environment.

The scope of Privacy is largely context dependent. On the Internet for instance, users concerns are mainly:

- What personal information they want to share and with whom;
- Whether messages can be exchanged without being read or traced;
- Whether their connected status and behavior is unobservable;
- Whether anonymity in consultations and expression on sensitive matters is preserved.

Achieving Privacy in the deployment of complex applications requires all actors, technology providers, designers, operators and Authorities to mutually stress for compliance to general principles:

- Subject consent, with right to access and control the usage of disclosed personal data;
- Right purpose, as capturing personal information must be lawful;
- Collection limitation, i.e. only data needed for that purpose can be collected;
- Data quality, i.e. collected data must be accurate, complete and up-to-date;
- Transparency as the subject can only consent if he/she is aware and understands;
- Safeguard of legitimate disclosures;
- Right for the subject to access, correct and erase stored personal information;
- Accountability to make all recipients liable of any personal information misuse.

Web 2.0 was a major step in connectivity offering normal subscribers the potential to play an active role on the Internet. Social Networks development eventually started with it. This is an unprecedented experience for most Internet users who are now faced to Privacy issues regarding the management of their own identity. The EC Article 29 Working Party in charge of observation of societal changes that could affect Privacy legislation recently issued a recommendation to redefine the roles and responsibilities of Social Network actors [393].

Electronics systems are becoming more and more intrusive. This is the natural consequence of a rapid movement towards downsizing that the Moore law initiated few decades ago. In our pervasive environment people do not always realize the underlying capabilities of daily used sophisticated devices they own. The lack of visibility of electronic parts adds a particular dimension to user's ignorance as it is very common with credit cards or fare tickets. Technology advances constantly enable business opportunities which in turn trigger new applications development. More integration on powerful platforms is also a logical step forward to increase the user experience and gain Market shares. Sustaining Privacy in a modern society is therefore a permanent challenge to keep reasonable distance between consumers and citizens on the one hand and technologies used to support the new services on the other hand. Besides the legitimacy required for any personal data processing Privacy would always require maintaining a good mix of: Transparency, Verifiability, Assessment and Accountability.

Transparency requires that sufficient information is provided to the data subject before any personal data processing (including capture, storage and/or transfer) occurs. A vague indication that such processing will be done is not sufficient: the nature of collected data and purpose of the following processing must be expressed to the data subject who can object undesirable purposes like direct Marketing or transfer to third parties.

Verifiability fully complements the principle of transparency as it offers the data subject some right to access and correct, block or erase data and check compliance of the data processing

Assessment is a requirement for data operator and controllers to process personal data according to the legal principles, which among others impose the use of safeguard measures to guarantee only authorized accesses and fully compliant processes.

Accountability is important to enforce operator and controller responsibilities in a Privacy compliant implementation of personal data processing. They can be liable for data leakages or misuses due e.g. to inappropriate processing rules or insufficient security measures implemented to protect such data.

6.1.1.3 Right to Privacy is never absolute

Important limitations to Privacy exist in all regulations for National Security reasons. Criminal investigations and protection of the Society require for Authorities to explicit disclosure rights to conduct legitimate inquiries. From that perspective service operators may be enforced to keep ephemeral data like traffic data for the sake of judicial procedures initiated long after the communication ended. Those data could normally only be used for establishing or billing electronic communications so there is no "right purpose" to save this information for a longer time than necessary for the business. In this case however States may require the operator to archive the data in a secure way although for a limited period defined by the law. This exception to the Privacy

principles is known as Data retention rule. In Europe this principle comes in force through a Directive promulgated in 2006 [394]. This however remains subject to hard public debates as monitoring shows a continuous growth in data breaches due to the increasing volume of stored data [395].

6.1.2 Privacy Paradoxes

6.1.2.1 People tempted to relax Privacy for a better experience

In 2008 IBM conducted an inquiry of 4400 consumers from 11 countries to analyze behaviours of customers faced to the release of their sensitive data, for instance to optimize insurance services/costs balance by opting to Usage Base Insurance (UBI) models [396]. However this highly depends on the coverage domain and shows significant country-based differences. For instance installing GPS transmitters to locate the owner car in case of theft gets an acceptance rate of 60 (UK) to 90% (FR and NL). Similar rates are obtained for house protection systems. At the other end sensor-based health monitoring at home with premiums is only approved by 23% (CH) to 45% (UK) people.

On the other hand many are scared about Web sites that track their behaviour. Not surprisingly a balance exists between the perceived convenience and benefits in terms of cost reduction and time savings for an improved service and the eroded privacy seen as a normal counterpart. Perhaps a more nuanced trade-off should be expected about identity management applications deployed by the public sector because of possible consequences of unauthorized use of identity and rather limited trust in administrations ability to control and protect personal information in a secure way.

In addition consumers express a lot of concern about their privacy online in surveys. At the same time, few take appropriate protection measures.

6.1.2.2 More connectivity for more convenience

Today electronic devices that only operate in isolation are the exception. Even small devices require at least some interfaces for configuration or minimal control. This implies the possibility of data exchanges and communication protocols with a host system at initiation or personalization time. Typical examples are:

- Medical care and surveillance sensors and equipment, possibly arranged in wireless configurations
- Electronic passports and identification cards used for cross-border checks, on-line administration or access control
- Payment and self-banking operations using ATM or POS terminals that limit cash transfers and improve security and accuracy.
- Supply Chain Management (SCM) systems based on Electronic Product Codes and RFID to achieve higher performance, profitability, traceability, reliability and services integration in Logistics.

Those applications should not be considered separately as more service integration creates attractive business opportunities. For example Mobile payments now rely on contactless interfaces to confirm (“wave”) payments by simply touching RFID tags attached to some products or services offered to the consumer.

In addition many applications use back-office intelligence to process events and information captured from electronic tokens hold by people, which limits the amount of data to be stored in personal tokens and devices. From that perspective interoperability with cooperative service infrastructures is a basic requirement. In the future this property would culminate in Global Connectivity, through the concept of the upcoming Internet of Things (IOT). A recent communication of the European Commission on this phenomenon recommends European policy-makers and public authorities to ensure that IOT technologies and applications will be used to stimulate economic growth, improve individuals’ well-being and address some of today’s societal problems at the same time [397].

Sharing intelligence over interconnected networks improves the user experience as a single click or touch can magically trigger a long sequence of transactions. This invisible complexity however can shade underlying processes that run without the user being even aware of their existence. Those background applications are designed to exploit related data that transit through the different nodes of the System. The amount of disclosed information can be considerable as a single identifier can just be an initial entry to a vast collection of data distributed over a large configuration of servers. Even assuming lawful accesses and right processing of personal data the user has finally little control on it. Frequently he/she has no guidance or appropriate education to comprehend the system and evaluate potential risks of security breaches. And even if people spend the effort to evaluate the Privacy policies published by their data processors, they are faced to complicated procedures, lengthy and cumbersome readings. A recent survey showed that reviewing on-line policies is becoming impracticable for conscious Internet users as in average careful just reading and approval would cost up to 20 hours a month [398].

6.1.3 Personal Identification, key in Electronic Privacy

From a business perspective acquiring behavioural information about customers is crucial. At Point of Sales for instance automatic collection based on loyalty cards is now preferred to expensive surveys which require more acceptance and cooperation from the consumer part. Whatever the method and technology used the hidden objective is always to profile consumers for statistical and direct marketing purposes. The consumer once agrees on a relaxed Privacy attitude in the application context as he/she gets some compensation later through discounts and rewards. Collection starts when his/her identification is caught by the system at the cash position and linked to the registered transaction, including the list of purchased goods. The consumer history is further consolidated by the system to build and optimize each individual profile over time. The scenario repeats with all visited retailers so many consumers use to bear multiple identification cards to refer the related loyalty program on cashier demand.

So far the risk of unlawful linkage of multiple tokens owned by individuals was contained to operator database systems as contact, barcode or magnetic strip identification card contents can only be accessed if they are **physically** presented to a single compatible reader. Recent introduction of contactless interfaces for more efficiency and convenience in cash operations adds new vulnerability to direct over-the-air attacks. Low cost sniffers can log RF transactions or collect valuable information from the set of cards a victim bears in a wallet. Eavesdroppers can easily operate in the vicinity, without the owner being aware of. This scenario has been proven feasible in all public areas (street, busses...).

Hacking a single identification token is generally not sufficient to create great value for the attacker. However concentration of identifiers held by individuals makes it possible the collection of significant data and tracking over time. Correlating all those data, including precise location/time information of people in the range helps in creating enhanced profiles and/or permits the leakage of sensitive information that a single card would not reveal.

Typical misconception in implementing Privacy Enhancing Techniques (PET) could also create false confidence in a good Privacy match. ID randomization, for instance is recommended as a primary countermeasure to protect the personal identifier used by the application like a Social Security Number or a Driver License or National ID. The validity of the method highly depends on the quality of the implementation as low RNG entropy and leaks in the protocol can be sufficient to mount tracking scenarios and repeat attacks at different places. Doing so an attacker accumulates knowledge more than expected if we consider each exposure separately.

Problem complexity still increases as multi-application platforms are now emerging. Powerful architectures developed on such devices can endorse several roles that automatically adapt to versatile scenarios. Typical examples are in the new mobile phones generation that can easily integrate contactless micro-payments in entertainment, transportation, road tolling and parking fees applications. Additional radio links can be further added to e.g. fire car engines or give access to building controlled areas. Being part of the value chain Mobile operators want to increase the bandwidth usage therefore they strongly support those new business models.

6.1.3.1 RFID is gaining momentum

Up to 2.2 billion RFID tags were deployed in 2008 for various applications from tolling to shipping containers identification, roughly a third of these tags in Europe. Market figures show a sharp growth from €4 billion in 2008 to €20 billion over 10 years. This made it necessary for the European Commission to investigate on the RFID impact on Privacy Regulation in Europe. This has been assigned to the "Article 29 Working Party" an official EC organ in charge of expressing opinions and making recommendations on the Privacy law application in EU. The mission included a public consultation on RFID [399] followed by a general Recommendation on sensitive applications of this technology and the required process to ensure Privacy in design and deployment of such applications [400].

The EC Recommendation provides a legal definition and scope to RFID and the covered applications. The main requirements of the Recommendations relate to Privacy:

Opt-in by default: tags attached/incorporated to products in the retail sector should be automatically deactivated as soon as acquired by a consumer, immediately and free-of-charge, unless the consumer explicitly asks to keep them operational.

Privacy Impact Assessments (PIA): these should be conducted by Operators before using smart chips to ensure any use of personal data is secure. These assessments should be reviewed by national data protection authorities.

Exceptions to Opt-in principle in retail: can be granted after the Privacy Impact Assessment conducted by the Operator of the targeted application shows there is no Privacy risk for the consumer.

Transparency: Operators should provide clear and simple information so that customer know if smart chips are used, what personal data will be used and for what purpose. They should also provide a contact point for citizens to obtain more information.

Logo: Consumer awareness should be emphasized on products containing smart chips through a common European sign that indicates their presence in/by a product.

6.1.4 Smart Chips and Personal Identification

Personal tokens with Smart Chips are already used from a long time in the European banking sector for payment applications. So far mainly debit cards included such chips that interface with ATM and POS terminals through surface contacts.

Out of Europe the situation is quite different as many countries like US or Russia lagged in chip card adoption for payment. They are now rapidly migrating from the old magnetic strip (no chip) to contactless or dual interface smart chip models. Contactless interfaces are first considered for their increased transaction performances in all payment scenarios.

Governments on their part are promoting the use of electronic identification in their relations with the citizen. In many European and Asian countries e-ID cards are issued, aiming in first instance at National Security reasons. At the same time governments have started the deployment of on-line Administrative services like taxation and form request based on the e-ID. Some even go one step further and suggest or encourage commercial and social usage of the e-ID on the Internet. E-ID cards may be contact, contactless or dual depending on customer requirements.

International air travel documents are now mixing booklet and contactless chip in various anti-fraud combinations globally known as the e-Passport. Recent versions include biometric data of the subject like face image and fingerprints. However interoperability is a major requirement in this category. Because not all inspection and back-end systems are equally capable many security and privacy features are still optional.

Public transportation is an evolutionary market for smart chips. Contactless electronic ticketing has now proven to be very cost effective and efficient in optimizing the passenger access conditions and queuing times. Such systems can integrate subscription pass models, increasing the accuracy of statistical traffic data.

The introduction of contactless interfaces in identification or entitlement documents emphasized the risk of Privacy leaks due to incorrect application designs or procedures. Look at the Basic Access Control (BAC) feature which has been introduced in electronic passport to protect against intrusion through skimming attacks. In principle an attacker should have physical access to the Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) information printed on the booklet to generate the key so accessing the sensitive information of the passport. However that MRZ information is made of a serial number and personal data that sometimes may be inferred from other sources. If the serial number is not randomly generated the key entropy may be lower than assumed in the specification hence the whole Security and Privacy of the document may be compromised. Therefore the quality of implementations, not just the compliance to the specifications is important to achieve Privacy goals in sensitive applications [401] [402].

6.1.5 Data Collection Systems and Privacy considerations

All those applications require operators to deploy complex back-end server architectures to process events generated at the terminal points. For instance RFID tags used to identify pallets and cases are polled several times along the supply chain to track products in packing, repacking, warehousing, transport and distribution operations. Those tracking events are recorded and further processed to generate logistic reports and automate business transactions. Manufacturers are now close to introduce item-level tagging that would integrate retail operations in supply chain management. This will enable fast reordering while optimizing storage space and other assets requirements. Item tagging would also be a great opportunity to increase the value chain through the introduction of novel applications like integrated product warranty, consumer information and recycling instructions. Consumer could then directly access such services through an RFID-enabled Mobile phone or a kiosk installed in the shop. However this puts additional risks on Privacy as tag identifiers could easily be linked to personal identifiers leaked by the contactless cards borne by the consumer in the Point of Sale. Such traces could be used by the Back-end Information Systems to profile consumers and provide fine grained Marketing information to all the operators in the Supply Chain. Such linkability can be prevented through appropriate measures to be implemented both in the Network services and the tag-reader configurations.

6.1.5.1 Conclusions on Privacy

Differences in Privacy perception largely percolate in the regional legislations that multinational organizations face when they plan to distribute sensitive products or services worldwide. Chip

manufacturers active in Identification products are generally road-mapping custom versions of their base products. It could be such that Privacy regulations have a significant impact on the number of possible releases.

Fast penetration rate combined with shortened lifecycles in identification technologies let more powerful, contactless products constantly gain entry to the Market. Integrators and operators could not easily prevent Privacy breaches when they start integrating those technologies in new use cases without the support and expertise of technology providers and manufacturers. RFID and smart chip manufacturers are best placed to evaluate the risks of personal data leaks and assist in the right selection of sensitive products and features for the envisioned applications.

To increase the value and optimize data processing back end applications and systems are fast evolving towards intricate and cooperative architectures that sometimes share the collected information. Response to financial fraud is a typical example of an application that requires sophisticated analysis tools and sensitive data exchanges amongst several administration offices holding personal records. Combination of car usage and payment traces in road pricing applications is another example of cross-related sensitive information. Risks of data breaches will unmistakably grow in the future, requiring appropriate data protection measures and fine-grained authorization mechanisms. Selective credentials and dedicated identifiers, for instance, could be generalized to limit personal data exposure in versatile platforms used to access multiple centralized services.

A systemic approach of Privacy is necessary. In order to achieve full compliancy in design and development of sensitive applications all actors involved in the business chain should cooperate. This cooperation should be effective from the early stages of the proposal as use cases, components, system architecture, applications and deployment can be all affected by Privacy requirements. A complete Privacy Impact and Risk Assessment procedure should be initiated using a top-down decomposition method that requires first answering three fundamental questions:

- Where is the targeted application deployed (Legal constraints and cultural significance);
- For what purpose (Scope);
- For which scenarios (Business requirements).

This would normally enable an identification of the Privacy objectives and potential threats to be considered in further project steps. This approach will also help making correct architecture choices and trade-offs from the beginning hence asserting the proposal and going to viable solutions quicker. System design and deployment represent huge investments for integrators and operators active in Supply Chain, Public transportation and Government applications. Chip manufacturers can also contribute in promoting best practices that preserve consumer Privacy in the Customer project from the early stages. This would always pay off in terms of improved image and less risk of expensive revisions or corrective measures to adapt the original solution later.

6.2 Security

In the frame of IoT-A security is an important topic because security, or the lack of, can consistently impact on the adoption of the IoT paradigm. Moreover, IoT-A has the almost unique chance to set up the design process of a global architecture taking into account the security issues from the beginning. For these reasons, assessing the security SOTA is of the greatest importance.

Because no reference architecture is yet available, this section only investigates the SOTA of the future components of the IoT, and provides considerations on relevant threats and possible approaches to provide security features. This Section is organized in two subsections which focus respectively on the legacy security issues inherited from the current Internet architecture and on the security issues of WPAN and generic wireless network technologies that will likely be used for building the periphery of the IoT.

ICT systems can be subject to a large number of attacks, and especially wireless ones. These could be functionally characterized as pertaining to one or more of the following groups which we list hereafter for sake of completeness.

Eavesdropping Attacks

This is the process of listening for and possibly recording network traffic in order to derive any kind of useful information (from determining the actors to understanding the content of the communication). It generally is a passive attack.

Spoofing Attacks

Actions aimed to masquerade an entity (user, node, application) as another one in order to gain an illegitimate advantage.

Denial of Service Attacks

Malicious actions preventing legitimate users from actually using a service or functionality of the network or of a device. Different techniques apply here:

- Consumption of device resources (bandwidth, memory, processing capabilities, batteries)
- Prevention of proper communication with the device

Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks consist in the simultaneous action of many nodes to flood a target with requests, so that the target is no longer able to offer certain services.

6.2.1 The Legacy of Internet

6.2.1.1 Threats on Legacy Internet

While IoT devices exhibit specific vulnerabilities to novel attacks that are described below in this chapter, they are also likely to be targeted by classical Internet attacks, since an IoT infrastructure is expected to be connected to the Internet and/or to involve protocols and interfaces similar to those running on the Internet.

Sometimes, the consequences of these "classical" attacks will be the same as if they were released on legacy Internet components. Sometimes, though, they will be more critical because of the limited resources of the IoT components, the specific topologies they form, the payload they are used to carry or their deployment scenarios.

These attacks on the legacy Internet are briefly reviewed in what follows. When appropriate, their impacts on IoT architectures are given a particular highlight.

6.2.1.1.1 Denial of Service Attacks on the L1-L3 Communication Protocol Stack

Jamming attacks against the physical layer are an efficient means for an attacker to disrupt wireless communications by overwhelming the radio carrier with bogus data, either continuously or using some well-chosen pattern. Specific attack scenarios and defensive measures relevant to the IoT-A context are detailed in next subsection. Going up one layer, attacks against the MAC (Media Access Control) consist for an attacker to purposely create collisions by sending its own packet when a legitimate user's packet is being transmitted. These attacks are difficult to detect and to prevent. A probabilistic solution for detecting attacks in a CSMA/CA network has been proposed in [415].

Attacks against the routing protocols that enable efficient delivery of IP packets have been developed against all major vanilla Internet protocols. Intradomain protocols such as RIP, OSPF and interdomain protocols such as BGP all have exhibited vulnerabilities that have been exploited by attackers to carry out critical attacks, essentially impersonation of a legitimate router or falsification of routing messages [430]. IoT systems, often characterized by the presence of a routing decision at each node, are especially vulnerable to advanced attacks against the routing protocols such as selective forwarding, Sybil (node illegitimately taking multiple identities, [431]) or wormhole (using an offline channel to tunnel routing packets between two distant points of the network, [432]).

6.2.1.1.2 Generic Attack Schemes against Higher Layers

Flaws in upper layer protocols, either originating in operating systems components or in autonomous applications, are regularly discovered. In order to protect equipment against attacks launched from a remote location on the Internet, various systems are used in home and corporate environments. At best, these systems consist of a robust security architecture (multiple stage Demilitarized Zones) enforced with distributed intelligent firewalling (enabling behaviour control) and distributed intrusion detection systems, which, in their best form, can identify as malicious patterns corresponding to unknown attacks.

None of these techniques fits well to the IoT systems, which are characterized by low resources (hence, inability to maintain connection states or to perform intelligent packet inspection) and mutable topology. In addition IoT equipment might be especially difficult to patch once a novel vulnerability has been discovered.

6.2.1.1.3 Redirection attack

Redirection attacks are frequent in today's Internet and can occur at various layers of the communication protocol stack. ARP poisoning, ICMP redirect, DNS poisoning are very simple to carry out and have devastating consequences. A redirection attack is generally the first step for a man-in-the-middle attack, wherein the attacker gains access to all exchanged data (eavesdropping), and is able to change these data (alteration) or to inject arbitrary data (forging), while both end of the connection believe that they are directly communicating with each other.

6.2.1.1.4 Applicative Denial of Service

In the legacy Internet, DDoS are often used for a pure disruptive goal (e.g. political contestation). They can also be used to temporarily disable a legitimate node so as to enable a more subtle spoofing attack (e.g. session hijacking). Their consequences vary with the type of server that is targeted (http, dns).

In the field of the IoT, nodes are likely to be much more vulnerable to this kind of attacks. Generalized static configuration means that a node may not be able to switch to another server after its initial one has been disabled. On the other hand, an IoT node, due to its limited resources (e.g. number of available IPsec security associations [434]), can easily be rendered inoperative by a coordinated attack from even a limited number of attackers. Filling up its disk or memory, or exhausting its battery, can also be performed with greater efficiency if attackers are coordinating themselves.

Moreover, the availability of unattended nodes embedded in the environment could ease the task of corrupting a large number of devices and increase the threat of DDoS attacks in the future IoT.

6.2.1.2 Security Features

6.2.1.2.1 Authentication / Integrity

In order to prevent impersonation of legitimate users/devices and alteration of transmitted messages, data origin authentication and integrity algorithms are used in the Internet. These systems are essential for any transaction (including encryption – see below), so as nodes can make sure they are receiving data from the right peer. Public key infrastructures and X.509 certificates are largely used for that purpose in today's Internet, irrespectively of the OSI layer at which the authentication/integrity service has to be provided. 802.1X with PEAP (link-layer), most IKE IPsec bootstrapping (network layer), TLS (transport layer) make use of such certificates. However, its use in the IoT is only possible as long as powerful enough devices are concerned.

Other types of credentials are also used in legacy Internet. For example, login/password pairs are the credentials employed by human users, generally to unlock access to much more robust cryptographic material. These are subject to a wide variety of attacks from attackers, such as brute forcing, dictionary attacks or human-targeted social engineering. In order to allow for single sign-on, web 2.0 applications use ephemeral session identifiers, which, once hijacked, represent a simple way for an attacker to impersonate a legitimate user.

6.2.1.2.2 Confidentiality

Confidentiality is a major concern for today's Internet. Various systems exist that allow an attacker to eavesdrop data packets exchanged between two Internet nodes. Generally, the edge links represent the weakest segments, where passive listening or simple redirection mechanisms combined with large-scale access expose exchanged packets to the most important risks. This threatens the confidentiality of users' private information, which can have significant consequences (theft of identity, malicious use of banking information, economic espionage). Eavesdropping on the core segments is a more complex operation to carry out, yet it offers both the possibility to access more private data and to access information about network configuration, which can eventually be used to launch more critical attacks. Legacy Internet system mitigate these attacks by relying on link-layer (e.g. WPA), network layer (IPsec) or applicative layer (SSL) encryption of exchanged data. All of these solutions will be used in the IoT world: 802.15.4 AES security, IPsec-capable chips, SSL over NXP systems. Yet resource limitations of these systems may lead to the use of weaker encryption algorithms, or may require that certain key management schemes be avoided. For example, static configuration might have to be used because Diffie-Hellman- or asymmetric-cryptography- based systems would not be adequate. These systems are also explicitly targeted by dedicated attacks (e.g. [433]).

6.2.1.2.3 Malicious Software

The whole picture of viruses and worms has changed in the last years. Destructive viruses have become less frequent, while dormant Trojan horses are being widely used as means for criminal profit organisation to get access to large groups of compromised nodes, which can eventually be resold, or used for illegal purpose (e.g. spam). Worms, on the other hand, are now exploiting the large applications diversity of web 2.0 (e.g. twitter) and may involve interaction with the user for propagating. While the reduced interaction with human users may lessen their probability of occurrence, both of these threats would have critical impact on an IoT infrastructure especially on resource limited devices, which may not support the burden of malicious code. Besides, IoT systems are likely to be targeted, for at least three reasons. First, they will represent the majority of Internet connected nodes in a near future, and will therefore be seen as a large pool of useful resource. Second, they are likely to be deployed in critical environment with little human monitoring. Third, they will be difficult to patch, should a flaw be identified in their operating system. Even if a remote software update is present, this update system itself would be a target of choice for a hacker.

6.2.2 Security in peripheral networks and autoID

As the peripheral networks and data-collection systems aim to collect and transport sensible and sometimes critical data, security concerns are raised. From an architectural point of view, the security of the peripheral part of data collection systems reflects the current trend of having vertical, silos-like

solutions. As such, security features implementations are technology/standard specific and usually are not integrated at system level. This is generally a consequence of the fact that embedded devices have limited processing and communication capabilities, which translates in the fact that a) PKI cannot be used b) long keys cannot be used for cryptography/signing on embedded devices. For these reasons, we can state that, usually, current data-collection systems have different security implementations for the peripheral part and for the transport one, providing no end-to-end security support.

The availability of wireless communication technology has greatly improved the ease of deployment in data-collection systems. The wide adoption of wireless solutions in data collection systems has greatly eased their deployment overcoming physical limitations related to the weaving of cables needed for the network infrastructure. From a security point of view though, wireless systems have an intrinsic downside: they use a shared physical medium for communication. To share the air as physical medium means that attackers can easily and anonymously obtain access to packets sent over the air from far away and with minimum costs. Moreover, connection/network access becomes both a critical and, unfortunately, a vulnerable process. For these reasons, in this chapter focus will be put on analyzing the security of wireless systems.

Even for those wireless data-collection devices that provide security features, there is another common issue: in such systems there is no trusted actor (i.e. device) by default. The process of defining a trusted actor and sharing the “secret” (i.e. key), subsequently used for authentication or encryption, is a critical and vulnerable one. Because of its utter importance, it must be done in a safe environment which generally means connecting to the devices physically (by cable) or wirelessly in a safe environment. Moreover, in such systems, keys are usually network-/system-wide, which means that compromising one node, will compromise all the network/system.

The systems employing wireless communication are subject to a large number of attacks. These could be functionally characterized as pertaining to one or more of the following groups.

6.2.2.1 Security of RFID systems

RFID systems are now widely used in the fields of identification/authentication and goods tracking. By essence, these systems are highly sensitive to security issues, especially in the fields of access control, user's privacy and availability. This sensitivity is further exacerbated if one considers the scenarios (industry, asset management, access restriction) in which these systems are employed.

Confusing identification with authentication, many companies actually lowered their physical security level when they adopted an RFID-based system for controlling access to their facilities, with unsecure RFID tags used to authenticate the employees / visitors. In addition, the privacy of the tags carriers can be compromised if the access to stored data is not tightly controlled itself. Finally, the availability of the system can be compromised if the tag is remotely destroyed or if the communication between the tag and the reader is disrupted.

This section reviews the various attacks that can be carried out against RFID systems.

Threat	Requirements	Targets	Approaches
Eavesdropping	Advanced reading device	User's private data	Encryption
Skimming	Expensive listen/transmit equipment (the more distant, the more expensive)	User's private /authenticating data	Shielding, encryption, blocking tag
Denial of service attack	Jamming equipment, blocking tag	Tag ↔ reader communication	
Relay attack	Malicious tag & reader (easier in case of NXP)	Authentication result	Synchronization
Man in the middle attack	Malicious tag & reader	Authentication result	Synchronization
Side-channel attack	Very accurate physical eavesdropping equipment	User's private data	
Hardware destruction	Large electromagnetic instrumentation	Tag	Built-in protective electronic components (limited efficiency)

6.2.2.1.1 Weaknesses of the contactless link

The contactless link has some features which add threats to the communication compared to the security of a smartcard or even to the security of a wireless device.

One characteristic of RFID is of course the distance over the air between the reader and the card which opens the door to the possibility to spy the transactions or to relay them.

The fact that contactless devices have no ON/OFF switch on board due to the remote powering is also a weakness for security and privacy since an attacker can easily discreetly read a card without your consent.

Finally, the last specific characteristic of RFID is the requirement of a singulation or anti-collision protocol to perform communications with several RFID devices in the reader field. Those protocols can be easily block generating denials of service.

All the potential threats over the RFID systems are discussed in the following part.

6.2.2.1.2 Physical attacks on RFID

Eavesdropping on the communication

The eavesdropping attack, see Figure 23, is to listen to a private transaction between a reader and a card without the consent of the protagonists in the intention to uncover secrets. This attack is called passive because it does not act on the RFID system. The attack at the physical layer is one of the easiest to achieve because it requires very little equipment: a simple field probe and an oscilloscope may be sufficient to recover signals from several meters away. Frames retrieved during an eavesdropping attack will be used to retrieve information. These frames can also be used as part of a replay attack. It is of course possible to produce more complex eavesdropping systems with signal processing in software such as Matlab. Numerous publications deal with this attack, but very few give the test methodology used to obtain their results.

The first results were published in 2004 by the NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) [367]. NIST researchers were able to retrieve confidential data on a passport located 9m from their spy probe. The equipment used by this team was a commercial reader with a specific antenna. However, the article gives very little information on test methodology and results. In view of the listening distance found by NIST, they have only recovered the data transmitted from the reader to the card. Their results also show that the ISO14443 type B would be more susceptible to attacks than the ISO14443 type A.

In [367], researchers from BSI (German Federal Office for Information Technology Security Information) show that it is possible to listen to communications between an RFID reader NXP card

Figure 23 Eavesdropping Attack

(ISO14443 type A) by standing at 2 m from the reader. The reader antenna and antenna system are placed on second Gauss listening position.

The FOIS (Federal Office for Information Security) report in 2004 on the risks associated with RFID communications [367]. This report does not really show experiments but includes a survey on the issue appeared in different articles. Some anti-collision protocols are an advantage for the attacker as these protocols often repeat the ID of the card. Theoretical evaluation based on the power transmission between the reader and the card, shows that the listening distance of the uplink can reach a few tens of meters while listening to the downlink cannot exceed five times the nominal distance running in the context of a communication at 135 kHz and 13.56MHz.

In 2006 [372] researchers Guerrieri and Novotny from NIST conduct experiments on the two positions of Gauss, and manage to spy an RFID communication to a 15m distance for the uplink in the second Gauss position and to a 6.5m distance in the first position of Gauss. All tests are performed with a NXP Pegoda reader complying with ISO14443 Type A standard.

In [368] and [375], the author presents various results of attacks on the physical layer and especially eavesdropping attack. This publication remains the most precise level of testing methodology. The distances found are 4m for the uplink and downlink. The paper unfortunately lack of results and the results found by Hancke are not exploited enough, see Figure 24.

Figure 24: Signals published by Hancke

In 2008 [370], G. Hancke published a new paper on Eavesdropping attack. This document complements the first by adding more performance and better use of stored data. G. Hancke investigated the attack for the different standards operating at 13.56 MHz with a test methodology extensively studied, see Figure 25. The antenna is placed on first Gauss listening position at different distances from the transmitting antenna. The signal is then acquired on a computer for processing.

Figure 25 Experimental Method

Table 7 shows the results obtained by Hancke for different standards at 13.56MHz for the uplink and downlink.

	ISO14443-A et ISO15693	ISO14443-B
Reader to card	> 10 m	3 m
Card to reader	1 m	3 m

Table 7 Results obtained by Hancke

Skimming

Skimming entails two functions that are usually in conflict: we need an antenna with a high quality factor for generating a high magnetic field with minimum of dissipated power, however, at the same time, we need a large bandwidth and so a weaker quality coefficient for modulating the field and sending commands. These two operations can be made with separated devices equipped with distinct antennas but they must operate with the same clock.

Figure 26 Skimming attack

As with passive listening, we must watch out for spectacular announces. For instance, a Flexilis team claimed at Defcon'05 to have set a new world record of passively reading a contactless card from 69 feet. In fact, they used an UHF chip and not a ISO-14443 device.

In the Kroninger study [378], energizing a contactless card at 50 cm distance is hardly feasible. However, energizing at 1 m is impossible, because dissipated power grows with the cube of distance. If we need only 0.5W for energizing a contactless card at a distance of 5 cm, we need 500 W at 50 cm, which is not easily achieved using portable power appliances. At 5 m, we would need 500 kW. Thus, it would not only be a problem of portable power generation, but also a hazardous exercise for the attacker.

We can also find practical values in publications describing the realization of relay attacks. Z. Kfir and A. Wool [377][379], University of Tel Aviv, evaluate a simulated reading distance of 40 to 50 cm. From this study, I. Kirchenbaum and A. Wool [376] build a demonstrator, easily made for less than 100\$, which is able to read a contactless card from 35 cm afar.

6.2.2.1.3 RFID Denial of service

The goal of denial of service attacks is to somehow deny a given service (e.g. identification) to valid users. Denial of service attacks are easy to accomplish and difficult to guard against. They can be divided into the three categories:

- [1] Interferences in the anti-collision protocols: blocker tag and RFID guardian. If they are devices to protect the privacy of users they are also potential means for denials of service.
- [2] Reader- and card jamming
- [3] Faraday cage

The cases of the destruction of the tag or the reader and the fraudulent use of the “kill” command will be addressed in a specific paragraph.

6.2.2.1.4 The blocker tag

Juels et al. [Jue03] developed a device that blocks the tree-walking singulation protocol and prevents intrusive readers from query the UIDs of the tags we may carry. The idea of the blocker tag is to emit both a ‘0’ and a ‘1’ during singulation, creating a collision and forcing the reader to branch on each and every branching point during its singulation algorithm. By emitting simultaneously a ‘0’ and a ‘1’ (which requires two antennas) at each node of the tree, the reader can never complete its algorithm, and so never finds out if the protected entity possess the tag with the protected UID.

As a consequence, the consumer is protected against unwanted scanning. However, the blocker can not only be used as a protection device but also as a device that could potentially help an attacker generating a denial of service in a legitimate system. We can even assume that a blocker tag is always malicious since it cannot be selective and forbids the reading of one tag whereas it authorizes the reading of others. For example, if UIDs beginning with a ‘0’ are blocked, then the reader may never get around to reading UIDs beginning with a ‘1’.

The blocker tag works like as a passive tag: it needs to be in the reader field for it to work, and will protect only a small volume around itself.

6.2.2.1.5 The RFID Guardian

The RFID Guardian is an active device that can be part of a mobile phone or a PDA that the user carries with him. It can stop any pervasive reading by actively emitting a jamming signal in the sidebands of a typical RFID tag. Such a device can have multiple functions:

- Information can be sent to the reader or to the tag for secret key management, authentication, access control
- Monitoring of the RFID environment to warn of possible unsolicited reading
- Creation of collisions to prevent from the possible inquisitive reading

The RFID guardian can be a very useful tool to ensure our privacy. Naturally, by the same virtue it is also an efficient device to carry out a denial of service attack.

Whereas the blocker tag is designed to carry out a simple load modulation, the RFID guardian [381][382][384][385] is an active device that requires batteries and thus is able to emit its own signal. As a consequence, its effective area of protection is much larger, about 50 cm in radius [381]:

“The comparatively tiny sidebands have approximately 90 decibels less power than the reader-generated carrier signal, and this is the reason why RFID tag responses often have such a limited transmission range.

The secret to creating fake tag responses is to generate the two sideband frequencies, and use them to send back properly-encoded responses, that are synchronized with the RFID reader’s clock signal. The simplest way to generate these sidebands is to imitate an RFID tag, by turning on and off a load resistor with the correct timing. The disadvantage of this approach is that passive modulation of the reader signal will saddle our fake tag response with identical range limitations as real RFID tags (~10 cm for our test setup).

A superior alternative is to use battery power to generate the two sideband frequencies. These super-powerful sidebands are detectable at far greater distances, thus increasing the transmission range of our fake tag response.

The RFID Guardian prototype utilizes the “active” tag spoofing approach. The following figure shows the signal generated by our tag transmitter. The spoofed “sidebands” are transmitted at a power level roughly equal to the reader’s carrier signal. This has increased the range of our fake tag responses – from 10 cm to a half meter away!”

This smart jamming can also be selective and can make the reader think that certain tags are absent from its field. Thus, in a ALOHA anticollision protocol, the RFID Guardian is able to determine the time-slot where those tags will answer and then to emit a jamming signal in those time-slot to create a collision and to prevent from the inquisitive reader to understand the UIDs of the protected tags.

Figure 27: Selectively jamming of Tag 2 with the RFID Guardian. Since we increase the number of collisions, the singulation protocol is slowed down but the reader will be able to read all the permitted tags contrary to the blocker tag. However, in case of the use by an attacker, it can be imagined that a collision is created in every time-slot and in every round. Then, a denial of service is generated with a full blocking of the reader [381].

6.2.2.1.6 Reader and card jamming

The jamming attack is often mentioned in numerous papers without being fully detailed. The idea is to emit a signal in the same bandwidth as the reader or the tag in order to blur the transmission between the reader and the tag.

Considering that this attack presents no ingenuity in the noise emitted or in the period it is emitted, the only constraint is to flood the reader or tag signal in a higher level noise. The maximal level of emitted magnetic field is already restricted in international agreements. The ETSI EN300-330 describes a template of magnetic emission at 10 m around 13.56 MHz. According to the following figure, it is illegal to emit more than 20 dB μ A/m at 10 m in the 13.56 MHz frequency.

As a consequence, any attacker that is able to pass this limitation is sure to create an efficient jamming of a RFID reader. Exceeding the standard does not necessarily mean that the jamming signal requires a lot of power, however. If the noisy emission is in the exact bandwidth of the reader signal, only a few watts (1 to 2 W) are enough. To blur a tag signal is even easier since its signal is much lower than the reader's.

Figure 28: ETSI EN300-330 13.56 MHz magnetic field strength limit at 10 metres measurement distance. A higher signal in the bandwidth will blur the communication.

6.2.2.1.7 Shielding and using a Faraday cage

A basic solution to prevent from a reader to read our contactless card or RFID tags is to shield them by confining them in a wallet made of a metallic sheet or mesh. This wallet plays the part of a Faraday cage blocking the HF and UHF radio signals of readers. To be efficient against HF electromagnetic waves, the thickness of the metallic sheet should be greater than 20 μm for a metal with a good conductivity like copper or aluminum. Considering the metallic mesh, the period of the grid should have a length around half of the wavelength.

This solution is cheap, efficient and is not based on a complex technology. As a consequence, it is a very reliable way to ensure the security of contactless devices while not in use. There exists a large supply of this kind of wallets on the Web [454].

Figure 29: Wallets with metallic shield

6.2.2.1.8 Relay attack

The relay attack is based on a specific weakness of the contactless smartcards or RFID tags: the possibility to activate the device without the consent of the user. Currently, there exist no RFIDs that can be simply switched off by their owners. Thus an attacker can access the card discreetly, without

knowledge of its owner, and relay information through a communication link between the card and a remote reader. The reader will assume that the card, and by implication the user, is in close vicinity and will allow secure transactions to take place that should only be carried out by consent of the cardholder.

Even if the attacker is not able to view in plaintext any communications that take place, this is not needed as long as he can continue relaying the respective messages. The attack can be further enhanced by relaying the initial authentication sequence after which subsequent data is modified before relay.

Figure 30: Principle of the relay attack

Relay attacks involve two different devices and as a consequence two attackers that must coordinate their actions, except if the relay is really short (an arm's length for example). The device that will skim the data off the attacked person is named the "leech", though the term "mole" is sometimes also used. The leech is linked via the relay to the "ghost" (also named "the proxy"), a fake card that will reproduce the data of the genuine card.

To define the features of a relay attack, three different parts should be characterized: the leech, the ghost and the relay between them. The leech is a skimmer that has to activate and power the attacked contactless card and to communicate with it. Skimming a card is an attack in itself and is already intensively discussed in this document. The leech-to-tag reading distance could be up to 50 cm [379] by supplying enough current in a specifically designed antenna and by employing intelligent signal processing.

The ghost is able to eavesdrop on the communication with a genuine reader and to talk back to it. The eavesdropping on the communication is also well documented in this document. Concerning the fake card response, active modulation could be used instead of a load modulation that requires a close coupling and so a short range. [379] assesses that the ghost-to-reader distance could be as far as 50 meters. However, no realization lets us confirm such a distance. The RFID guardian [381] that has to provide the same functionality has a 1 meter operating distance.

The ghost and the leech are not specific to the relay attack since they are used for skimming or eavesdropping on the communication. The main challenge to be overcome during the relay attack is the fact that relaying data introduces delay into the system. It is therefore pertinent to consider the timing constraints in the original system. ISO 14443-3 specifies timing requirements to maintain bit synchronization during the anti-collision process. Response time is specified as $(n \times 128 + 84) / f_c$ if the last data bit sent by the reader was '1' and $(n \times 128 + 20) / f_c$ if the last data bit sent was '0'. Response times are calculated using $n = 9$ for REQA and SELECT commands, and $n \geq 9$ for all other commands. The minimum timeout defined for REQA commands is $7000 \times f_c - 500 \mu s$. ISO 14443-4 specifies the FrameWaiting Time (FWT) as $(256 \times 16 / f_c) \times 2FWI$, where FWI is a value from 0 (FWT = 300 μs) to 14 (FWT = 5 s) with a default of 4 (FWT = 4.8 ms). The FWI value is defined by the card in its ATS response. The Frame Waiting Time defines an upper bound, and a modern communication

channel should be able to forward a few data frames in 5 s. Therefore the anti-collision timing constraints are more of a concern, especially since the responses are ordered to a bit grid, resulting in the card only answering when the information is due, after 91 μ s and 86 μ s respectively. An idle reader transmits REQA commands periodically and as a result the ghost held to the reader requests information from the leech with the same regularity until the leech is within range of the targeted card. The minimum response timing (86 μ s) opens the door to a large number of communication protocols and modulations: GSM, TCP/IP with WIFI, in authorized radio bands. The more useful is the NFC standard developed for mobile phones where the three required components are available in the same device: the RFID reader, the RFID card and the communication relay with GSM (or even WIFI in smartphone) [379]. All those communication protocols always implement a modulation and bit coding that are different from the RFID standards. Therefore they require adapting a stream bit coding that can take time. [371] shows in their implementation that this double adaptation (from the ghost to the relay and from the relay to the leech) introduces a timing delay from 15 to 20 μ s that does not disturb the service.

The different developments point out the low cost of such an attack: it could require less than 200 €. However, this cost could be drastically reduced if the relay is just a wire that transmits along a short distance (around 1 meter) the bit stream with only an amplification of the signal, since an adaptation of the modulation and of the bit coding is no longer required.

With its capability of attacking from a long distance without the consent of the user and of bypassing the encryption of the contactless transaction, the relay attack appears to be one of the main threats for RFID systems.

In literature, we distinguish two kinds of relay attacks:

Mafia fraud: prover (the tag) and verifier (the reader) are honest. The attacker only relays the messages.

Terrorist fraud: prover is honest but the verifier collaborates with the attacker.

6.2.2.1.9 Man in the middle attack

The “Man in the middle” attack is often mistaken for the relay attack. They are indeed similar but with the distinctive feature that in this attack the bits stream can be modified during the relay. Since the relay implies the adaptation of the modulation and of the bit coding by the leech or the ghost for its use, it is not a challenge to change arbitrary bits. This additional feature may take time but it will always be shorter than the 5 seconds timeout of the reader. However, by changing the data transferred, the opportunity to bypass the encryption of the transaction that exists in the relay attack disappears. Thus, if the communication is ciphered, the attacker should know the secret keys of the algorithm to change the data. Two stages are then required: the decoding with the known key (that requires another kind of attack to be retrieve), the coding of the modified plaintext. The 5 seconds timeout is obviously enough to compute any cryptographic algorithm even with asymmetric keys.

6.2.2.1.10 Side channel attacks on the contactless interface

Besides the SPA (simple power analysis) and DPA (differential power analysis) which use the signal of the power supply to retrieve cryptographic keys, there is another technique used exclusively in contactless technology: RFA (Radio Frequency Analysis).

Indeed, the carrier of the RF communication is modulated (the signal is really weak) by the consumption of the chip and so the statistical tools used for SPA and DPA can be performed on the RF signal during a secure protocol to catch the computed cryptographic keys.

This attack implies a really accurate eavesdropping attack which can only be monitor in a laboratory.

6.2.2.1.11 Destruction

This attack consists in making definitively unusable a contactless card, but it can concern the reader, too.

Although this attack threatens contactless system availability, it is different from the denial of service attack because once performed, it is irreversible.

Destruction is considered as an attack when it is practiced without the holder's consent but it is privacy protection if a card is definitively destroyed with the consent of its holder in order to protect its data from any future attacks.

We can distinguish two destruction types: material destruction and software destruction. As this state of the art talks exclusively about contactless RFIDs, only distance material destructions are treated.

6.2.2.1.12 Material destruction

Destruction appears rarely in literature unlike chip self-destruction in response to chemical, mechanical, etc. attacks practiced directly on the chip and described in patents.

The BSI report compares contactless chips with EAS (anti-theft) which can be used at stores' cash desks. A strong magnetic field can induce a high voltage on the chip and an electrical failure or a

warm-up of input stage. Protections, such as Zener diodes or self-healing fuses, can be integrated but the effect will always be limited by the available chip area. There is no absolute protection against destruction by electromagnetic field. On the other hand, generating a strong magnetic field requires a large instrumentation [388].

Some publications give the microwave oven as a tool for destroying a contactless chip. Of course, this method can only be used to destroy one's own tags.

6.2.2.1.13 Software destruction

As in the previous case, there are not many publications on this subject. Software destruction needs commands allowing definitive card inhibition of the card, just like the "kill" command in the EPC standard. It is quite easy to protect against this threat using an authentication process but the RFD then becomes more complicated. We must use either keys, passwords or other methods to authenticate the destructive command [387][388].

6.2.2.1.14 Counterfeiting, substitution and replay attack

Numerous attacks on contactless cards or RFID tags require counterfeit cards. For example, a skimming attack can enable the dumping of the entire memory of the attacked chip and then a duplication of this memory in a customized card could be a real security hazard. Thus, as anybody can easily buy on the Internet any card from any manufacturer (ST, ASK, TI, ...), that has a microprocessor which can be easily programmed, this hazard is very real.

It is also possible to substitute a RFID tag on an item with another tag of a cheaper item or with a tag that is totally reprogrammed with an aforementioned chip. The difficulty is then often to reproduce the packaging of the tag that can contain holograms (e.g. credit card), signature, magnetic tapes, barcode and optical signatures. The solution is then often to tamper with the chip and replace it with a reprogrammed one.

6.2.2.1.15 NFC

While Near Field Communications (NFC) systems generally exhibit the same vulnerabilities as RFID systems, they may also be targeted with some specific attacks, related to their use cases, their inner architectures and their technical capabilities. These attacks are presented in what follows.

Figure 31: NFC sub-systems and interfaces

User Tracking

The unique identifier of an NFC can be tracked by malicious users nearby as the owner of the NFC device moves around. This kind of attack against user's privacy is as relevant as it is with RFID scenarios. It may actually be worse if one considers that an NFC device (mobile phone) is more likely to be almost always carried with a user, and may therefore disclose information on a regular basis. The use of random UIDs is of course an efficient way of countering this attack.

Relay Attacks

The classical relay attack against RFID systems becomes easier to carry out through the use of NFC systems, which make available to users generic tag/reader functions. Hence, two NFC devices can be

used to mount a relay attack, the first one plying the role of the reader and the second one playing the role of the tag.

Confidentiality

Communications between NFC devices are typically not secured (neither encryption nor authentication service) and may therefore be subject to eavesdropping or data forging attacks. A solution is to provide security at a higher level (e.g. SSL communications). It must be noted that some manufacturers such as NXP with Mifare or Sony with Felica do provide native (proprietary) encryption for the NFC communication.

Remote interaction with the secure element (SIM Card)

NFC devices allow the secure element (e.g. USIM) to be accessed from the NFC controller through an SWP (Single Wire Protocol) or S2C (Signal-in Signal-out Connection) interface. Read/write access to sensitive information (e.g. tickets, money) could be especially harmful to the user.

Attack against host applications / Malicious host applications

An NFC device receiving NDEF information from another NFC device would launch an application to process the received data. Vulnerable non-secure applications would allow an attacker to gain control of the application processor, which would result in various possible attacks against the device (reboot of the system, disclosure of sensitive data...). Compromised or malicious applications could also access / alter the data stored on the secure element, if the authentication system they use is either absent or inefficient [388]. The interface between the application processor and the secure element is needed e.g. to perform non-NFC, over the air transactions. In addition to providing (secured) access to the secure element, this interface allows any application to access the list of applets stored in the secure element without restrictions. This represents a privacy issue for the user.

Phishing attacks

The NFC functionality of a mobile phone could be used to enhance the browsing experience of a user, by letting him start visiting a website immediately after touching an NFC tag, without manually entering a long URL first. Likewise, phone number information stored on a tag can help the user to quickly dial a number from his mobile phone, without having to enter it manually. These use cases are highly vulnerable to phishing attacks, where an attacker would have replaced the correct URL with a malicious one (e.g. fake bank website) or the correct phone number with a premium rate phone number [456]. While the user is offered the possibility to inspect the retrieved content (URL, phone number) before accessing it, a majority would implicitly trust this information.

Viral Attack

The fact that an NFC device is able to establish bidirectional communications with its peers make it especially vulnerable to viral attacks where a worm propagates from device to device. The attack can be especially simple to carry out. For example in [456], a proof of concept worm was designed and implemented; this worm would simply erase the content of any URI NDEF tag it would detect, and replace the original content with a link pointing to a copy of itself. Then, any unaware phone reading the tag afterwards would be asked to download and execute the now malicious URL target, with a high probability of acceptance.

6.2.2.2 Wireless Sensor and Actuator Networks

Wireless Sensor and Actuator Networks (WSAN) devices are usually battery-powered (unlike passive RFID) and thus have longer communication ranges. Unfortunately, current technology can provide power for operating these devices with long range specifications for only a limited time. In this scenario, battery power is both a constraint to security features that consume energy and a critical resource that can indirectly be the target of attacks. In this section we analyse the security threats to which WSANs are subject. Some threats (specifically Jamming, Tampering and Eavesdropping) have not been addressed as they were already analyzed in the previous section concerning RFID.

Layer	Threat	Requirements	Targets ¹⁹	Approaches
Transport	Ping/ICMP flood	attacker being part of the network, ICMP	All connected devices	
	Synflood	TCP, attacker being part of the network	All connected devices	

¹⁹ Type of affected networks or devices

Network	Neighbor discovery attack	Neighbor Discovery protocol	Networks using unauthenticated ND protocol	Authentication support for ND protocols
	Wormhole	Mesh networking	Multihop wireless networks	Specific hardware, time constraints on packet delivery
	Black hole	Attacker being part of the network	Multihop wireless networks	Don't use plain distance-vector based protocols.
Link	Spoofing	-	All networks, especially wireless	Packet authentication
	Eavesdropping	-	Wireless networks	Encryption
	DoS - Collision	-	Wireless networks	Use UWB, increase datarate
	DoS - Exhaustion	-	Embedded wireless networks	Link-layer Intrusion detection
	Replay protection att.	Replay protection	Multihop wireless networks	RANBAR, Tesla
Physical	Tampering	Physical availability of device	All devices	
	Jamming	-	All wireless devices	

6.2.2.2.1 ICMP flood

Requirements: malicious node must be part of the network, network using ICMP

ICMP flood is a class of attacks, ideally leading to a denial-of-service, that can be performed by sending a huge amount of ICMP packets.

An example is the **ping flood**, where the attacker sends ICMP echo request packets (ping) consuming incoming bandwidth and CPU time on the target, which while responding will consume also outgoing bandwidth and additional CPU time. Spoofing the source address of the packet will prevent the target from consuming incoming bandwidth on the attacker. In order to maximize the efficiency of this attack it is often performed in a coordinated way from multiple malicious hosts.

This attack seems gaining back potential in the IoT domain, in particular in WSN, being an effective way to consume CPU time and power and being bandwidth quite a scarce resource.

Another ICMP flood technique is the **smurf attack** [184], in which the IP of the target is used as a source IP for an echo request to a number of hosts in the network which will answer with an ICMP echo reply each, consuming incoming bandwidth and CPU time on the target. This attack is dangerous because it doesn't require to have any control on the hosts that will be used, and it is extremely difficult to trace, because ICMP echo request packets are usually not logged, filtered or even taken into account from intrusion detection systems.

In the simpler case the attacker needs to carry out the attack from a machine with more outgoing bandwidth than the incoming bandwidth of the target, but in other cases the attacker relies on botnets or coordination agents. Stacheldraht [185] (in German it means barbed-wire) has been one of the first and better well known DDoS agent, it is an evolution of TFN and Trinoo, and in 1999 it was embedding a lot of techniques that are still present in current botnets, and among of his features the most disruptive was the smurf attack.

While these attacks could seem obsolete in the Internet, there is the need to consider their impact on WSN and IoT.

ICMP is only one category of **flood attacks** which is peculiar because of its features of firewall evasion, but due to the common lack of firewall in IoT probably any flood can be considered similar, ranging from a simple **UDP flood** using DNSSEC as an amplifier (potentially disruptive on the Internet) to the evasive TCP **XMAS flood**.

6.2.2.2.2 SYN flood

Requirements: malicious node must be part of the network

When an application or a client attempts to establish a TCP connection [184], client and server exchange a sequence of messages following the procedure called three-way handshake. The messages are the following:

- the client sends a packet with the SYN flag set to 1 and a sequence number (SEQ), this is called SYN message;

- the server after the reception sends a packet with both the SYN and the ACK flags set to 1 and uses the SEQ number incremented by one as acknowledge number and an unrelated number as SEQ number, this is called SYN-ACK message;
- the client upon the reception of the SYN-ACK message, creates a packet that uses the SEQ number included incremented by one as acknowledge number, with the SYN flag set to 0 and the ACK flag set to 1. This is called ACK message and the reception of such a packet on the server means the connection is open on both sides.

Back in 1996, a number of "underground magazines" and, then, CERT [188] pointed out how it was possible to exploit such a message sequence in order to cause a denial of service on the server.

At the time, it was common for servers to allocate resources to the connection upon the reception of the SYN message on the server. In case of a fixed length queue it was possible to send a number of SYN messages equal to the length of the queue to fill it up and render the server unable to host other "half opened" connections. In case of dynamic allocation of such a queue the effect can be as dramatic as memory exhaustion of the server.

In order to mitigate [187] or even prevent, such kind of attacks Daniel J. Bernstein promptly proposed a fix that is not breaking any compatibility with TCP. This fix consists in the utilization of cookies carrying the information needed for a full open connection instead of the establish of an half open connection in the server. This is achieved by crafting the 32 bits SEQ number of SYN-ACK messages containing such information. The exact, encoding is implementation dependent and the client doesn't need to be aware of it. Daniel J. Bernstein proposed the following scheme (which is the one implemented in the linux kernel):

- first 5 bits are an arbitrary number identifying a 64 seconds time window
- following 3 bits encoding over 8 possible values the MSS (maximum segment size)
- and in the last 24 bits are encoded in a way only the server can verify: IP addresses (client and server), ports (client and server) and the first 5 bits;

The rationale behind the SYN cookies is to allow the creating of a connection only upon the reception of ACK message while not enabling new potential issues (ACK flooding).

SYN cookies typically are not used by default, even if they are implemented in the majority of TCP stacks, because of inherent limitations, namely:

- inability to store TCP options
- inability to deal with selective acknowledge
- limitations on the MSS possible values (in the linux implementation only 8 values are possible)
- if the final ACK is lost the connection freezes and this can lead to a consequences more dramatic than TCP without cookies due the life span of the cookie

In order to overcome some of this limitations new implementations (available, for instance, on Linux 2.6.26 and FreeBSD 7.0), exploiting the optional Timestamp field of SYN messages, emerged. A limitation of this technique is that it can only be used if the SYN itself contains a Timestamp option, an option that seems to be widely implemented today, and hosts that support window scaling and SACK typically support timestamps as well.

Syn cache is another approach to mitigate SYN flood effect. It has been proposed in 2002 by Lemon [189]. It consist in storing in an hash bucket only partial information about the half opened connection. It is more challenging to fill an hash bucket than a normal queue and having proper rules to purge caches even during an heavy SYN flood users can experience only small degradations of service.

Lemon proposed also hybrid techniques of SYN cache and SYN cookies, for instance, upon the filling of the cache the reaction can be to switch to SYN cookies instead of purging.

WSAN protocol stacks seems to be more exposed to SYN flood than normal protocol stacks, due to inherent low resources.

It is safe to assume that both SYN cache and SYN cookies requires computing overhead due to the various hashing involved, but they seem still preferable to a TCP stack without any protection against SYN flood, in particular considering memory scarcity affecting IoT devices.

6.2.2.2.3 Neighbor Discovery Attacks

Requirements: A Network Discovery Protocol, malicious node must be part of the network

Self-configuration capabilities in wireless ad-hoc networks are based on Neighborhood Discovery (ND) protocols. The nodes of such networks use these protocols to gather information about the topology of the network and to organize routing. ND protocols use broadcast packets to properly set up the network in the initial deployment and to assess which nodes can be reached directly without the need of a router. **Attacks to the ND protocols** usually rely on making target nodes believe they provide network functionalities (e.g. they are the closest router) in order to alter the proper perception of the network topology and disrupt network traffic, possibly overloading a target node.

The IPv6 Neighbor Discovery Protocol uses Internet Control Message Protocol Version 6 (ICMPv6) to support Router Discovery, Auto-Configuration of Addresses, Neighbor Un-reachability Detection (NUD protocol), IPv6 Address to Link Layer Resolution, Duplicate Address Detection and Redirection. NDP features are more rich than IPv4 equivalent set. Moreover, NDP does not feature by default any security features, which makes it vulnerable to a set of attacks.

Figure 32: Redirect attack router advertisements from legitimate and malicious nodes

In the **IPv6 Redirect Attack** [190] represented in Figure 32, a malicious node redirects packets away from last hop router (R, the router closer on the link to the target node) or other legitimate receiver to another node on the link (generally the target). This can be achieved by tricking target nodes (A, C) on the link to accept itself as default router. In order to do this, the malicious node will multi/unicast forged Router Advertisements in response to Router Advertisement Solicitations from the newly connected target hosts. The malicious node must continue to send Advertisements in order for the attack not to fail due to router expiration.

This attack is not a concern if the access to the link is restricted to trusted nodes (Corporate Internet NDP Trust Model as defined in RFC 3756 [191]). However, in the largely wireless-communication-based IoT, this issue is significant as nodes usually cannot trust other nodes at Network Layer (**Ad-Hoc Network** NDP Trust Model).

SEcure Neighbor Discovery (SEND) [192] provides security mechanisms in order to address the threats identified in [191]. It provides Processing rules and a security architecture based on Certificates and Authorizations in order to secure the IPv6 ND protocol.

6.2.2.2.4 Black hole attack

Requirements: malicious node must be part of the network

Distance-vector based protocols provide another easy avenue for an even more effective DoS attack. Nodes advertise zero-cost routes to every other node, forming routing black holes within the network [193]. A Black hole attack impacts on the network by stealing all packets for a given node or a group of nodes which thus are lost. As their advertisement propagates, the network routes more traffic in their direction. In addition to disrupting message delivery, this causes intense resource contention around the malicious node as neighbours compete for limited bandwidth. These neighbours may themselves be exhausted prematurely, causing a hole or partition in the network. Although nodes can detect a black-hole attack more easily than they can detect greed, neglect, or misdirection attacks, a black-hole attack is more disruptive. Other nodes with untainted knowledge of the network topology may suspect inconsistent advertisements. The most effective countermeasure is not to use plain distance-vector based protocols [194].

6.2.2.2.5 Wormhole Attacks

Requirements: multihop wireless network

Wormhole attack is a replay attack, in which an attacker simply registers a route advertisement packet in the geographical proximity of the node (call it E) emitting such a packet and replaying it at a different

location, out of the range of node E. This attack can have disruptive consequences on the routing behaviour of the network.

In the above figure (Figure 33) a wormhole attack is carried out. The normal path from A to E would be A -> B -> C -> D -> E built from routing advertisement packets. If M1 capture a packet emitted from E advertising his presence, and it transfer the packet to M2 (out of band or whichever other mean) and M2 replays the packet advertising E presence A will try to communicate directly to E.

Figure 33: Wormhole attack scheme

Wormhole attacks are particularly dangerous because they do not require an attacker to gain the control of a node, to compromise wireless nodes or to be able to inject a node inside the network. This attack does not require to modify the content of a packet either. In order to be able to carry out such an attack it is enough to have a mean to register a packet and a mean to replay it.

Hu spoke about wormhole attack for the first time in INFOCOM 2003 [195], calling wormhole attacks generally the tunneling over a faster "tunnel", but he pointed out how disruptive this technique could have been against DSR or AODV routing mechanisms.

Since 2003 a number of solutions have been proposed according to specific requirements against wormhole attacks, some solution relying on cryptography, other solutions relying on geographical or timing information. A majority of solutions even requiring additional hardware to be implemented like by adopting synchronized clocks, positioning devices, or directional antennas, which we will not take into account.

In 2005 Khalil et al. presented LITEWORP [197]. LITEWORP, which is a lightweight countermeasure for the wormhole attack, does not require any of the previously mentioned specialized hardware. LITEWORP focused in particular to resource-constrained multihop wireless networks, such as sensor networks. It seems the effort has been presented for static networks and never expanded to mobile networks.

In 2006, Eriksson et al [198], from UC Riverside presented TrueLink, a timing based countermeasure to wormhole attacks. TrueLink performs link verification between two nodes A and B in two phases: the rendezvous phase, and the authentication phase. In the former, A and B exchange nonces B_a and A_b , where the subscript indicates the node that generated the nonce. This exchange proves the adjacency of the responding node through the use of strict timing constraints; only a direct neighbor is able to respond in time. In the authentication phase, A and B each sign and transmit the message (B_a, A_b) , mutually authenticating themselves as the originator of their respective nonce. The timing constraints of the rendezvous phase makes TrueLink immune to capture and replay style wormhole attacks, and strictly limits the range of attacks based on "wormhole" intended as a faster communication means.

6.2.2.2.6 Link Layer DoS

There are three typical ways to deliver Link Layer DoS attacks. Such attacks are well described in [196], which is a complete resource for these type of attacks.

In **Collision Attacks**, the attacker listens on the WPAN channel it intends to disrupt and, when it discerns that a message is being sent, it sends out its own signal so that it would combine (and interfere) with the legitimate one. Nodes listening on that channel will receive the altered transmission that can't be interpreted into a message, as it will likely fail the CRC check. The attack wastes network bandwidth and depletes the nodes' battery supplies. Error connection techniques can only mitigate this situation.

In **Exhaustion Attacks**, the attacker must be part of the attacked wireless network and leverages its Collision Avoidance features to exhaust the other nodes. The malicious device continually sends a Request to Send (RTS) packets to the target node as if it wanted to reserve the usage of the medium. The target replies with a Clear to Send (CTS) packets and waits awake (without going in sleep mode) for the announced message which never arrives. This attack wastes bandwidth and can provoke starvation and power depletion of the other nodes. If authentication could be supported at Link Layer level, this vulnerability would be mitigated as CTSs would not be sent and devices wouldn't be prevented from entering sleep mode.

The **Denial-of-Sleep** Attack is actually a class of attacks that aim at keeping target devices awake, not allowing them to enter sleep mode in order to save battery life. As the wireless medium is shared and the Link layer cannot provide authentication features, malicious nodes could send a set of techniques to provoke the exhaustion of the target's battery supply. Note that simply receiving a message from the air interface depletes as much battery power as sending. All the following actions can achieve this goal, beyond causing other issues to the network: injecting uni-/broadcasting messages, replaying messages, sending control packets.

Such attacks are specific and relevant for networks of embedded device. Authentication at Link Layer could mitigate the relevance of some of the threats, but this would drastically affect the bandwidth of wireless embedded devices.

6.2.2.7 Replay and spoofing attacks in WNSs

Another way of corrupting wireless sensor is by manipulating the contained data or in case the data is allocated (e.g. summed up) by replaying the same data a second time. This kind of attacks is called **replay attacks** and could be easily prevented through digital signage of the package which also includes a sequence number to detect replays. But the cost regarding computing power or energy needed might be too high for wireless sensor for straightforward solutions.

In **spoofing attacks** the attacker sends forged packets masquerading them as coming from a different source. This usually involves the alteration of packet headers and can be performed at different layers of the stack. Spoofing can be used in Man-in-the-Middle attacks in order to impersonate another node. RANBAR is an algorithm based on RANSAC (RANDOM SAMPLE CONSENSUS) [199] which provides an outlier elimination technology usable for sensor networks in order to address spoofing. Unlike other algorithms no prior assumption on the data is needed except that it is independent and identically distributed in case no attacks are present. Thus RANBAR allows the detection of attacks present, but does not prevent them.

As providing the proof that a message is authentic might be too time consuming for real time applications, the TESLA protocol [200] postpones the sending of this information, providing only the data and sends the prove of authenticity later. Problems related to the packet order could not occur in a broadcast network, but may arise in case the packet order is not always assured.

6.2.2.3 The SENSEI approach

The SENSEI project worked on security for wireless sensor networks looking at security solutions for node management, connectivity, and middleware [476]. A Secure Code Update solution is used for securing the code dissemination protocols Synapse++ [477] or Rateless Deluge [478]. This solution is the first secure code update solution that uses Fountain Codes for more efficient code dissemination on the network. The first solutions using Fountain Codes were subject to pollution attacks and it is challenging to secure this propagation technique. To improve the network connectivity, solutions for Jamming Mitigation and Secure Routing have been developed [479]. Node Capture and Replication Detection components [480] enable the detection of node captures and node replications which would endanger the connectivity. These solutions are particularly important to achieve security in WS&AN islands when they are deployed in public environments and not protected against physical access. If higher costs are tolerable, smart cards can be integrated in the sensors as a tamperproof hardware component to provide a generic security for achieving resilience against physical attacks. This trusted hardware component can be used to defend against a broad range of security threats resulted from node compromise attacks in WS&ANs. As a middleware solution, the data aggregation in sensor networks has been improved. FAIR [481] is a secure middleware component for resilient in-network data processing. It provides data integrity and evaluates the quality of information that is a prerequisite for SENSEI context processing. FAIR enhanced the state-of-the-art by being able to remain

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operational even under attack. The protocol gives an estimate of the quality of the information provided.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable D1.1 provided a description of the state of the art on technologies participating in the Internet of Things universe. In particular it addressed the existing architecture and framework solutions in Section 1, the latest modelling techniques for IoT in Section 2, the communication protocols in Section 3, the identification and resolution framework in Section 4, and the available IoT object platforms in Section 5.

The main overall conclusions which emerged from this activity are that the need for a common IoT framework is felt more and more urgent by the many stakeholders of the system. Also, the main players on the market need that none of their technologies will be excluded from the IoT-A. Finally, the process for ultimately provide a comprehensive IoT framework will go through three steps: a first chaotic period where many proposals will be drafted from both projects and the market, a second period where different standardization bodies will provide their interpretation on the IoT universe, finally, the third step will be decided by the market itself by defining the final aspect of the IoT. According to this report, nowadays we are in between the first two periods, as many solutions are available from projects, market and standardization bodies, however a unifying view on IoT is still to be achieved.

The next subsections provide conclusions for each of the sectors analyzed in the report.

7.1 Architecture

From an architecture perspectives, many solutions have been provided coming both from project, such as SENSEI, BRIDGE and CASAGRAS and from standardization bodies, such as IETF, ETSI and ISO. What clearly emerges from the background, is that at least two different communities are working on the definition of an architecture for the IoT, namely the WSA and the RFID sectors.

It will be one of the main task of the IoT architecture that of unify these two worlds and bring them into a consistent Web-enabled framework.

7.2 IoT modelling

This section illustrates that considerable amount of description languages, tools and standards are available for modelling services and processes. However, there is a certain gap with respect to IoT-Aware process modelling: existing process modelling languages lack features to express goal-oriented and event-driven interactions with IoT entities, processes and services. Nevertheless, we could identify that process modelling languages such as BPEL and BPMN 2.0 are promising candidates that we will consider for extension.

Many projects, e.g. SENSEI and SemProM, cover important orchestration aspects, but none of the surveyed projects provides a full solution for describing all aspects of IoT-Aware business processes. IoT-A will therefore re-use many of the described approaches and extend them for the IoT domain.

7.3 Communication protocols

With this report we covered a great deal of protocols, standards, solutions and projects for the communication among smart objects. Our main observation from the material that we have collected here is that a considerable amount of work still has to be done to deliver a comprehensive solution, one that will allow the different levels of a communication stack to interact, while allowing different technologies (possibly from different vendors) to communicate with one another and while also being compatible (even though with reduced performance) with native, and thus non-optimized, systems. IP-compatibility is clearly a must for such a solution, as the many on going standardization activities and projects show. For this, it might make sense to adopt (and adapt) existing standards such as 6LoWPAN, CORE and COAP. Much still has to be done in terms of security, for which threats have been pointed out but once again comprehensive solutions lack. Finally, an ideal protocol set for smart objects should include an adequate Transport protocol, which appears to be missing for embedded systems.

7.4 Identification and resolution frameworks

In this report we covered the state of the art regarding identification and resolution frameworks. Identification, naming and addressing provide the basis for the work in IoT-A. Entities of Interest, resources and services need to be identified and in the resolution process names and identifiers need to be resolved to addresses for accessing the services that can provide information about the Entities of Interest or enable the execution of business processes. It is clear that there are a number of different identification schemes that are highly relevant for the Internet of Things. IoT-A needs to find a solution that allows the integration of the heterogeneous identification schemes into the resolution

infrastructure. Resolution and discovery frameworks are the functional components that provide the resolution and discovery functionality. There are a number of different approaches for realizing the functionality and IoT-A needs to decide which best fits the requirements of the Internet of Things. An important aspect for allowing users to efficiently discover Entities of Interests and Services are index structures, which may have to be hierarchical or multi-dimensional, e.g., in the case of geographical coordinates. The distribution of these index structures in a distributed resolution infrastructure will be major challenge. Accessing the real world through the Entity of Interest abstraction requires the association of Entities of Interest (modelling Real World Entities) and the services providing information about them or allowing the execution of business processes. An important aspect for keeping the associations up-to-date, especially in the case of mobility, is the tracking of the location of Entities of Interests, and especially of the devices hosting the resources. With respect to privacy, the identity of the users involved in an IoT system is of special importance, therefore identity management frameworks have to be integrated.

7.5 Hardware

Overall, the material in this internal report provides a solid overview of existing blocks for 1) processing, 2) communication and 3) security. These will be the “lego blocks” of our WP5 demonstrators for the IOTA system. It is therefore crucial to have a solid compendium of them here, including guidelines for their adoption, pros and cons of each solution etc. Even through the review could not be comprehensive of all products in the market, it certainly contains the most widespread and commonly adopted ones. In fact, it has to be noted that there are many existing commercial products that are proprietary (i.e., whose technology is covered by patents and with no open specification/support available such as, e.g., Z-Wave). While we also reviewed some of the close products, in our future activity in IOTA we will tend using open standards

7.6 Security

The SOTA analysis describes a prohibitive scenario for what concerns the security of the IoT. The greatest threat to the IoT paradigm resides in the periphery of the network. Here, wireless communication is very difficult to secure due to the constrained bandwidth, processing and power resources of IoT devices.

The main threat here comes from the lower layers of the protocol stack (physical and link) of the peripheral wireless network/communication. Here no physical authentication can be provided and packets can be easily forged and replayed. Link-level authentication can mitigate the issue, but in turn impacts on the bandwidth available for application communication as well as processing capabilities and battery power. Moreover such systems usually require a pre-deployment key distribution or setup. It is thus evident that communication at the periphery of the network cannot be secured with the same standards as full-function devices. In order to provide the highest standard of security available in a given network trunk, the scalability of security features is suggested as a solution. As peripheral networks usually have a full-function device acting as gateway, and RFID systems usually can rely on reader systems that have less or no battery constraints, it is advisable that these devices provide the mechanisms for security scalability. This solution though must not be perceived as an improvement of the peripheral network security.

Beyond providing higher encryption standards on the core of IoT network, gateways could also support IoT- or application-level authentication and policy-based access management.

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